

ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY OF INDIA

ANNUAL REPORT

ON

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FOR

1975-76

**ANNUAL REPORT
ON
INDIAN EPIGRAPHY
FOR
1975-76**

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Do.	Do.	Tūmukuṇṭa	B 39-44
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Do.	Do.	Saugrām	D 258-60
Burdwan	Burdwan	Suātā	D 261-63
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Calcutta	Calcutta City	Calcutta	{ C 4110-11 D 265
Hooghly	Arambagh	Ārāmbāgh	D 266
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District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-Division	Place of Find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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Murshidabad	Murshidabad	Jangipur	
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Santhal	Rajmahal	Rājmahāl	} B 78 D 67-69

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Do.	Do.	New Delhi	

GOA

Goa	Goa	Panaji	B 89-90
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GUJARAT

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Topographical Index of Inscriptions—*Contd.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-Division	Place of Find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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Do. . .	Do. . .	Murukwāḍa . . .	B 138
Do. . .	Do. . .	Pāḷa . . .	B 139-43
Do. . .	Do. . .	Rāyapaṭṭaṇa . . .	B 144
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Tumkur . . .	Gubbi . . .	Kaḍaba . . .	B 148-50

KERALA

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Topographical Index of Inscriptions—*Contd.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-Division	Place of Find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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KERALA—*Concl'd.*

Trichur	Trichur	Oorakam	B 152-53
Do.	Do.	Trichūr	B 154-55

MADHYA PRADESH

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Hoshangabad	Hoshangabad	Hoshangābād	B 159 D 127
Indore	...	Sunel	C 4136-44
Mandasor	Garoth	Dasoria	C 4145
Do.	Do.	Garōth	C 4146-47
Do.	Do.	Haṇmatyā	C 4148-49
Do.	Do.	Mailkheda	C 4150
Morena	Morena	Mitāvali	C 4151-53
Rewa	...	Silahārā (near Dhārsāgar)	C 4154-59
Sehore	Budhni	Pāṅgurāria	B 160
Vidisha	...	Besnagar	C 4160-64
Do.	Basoda	Udaipur	B 161
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Amravati	Achalpur	Deūrvādā (Devalvādā)	D 129
Do.	Amravati	Amravati	B 164-65
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Topographical Index of Inscriptions—*Contd.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-Division	Place of Find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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Greater Bombay	Bombay city	Bombay	D 135-41
Nagpur	Nagpur	Nagpur	{ B 202-03 D 142-46
Do.	Sīndkhed-Raja	Sīndkhed Raja	B 204-07
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Do.	Yeola	Ankai Tankai	C 4167-72
Poona	Junnar	Junnār	C 4173
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Do.	Barmer	Bārmer	D 148
Do.	Siwana	Siwānā	D 149
Chitorgarh	Chitorgarh	Chitōrgarh	D 150-52
Jaipur	Jaipur	Āmber	{ B 208 D 153
Do.	Do.	Jaipur	D 154-55
Jaisalmer	Jaisalmer	Jaisalmer	D 156-60
Do.	Do.	Ladrovā	D 161
Do.	Phalodi	Phalodi	D 162
Do.	Pokaran	Pokaran	D 163
Jalore	Jalore	Jālore	D 164-65
Jodhpur	Jodhpur	Jodhpur	D 166-67
Kotah	...	Baḍvā	C 4175-76

Topographical Index of Inscriptions—*Contd.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-Division	Place of Find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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RAJASTHAN—*Concl'd.*

Nagaur	Didwana	Daulatpur	B 209
Do.	Jael	Barī-Khātu	D 168-70
Do.	Nagaur	Nāgaur	D 171-89
Do.	Parbatsar	Makrānā	D 190-94
Pali	Bali	Sēvāḍi	C 4177-78
Do.	Pali	Pāli	D 195-99
Do.	Sojat	Sojat	D 200-201
Sikar	Dantaramgarh	Jiṅ-Mātā	C 4179
Sirohi	Abu Road	Mount Ābu	C 4180-211

TAMIL NADU

Chingleput	Kanchipuram	Kāñchīpuram	B 210-11
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Do.	Do.	Erudukōṭṭai	B 215
Do.	Do.	Kāraṇḍapaḷli	B 216
Do.	Do.	Muchchandiram	B 217
Do.	Harur	Achchalavāḍi	B 218
Do.	Do.	Ellappuḍaiyānpaṭṭi	B 219
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Do.	Do.	Kīrapaṭṭi	B 221
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Do.	Do.	Meṇasi	B 223
Do.	Do.	Muttāṅūr	B 224-25
Do.	Do.	Pāppāmbāḍi	B 226
Do.	Do.	Periya Paṅṅimaḍuvu	B 227-28
Do.	Do.	Tīrthamalai	B 229-30
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Do.	Uttangarai	Mallāpuram	B 233-39
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Topographical Index of Inscriptions—*Contd.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-division	Place of find or deposit	Appendix and No.
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Do.	Do.	Kadirampatti	B 245-46
Do.	Do.	Koṇḍappanāyakkaṇ- patti	B 247
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UTTAR PRADESH			
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Allahabad	Manjhanpur	Pabhosā	C 4212
Bijnor	Bijnor	Bijnor	D 224
Do.	Do.	Chāndpur	D 225
Do.	Do.	Jahānābād (Ganj)	D 226
Do.	Do.	Maṇḍāwar	D 227-28
Do.	Do.	Ṭuṇḍpūrā	D 229
Etah	Aliganj	Aliganj	D 230-31
Do.	Jalesar	Jalesar	D 232-44
Do.	Kasganj	Kāsgaṅj	D 245-46
Jhansi	Lalitpur	Chandpur	C 4213
Lucknow	Lucknow	Lucknow	C 4214-15
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Topographical Index of Inscriptions -- *Concl.*

District	Taluk, Tahsil or Sub-division	Place of find or Deposit	Appendix and No.
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UTTAR PRADESH *Concl.*

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ANNUAL REPORT ON INDIAN EPIGRAPHY FOR THE YEAR 1975-76

INTRODUCTION

GENERAL

During the year under report, 3 copper-plate grants and 678 stone inscriptions were examined by the Epigraphical branch. Of these, the copper-plate charters are included in Appendix A. Appendix B contains 269 stone inscriptions, the majority of which were collected by the members of this branch. In Appendix C, continued from the previous year, are noticed 110 inscriptions. In Appendix D are included 299 Arabic and Persian Inscriptions examined by the Superintending Epigraphist for Arabic and Persian Inscriptions. Appendix E contains a list of the negatives of the photographs taken during this year.

I visited New Delhi and Madhya Pradesh and my collection includes Nos. B 79 and 160, the latter being an important inscription of Aśōka. Shri K.G. Krishnan, Superintending Epigraphist visited Andhra Pradesh and Goa and Nos. B 2-4, and 6-10 of his collection are noteworthy. Dr. S. Sankaranarayanan, Deputy Superintending Epigraphist visited Kerala and Tamil Nadu. His collection includes some interesting inscriptions like Nos. B 152, 210-11 and 259. Shri V.S. Subramaniam, Senior Epigraphical Assistant visited some villages in Tamil Nadu and his collection includes some important inscriptions like Nos. B-219-20, 222, 224 and 225. Shri C.R. Srinivasan, Epigraphical Assistant completed the village-wise survey of Tiruppattur Taluk in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu. No. B 247 of his collection is interesting. Shri M. Jayarama Sharma, Epigraphical Assistant visited many villages in Karnataka and his collection includes some important inscriptions like Nos. B 94-95 and 111. Dr. S. Subramonia Iyer, Epigraphical Assistant visited Bihar and Madhya Pradesh. Among his collections Nos. B 46, 72 and 161 are important. Dr. S.S. Ramachandra Murthy, Epigraphical Assistant visited the areas to be submerged in the Srisailem Project, Andhra Pradesh and Nos. B 33 and 37 of his collection are noteworthy.

The epigraphs examined in this office also include those received from the various circles of the Archaeological Survey of India and the Superintending Epigraphist for Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur. Besides, the Director of Museums, Government of Tamil Nadu, Madras, the Director of Archaeology and Museums, Government of Karnataka, Mysore and Dr. Mrs. Debala Mitra, Director (Monuments), Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi, were also good enough to place at our disposal epigraphs in their possession for our examination and report. Our thanks are due to them for their help in this regard.

The inscriptions listed in Appendix D were examined by the Superintending Epigraphist for Persian and Arabic Inscriptions, Archaeological Survey of India, Nagpur. Except for the impressions of a few of them, the rest were copied from different places in Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal, by Dr. Z.A. Desai, Superintending Epigraphist, assisted by Shri M.F. Khan, Senior Epigraphical Assistant and Shri S.S. Husain and Dr. M.Y. Quddusi, Epigraphical Assistants.

During the year under review, as in the previous years, facilities for doing research on Indian Epigraphy and allied subjects were provided for scholars like Cecilia Wittmann of the University of Chicago and Shri Ranganathacharyulu of the Osmania University.

Important inscriptions of the year's collection are reviewed below

COPPER PLATES

HOYSAḶAS.—No. A. 2 engraved on a set of copper-plates from the Director of Archaeology and Museums Mysore, Karnataka belongs to the reign of Vira Sōmēśvara who is stated to have issued the grant from his camp at Vikramapura. It is dated Śaka 1165, Śubhakṛit, *Dvītīya* Bhādrapada, Amāvāsya, Solar-eclipse, Sunday corresponding to 1242 A.D., September 26 and records a grant of the village Āneyakallavāḍi-mahāgrāma comprising four villages Chākarasana-viḍu, Mākabbeyahallī, Gurugujēyahallī and Maisūru in Koṅga-vishaya by the king to his general named Kambayyadaṇḍādhīpa, who in turn, is stated to have granted the same renamed as Kambapura, after his own, for the enjoyment of the brāhmanas. The village was divided into 120 *vṛittis*, out of which ten *vṛittis* were assigned as *sarvamānya* for the teaching of the *Vēdas* and to the deities of the village and the remaining 110 *vṛittis* to the brāhmanas, stipulating the payment of tax of 168 *gadyāṇas* and 3 *paṇas* permanently, into the royal treasury, as *kaṭṭu-guttage piṇḍ-ādāna* (lumpsum payment of rent) (See *Ep. Ind.*, Vol. XII, p. 145, n. 5).

This interesting record furnishes for the first time the genealogy of the king's general Kambayya, who is described as the son of Dēvapilla and Chīlādēvī and the grandson of Āditya, the ruler of Chāta in Toṇḍa-dēśa. This officer is stated to have served also Narasiṁha, the king's father.

INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS

MAURYAS.—No. B 160 from Pāṅgurāria, Budhni Tahsil, Sehore District, Madhya Pradesh is engraved in Prakrit language and Brāhmī characters on the boulders and on the adjoining rock face in a rock shelter. It contains a new version of Aśōka's first minor rock edict. The introductory part of the edict bears great comparison with the first minor rock edict as found in Brahmagiri, Siddāpura and Jaṭiṅga-Rāmēśvara. King Piyadasi addresses

Kumāra Śaṁva in the course of his pilgrimage to the U (O) puṁṁtha-vihāra in the Māṁṁmadēśa. It is known from the two separate rock edicts at Jaugāḁa and Dhauli in Orissa that Aśōka had stationed at Tōsalī in Orissa, at Ujjayinī in Madhya Pradesh and at Takshaśilā in the present Pakistan such *kumāras* to serve as governors in their respective provinces. Further, it is known from the Brahmagiri, Siddāpura and Jatiṁga-Rāmēśvara minor rock edicts that Aśōka had stationed another *Kumāra* at Suvarṁagiri. The present Pāṁgurāria minor rock edict discloses for the first time that Aśōka had stationed a *Kumāra* at a city somewhere near Pāṁgurāria to govern the area around and that his name was Śaṁva.

KUSHĀNAS.—No. B 79 engraved in mixed dialect and Brāhmī characters on a slab found in the course of excavations at Kaṁkāli Ṭilā, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh belongs to the reign of *Mahārāja Rājātirāja* Kanishka. It is dated in the year 5, Grīshma 4 and 10th day. It records that the stone on which the inscription is engraved is the gift of Viśākhaṁitā described as Paśini and Brahmanikā, the wife of Vasuka, the daughter in-law of Kṛishṁa-bala and the daughter of Budhila of the Nirvargga community belonging to Kottiyagaṁa, Brahmadaśiya-kula and [Jachivāgu]rita-śākhā for the merit of all sentient beings. It does not add any new information to the history of the period although it is another record belonging to the time of the king Kanishka. The important information furnished by this record is that the donatrix belonged to a community called Nirvargga community, known for the first time from this record.

WESTERN GAṄGAS.—No. B 220 in Tamil language engraved in Vaṁṁṁṁṁ characters of the eighth century on a hero-stone from Kattarasampatti, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu is dated in the forty-seventh year in the reign of Śivamāra and records that while Kanda Vāṁṁnadiaraiśar was ruling over Puṁamalai-nāḁu, Vāṁṁgachchaḁai[ya]ṁṁār [Vē]ṁṁṁṁṁṁ a servant of Teliyān-I[lai] āṁ died in the course of a battle at Kūḁal. Śivamāra is no doubt identical with the first king of that name since Śivamāra II is not known to have ruled beyond 23 years (above, 1972-73, No. B 279). The highest regnal year 34 so far known for this king, is obtained from Halligere plates (*Ep. Carn.*, Vol. III Md. 113). The present record dated in the 47th year happens to provide the latest date for him since very soon after this date in 725 A.D. Śrīpurusha ascended the throne.

No. B 224 is a hero-stone record from Muttāṁṁūr from the same district, Tamil Nadu. It is in Tamil language and Vaṁṁṁṁṁ characters of the 8th century. This record is dated in the fifteenth year in the reign of Siri Purisaparumar (i.e. Śrīpurusha?). It records that while Amaraḁakkiyār was ruling the western-division of Puṁamalai-nāḁu and when Kāmaiyanār of Veḁāl-nāḁu, undertook a cattle-raid at Koṁṁamaṁgalam, Vaḁamachchāttaṁṁār, a servant of Amaraḁakkiyār died. The western-division of Puṁamalai-nāḁu seems to cover the area around Kṛishṁagiri, Morappūr, etc.

PRITHVĪGAṄGAS OF PAṄGAḁA-NĀḁU.—No. B 222 from Mattiyampatti, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu is in Tamil language and Vaṁṁṁṁṁ characters of the 7th-8th centuries and is dated in the 57th year of the reign of

Kaṭṭiṇaiparumar. It refers to the rule of Kanda-Vāṇadi-araiyar over Puṇḍamalaināḍu and records the death of Vēḍachchāttanār, a servant of Amaranīlaiyār after rescuing the cattle in the course of a cattle-raid by Aruṭṭiraiyar. It is well-known that Kaṭṭiṇaiparumar belonged to the ruling family called Pṛithvīgaṅgas who held sway over Paṅgaḷa-nāḍu during this period (above 1972-73, Introduction, p. 5 and *ibid.*, 1973-74, Introd. p. 3).

Kanda-Vāṇadi-araiyar, the ruler of Puṇḍamalaināḍu belonged evidently to the same family to which his namesake, who was a feudatory under Śivamāra in the 8th century as mentioned above, belonged. The regnal year quoted in the record is the highest known so far, for Kaṭṭiṇaiparumar.

NOḶAMBAS.—No. B 225 from Muttāṇūr, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu in Tamil language and characters is dated in Śaka 847 and in the 2nd year of the reign of Aṇṇiyaṇ Vira-Nuḷamban. It records the death of Gāmuṇḍar Maḍaiyar Maṇiyamaṇṇār of Ponṇṇaiyūr in the course of a cattle-raid by the Vallavaraiyar and Nāṭṭār, after rescuing the cattle. The present record cites the regnal year of the king and also quotes the Śaka date, which is not met with in other Noḷamba inscriptions, which quote either of these two only. The Śaka date and the second year cited in this, which is equated with 925 A.D., confirms the suggested date of accession for Aṇṇiyaṇ Vira Nuḷamban as 923 A.D. (above 1968-69, Introduction, p. 5). While the identity of the chief Vallavaraiyar, whose name is not given, is obscure, his title reminds us of a similar title borne by the members of the Rāshtrakūṭa family.

RĀSHTRAKŪṬAS.—No. B 111 from Muttage, Bijapur District, Karnataka, belongs to the reign of Kannaradēva (Kṛishṇa III) dated in Śaka 886, 965 (A.D.). The record refers to the fact that Tarḍdavāḍi-1,000 division was bestowed upon Tailaparasa (i.e. Taila II of the Kalyāṇa Chālukya family) by the king. Even though Tailapa's rule over this division is attested to in inscriptions as early as 957 A.D., (*S.I.I.*, Vol. XVIII, No. 27) the fact that it was actually conferred upon him as a personal fief is recorded only in this and another, (*S.I.I.*, Vol. XI, pt. I, No. 40) both dated in Śaka 886. The latter inscription cited uses the expression (*aṇuga-jīvitam*). Taila II who bears the epithets as *Samadhigata pañchamahāśabda*, *mahāsāmantādhipati* and *Āhavamalla*, is stated to have conferred upon Rāchanayya, the office of *nālgāmuṇḍu* and made a grant of 12 *mattar* of land to a deity (name lost).

CHĀLUKYAS OF KALYĀṆA.—No. B 95 from Hampi, Bellary District, Karnataka, dated in Chālukya Vikrama year 1 (1076 A.D.) records a gift of 80 *lokki-gadyāṇa* in every year to the teachers who expound *purāṇas* in a *maṭha* (name lost) by *Mahāpradhāna Daṇḍanāyaka* Sōmēśvara-bhaṭṭōpādhyāya. He was also known as a subordinate under Sōmēśvara II in 1075 A.D., bearing the epithets as *Mahāsāmantādhipati*, *Daṇḍanāyaka*, *Mahāpradhāna*, *Hiresōndhivigrahi* and *Manevergaḍe* (see Fleet's: *Dynasties of Kanarese Districts*, p. 443).

HOYSAḶAS.—No. B 215 which is undated and engraved in Tamil characters of about the 12th century, from Erudukōṭṭai, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu, records the installation of the deity Chittiramēḷi-Viṇṇagar-emberumāṇ at

Eṛidakkōṭṭai in Kuṅṛappaṅṅu in Kallaga-nāḍu in Rājarājachōla-vaḷanāḍu, a sub-division of Muḍigonḍachōla-maṇḍalam by Āṇḍāl, the wife of Ejñamūrti, son of Āṭkoṇḍa-pillai of Vimbaṅṅūr-Māṅgālūr, for the merit of Mudaliyār Tarmattālvār (Dharmattālvār) *alias* Pūrādarāyaṅ (Pūrvādhirājaṅ) in the month of Aṛpaśi in the year Dundubhi. The chief is perhaps identical with his namesake Dharmattālvār, who is mentioned as the son of Tribhuvanamalla Pūrvādhirājar Atti-ālvār in a record from Hosūr dated Śaka 1183, Duṅmati (above 1969-70, Introduction, pp. 8 and 1970-71, Introduction p. 9) after which the year Dundubhi (Śaka 1184), the date of the present record follows.

No. B 216 from Kāraṇḍapaḷli in the same district dated Vibhava, Vaikāśi records that while Kaṅḍar Sūriyan Tribhuvanamalla Pūrādarāyan Tarmattālvār was ruling, and when Vichchūranpaḷli in Kuṅṛappaṅṅu was destroyed, men were taken captive (*chiṛai*) and cattle were lifted by Sāmidēvan of Periyaku[ri*]-chchi in Kallaga-nāḍu in Muraśu-nāḍu, a person (name lost) who is stated to be the son of Kāliyāṇḍī...pamma-gāmuṅḍaṅ died after rescuing the cattle. No. B 231 from Bennekāllu *alias* Tammāndra-paḷli, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu, which is dated also in Vibhava refers to the rule of this chief. These two records dated in Vibhava (Śaka 1190) may be assigned to the same chief mentioned in the record from Eṛidakkōṭṭai referred to above on account of the proximity of the dates. An inscription from Bidurugere, Bangalore District (*Ep. Carn.*, Vol. IX, Bn 94), dated in Rākshasa (Śaka 1178) refers to the rule of the chief Tribhuvanamalla Pūrvādarāyan Gaṅḍar-Sūriyan who is probably identical with his namesake of the present records. It may therefore be surmised that Kaṅḍar Sūriyan Tribhuvanamalla Pūrādirāyar Tarmattālvār ruled the areas around Denkanikōṭṭai and Hosūr as a Hoysala feudatory from Śaka 1178 to 1190.

KĀKATĪYAS.—No. B 37, in Sanskrit language and Telugu characters, is found engraved on a pillar in the *maṇḍapa* of the Sōmēśvara temple in Sōmaśila, Mahboobnagar District, Andhra Pradesh. It belongs to the reign of Pratāparudra and is dated in Śaka 1217 (1295 A.D.), expressed by chronogram *muni-chandra-akshi-ravi*, Manmatha, Kārttika 12 (*vaiśṇava-tithi*) Saturday. The details are irregular. It records the grant of a village called Prōlayapuri situated in Koṃḍūrudēśa by Bolla, who was the son of Rudradēva and the grandson of Bolla, and who was described as *Kākēta-sēnādhinātha*, to god Sōmanātha of Sōmaśilā for the merit of his father and the king. Though the family to which the donor, his father and grandfather belonged is not stated in the record, it may be surmised that they are of the Cheṛaku family, the chiefs of which are known to have been the subordinates of the Kākatiyas.

An inscription (*A.R. Ep.*, 1965, No. B 59) from Pusulūru, Kurnool District, dated Śaka 1210 (current), Sarvajit (1288-89 A.D.) refers to *mahāmaṇḍalēśvara* Bollayya-reḍḍi of the Cheṛaku family as ruling from Kandana-voḷalu. This inscription does not mention any overlord and therefore it is presumed that he ruled over the territory independently for a short period (*ibid.*, Intro. p. 13). It may not be unlikely that Bolla, the grandfather of his namesake of the present inscription is identical with *mahāmaṇḍalēśvara* Bollayya-reḍḍi of the Pusulūru inscription referred to above. Another inscription (No. B 33) in Telugu language and characters found engraved on a broken stone-

slab lying in a field in Pedda Marrūru, Mahboobnagar District, Andhra Pradesh and dated in Śaka 1221, Vikāri, Śrāvaṇa śu. 1, Wednesday, Simhasamkrānti, corresponding to 1299 A.D., July 29 records that a certain individual, whose name is partially lost, made a gift of bronze lamp-posts and 2 *khaṇḍugas* of land in Maṛūru for maintaining perpetual lamps in the temple of Brahmēśvara at Ālaṃpūru for the longevity and prosperity of *mahāsāmanta* Cheṛaku Yimmaḍi Bollayaṛaḍi. Another inscription (*A.R. Ep.*, 1939-40 to 1942-43) from Nandikōtkūr, Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh dated Śaka 1213, Khara (1291 A.D.) refers to Rudra, the son of *Mahāsāmanta* Cheṛaku *Manuma* Bollaya Redḍi. If the expressions *yimmaḍi* of the Pedda Marrūru inscription and *manuma* of the Nandikōtkūr inscription are considered together it may be surmised that the grandfather of this Bollaya also had the same name. Thus we get three Bollayas of alternate generations among the five chiefs of this family in the genealogical order as Bollaya, Pedda Devaya (*ibid.*, 1937-38, No. B 322), *yimmaḍi-manuma* Bollaya, Rudra and Bolla or Bollaya.

CHŌLAS.—Of the two Chōla inscriptions Nos. 259 and 262 from the E-Gauriyamman temple, Vallam, Tanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, one (No. B 262) dated in the 40th regnal year (946-47 A.D. of the Chōla king Parāntaka I records that Aṇantañ-kāri *alias* Pirāntaka-Muttaraiyaṅ of Vaḍakuḷat-Tuṛuppāḍi in Eriyūr-nāḍu set up a perpetual lamp to be burnt in front of the goddess Bhaṭṭāraki at Vallam and also granted 76 sheep for maintaining this lamp and that Kuvāvam-Piramaṅ received the sheep and agreed to supply one *uḷakku* of ghee daily to the lamp. The other inscription (No. B 259) commences with the *meykīrtti* of *Tirumagaḷpōla* etc., of Rājarāja I and it is dated in his 16th regnal year (1000-01 A.D.). It records that the members of the Pāraśava community living in the fort of the locality undertook to supply one *uḷakku* of ghee to be measured by the measure *Rājakēsari* out of the produce of their lands to burn a perpetual lamp to the goddess Kālā-piḍāri Kai-talai-pūśal-naṅgai of *Karuvugala* Vallam in Eriyūr-nāḍu. It is stated that when he was seated on his day-time throne at *Viṅṅanēri*, the king had already approved the above arrangement at the request of Kambaṅ Maṇiyaṅ *alias* Vikramaśiṅga Mūvēnda-vēḷaṅ. The name Kaṭtalaippūśalnaṅgai of the goddess meaning a fighting lady with (the enemy's) head in (her) hand is significant. For even now the goddess E-Gauriyamman is depicted in a fighting pose holding a human head in one hand and a sword in another.

No. B 242 from the Jaina temple complex at Tirumalai, Polur taluk, North Arcot District, in Tamil Nadu is fragmentary. It is dated in the 23rd regnal year and 175th day of a king whose name is not preserved but who is described as a famous *Sārvabhauma* or emperor. The epigraph seems to record an undertaking by the *ūrār* of a place (name lost) to supply commencing from the 22nd regnal year, a huge quantity of paddy to the Jaina temple on the Tirumalai at Vaigāvūr. The transaction is said to have been entered in the official register on the date of the record in the presence of some high officials or feudatories. Among them one named Rājēndraśōḷa-Māvali[vaṅarāya] and another Rājēndraśōḷa-Atimūrkkachcheṅḡirai are noteworthy. The former may be identified with his namesake who is described as a *sēnāpati* and who figures in an inscription from Tribhuvani in Pondicherry State (*A.R. Ep.*, 1919 No. 176) dated in the 30th regnal year of Rājādhiraḷa I (1048 A.D.) as a donor of lands to a temple for conducting worship in the name of the king Rājēndra [I].

The name Rājēndrasōḷ-Atimūrkkachcheṅgirai is met with in an inscription from Tiruvāliśvaram, Tirunelveli District dated in the 17th regnal year of Uḍaiyār Sundara-Chōlapāṇḍya (*S.I.I.*, Vol. XIV, No. 161) who was one of the viceroys of Rājēndra I himself. If these identifications are correct, then the *Sārvabhauma* of the record may be identified with Rājēndra I or perhaps with Rājādhirāja I. The palaeography of the epigraph also may support this suggestion.

Of the two inscriptions from the temple of the goddess Karukkiṇil-amarn-davaḷ at Kāñchīpuram, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu, the first one (No. B 210) is fragmentary as its beginning is lost. It records a tax free gift of land in favour of the goddess Bhaṭṭāraki of the temple by the *mahānagarattār* of Kachchippēḍu (i.e. Kāñchīpuram) following the order of the king (name lost) of the record, issued at the instance of [his queen] Kōdaip-pirāṭṭiyār and executed by Ālappākka Viśaiyanalluḷāṅ. While giving the details of the boundaries of the gift land the inscription speaks of the temples of Karukkamarnda Bhaṭṭāraki at Kiḍandaperumāḷsēri, Peruṅgōvaraiyar-taḷi, Lavaṇiśvara temple at Mahintrapāṭi. The imprecatory portion of the record contains a reference to the Kāmakkōṭṭam i.e., the temple of Kāmākshī at Kāñchī. The second record (No. B 211) commencing in continuation of the fourth line of the previous epigraph, is dated in the 13th regnal year of the king Uḍaiyār Rājēndra-Chōla who may be identified with Rājēndra I on the basis of the palaeography of the inscription. It records the royal order conferring the *archanābhōga* right of the temple hereditarily on Vichchādiraṅ Jñānaśiva-piḍāraṅ who had been enjoying that right in the temple of Karukkamarnda-piḍāriyār (i.e., the present goddess Karukkinilamarndavaḷ) at Kāñchīpuram.

It is very likely that the queen Kōdaip-pirāṭṭiyār of the first record was identical with her namesake who was one of the queens of the early Chōla king Ariṅjaya (c. 956-57) (*S.I.I.*, Vol. XIII, No. 225). Hence that record may be assigned to the time of the said Chōla king or one of his immediate successors. However, it may be observed that the characters of this record are not much different from that of the second record of Rājēndra I, which is also written in continuation of the first as already pointed out. Hence, it would appear that the original earlier record was re-engraved for some reason not recorded, during the time of Rājēndra I. Further it may be observed that the first of the two inscriptions under study is perhaps the earliest of the Kāñchīpuram inscriptions known so far, to speak of the Kāmakkōṭṭam.

MISCELLANEOUS.—No. B 94 engraved on a broken lime-stone block, discovered in front of Mahānavamidibba at Hampi, Bellary District, Karnataka is in Prakrit language and in characters of 1st and 2nd century A.D. It reads: line (1). *tarasa putasa*; line (2). *rā dānam*. The discovery of this inscription takes back the recorded antiquity of Hampi and its surroundings to the beginnings of the Christian era.

No. B 72 engraved in Sanskrit language and Siddhamātrikā characters of about the 7th-8th centuries A.D. on a stone slab originally discovered in the course of excavations at Nālandā, Bihar Sharif Sub-division, Nalanda District, Bihar, introduces a hitherto unknown ruling family who were Brahma-Kshatras

by caste and who hailed from Mathurā. The first ruler of that family was Bhāśiva. His son was Rāhila. He was followed by Prathamaśiva who was probably his younger brother. It appears that Prathamaśiva had another name viz. Pūrṇavarman. The inscription records that an image of Buddha was caused to be installed by king Pūrṇavarman. The text of the record was composed by *Sāndhivigrahika* Durgadatta who is described as having obtained the position of *Mahārāja* and was engraved by Mādhava, the son of *Nāgara-sūtradhāra* Vāmana. No. B 161 engraved in Sanskrit language and Nāgari characters of about the 10th century on a slab set up in the front wall of a disused old shrine near the Udayēśvara temple at Udaipur, Basoda Tahsil, Vidisha District, Madhya Pradesh contains an incomplete *praśasti* of the Sun god. This will show that the shrine in which the present inscription is found might probably have been dedicated to the Sun-god. The prevalence of the worship of the Sun-God in Madhya-Pradesh in the 10th-11th centuries A.D. is well known and there is another eulogy of the Sun god composed by the famous poet *Mahākavichakravartti Paṇḍita Chchhittapa* from Bhilsā (*Ep. Ind.*, Vol. XXX, p. 215 f. and plate).

An inscription (No. B 46) in corrupt Sanskrit language and Nāgarī characters of about the 11th century A.D., is engraved on the pedestal of an image of Tārā discovered during excavations at Antichak, Bhagalpur Sub-division and District, Bihar, records the gift of the image in question by *Paramōpāsaka pratihāra* Udayavara of the Mahāyāna school for the merit of his parents and all sentient beings beginning with the teachers (*āchāryō-opādhyāya*). This shows the prevalence of the Mahāyāna school of Buddhism and the popularity of the worship of Tārā in Bihar in 10th-11th centuries A.D., In this connection, it is worth mentioning of an inscription engraved on the pedestal of an image of Tārā originally discovered at Hilsā and now kept in the state Archaeological Museum at Patna belonging to the reign of the Pāla king Dēvapāla (see *JBORS.*, Vol. IX, p. 31 f. and plate).

No. B 241 from the Jaina temple at Tirumalai, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu is interesting as it appears to have been dated in Śaka year probably [8*]93. Like other inscriptions from the same locality (*A.R. Ep.*, 1887, Nos. 80-92, 1907, Nos. 65-69), the present record refers to the Sacred hill (Tirumalai) at Vaigavūr in the Paṅgala-nāḍu, and it seems to record a gift of 10 *kaḷaṅju* of gold by Anṇattaḍigaḷ *alias* Śatrukulāntakan to provide for the worship of the *yakshis* and the endowment was entrusted to the priests of the Paḷli i.e., the Jaina temple on the said hill.

No. B 152 from the Bhagavatī temple at Oorakam, Trichur Taluk and District Kerala is in Tamil language and Vaṭṭeḷuttu characters of about the 11th century A.D. It records the agreement made by the administrative body (*ūrār*) of the locality called *Puriyaṅūr* that assembled in the temple for the purpose. By this agreement the *ūrār* undertook to maintain nine daily services (specified) in the temple of the goddess Bhaṭāri. It is interesting to note that the list of such services includes the recitation of the *Bhārata* i.e. the *Mahābhārata* and the performance of dance-dramas (*kūttu*). Thus the record under question stands witness not only to the popularity of these two services in Kēraḷa during this period (cf. above, 1970-71, No. B 65) but also to the antiquity of the present Bhagavatī temple wherefrom the record comes.

No. B 247 from Koṇḍappanāyakkappaṭṭi, hamlet of Nariyanēri, Tirupattur Taluk, North Arcot District is engraved on a slab in a field on a cart-track. It is in Tamil characters of about the 12th century and records that it was a highway (*peru-vali*) of Adiyamāṇ and the distance to Nāvaṛṭāvaḷam is 29 *kādam* from the spot. Another rare instance of a milestone on a highway is already known to us from an inscription in similar characters on a slab from Pāpināyakanahalli in Dharmapuri Taluk, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu, which gives the same details (above, 1968-69, No. B 169 ; Introduction, p. 12). Thus we come to know from these inscriptions that the two places marked by the original position of these stones were situated on the famous highway connecting them with an important centre of trade.

ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS

During the year, no new record of the Delhi Sulṭāns came to light. But a few Khālji and Tughluq inscriptions published earlier were examined afresh. No. 115, from Peṭlād in Kaira district of Gujarat, recording the construction of a mosque in A.H. 713 (1313 A.D.) during the reign of 'Alau'd-Dīn Khālji and governorship of Alp Khān was published in *Ep. Ind.*, Mos., 1917-18, p. 33 (pl. XI b), where the fact that the slab had cracked and lost some portion in the middle rendering the proper decipherment of the name of the builder difficult, was not noticed. In the published text, the builder is stated to be Sayyidu'l-Umarā Ikhtiyāru'd-Dīn and he is identified with admiral or commander of sea, Ikhtiyāru'd-Daulat wa'd-Dīn Alp Khānī who died about three years later at Cambay (*ibid.*, pp. 33, 38). But the missing portion contained in the second line the *nisba* of the builder, of which only the last three letters *r m i* remain and which suggest to be al-Balāramī tentatively. Again in *ibid.*, p. 33, Badru'd-Dīn Dinār mentioned in the text as having seen through the construction, is mentioned as father of 'Alāu'd-Dīn's wife, which is incorrect; it is perhaps an inadvertant mistake, as Bayley's *History of Gujarat* (p. 40) on whose authority the relationship is indicated, calls him correctly the father-in-law of Alāu'd-Dīn's son Quṭbu'd-Dīn Mubārak Shāh (also, Diyāu'd-Dīn Baranī *Tārīkh-i-Firūz Shāhi*, Calcutta, 1862, p. 389). The present inscription provides new information about his having been a servant of Sayyidu'l-Umarā Ikhtiyāru'd-Dīn.

All the four Tughluq inscriptions listed this year, Nos. 57-58, 81, 114, are except one (No. 57), published. Of these, Nos. 57 and 58 from Bodhan in Nizamabad district of Andhra Pradesh, constitute one inscription, but at present *one* slab bearing No. 57 (which forms its concluding part) is fixed into the west wall of the mosque called 'Ālamgiri-Masjid, which is in the heart of the town, while the two pieces of No. 58 bearing the rest of the epigraph are lying loose in the old Shāhī or Deval Mosque now known as Patthar-ki-Masjid situated far away in the mud-fort of the town. The published version of this inscription (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1919-20, p. 17, pl. XVI b) is not only incomplete, but includes text referring to the parentage of the Sulṭān, viz. 'son of Tughluq Shāh a's-Sulṭān' which in fact does not belong to this inscription but to another inscription of the same monarch inscribed in the same hand, published alongside the present one (*ibid.*, p. 16, pl. XVI a; also, *A.R. Ep.*, 1962-63, No. 14 of Appendix D). No. 57, which supplies the latter, continuous, though not again

complete, part (the date portion is missing) of No. 58, is noticed here for the first time and helps us to correct the above mistake, which arose, very probably, due to the fact that the two epigraphs (Nos. 57-58 of this list and No. D, 14 of *A.R. Ep.*, 1962-63, referred to above), executed in the same style of writing but in slightly different sizes, were found carved 'on several pieces' then lying in the Deval mosque, though how and when the slab containing No. 57 came to be fixed in the 'Ālamgīrī-Masjid is not clear.

The only other Pre-Mughal record to be noticed is No. 84, from Delhi. A published record of Sikandar Lodī (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1919-20, p. 7, pl. III a), recording the construction of a tomb (*gumbad* in the text), is well preserved, but the builder's name was read earlier as Daulat Khān (with a few letters immediately thereafter) having been left unread. But according to our reading, the builder was a woman named Daulat Khātūn, the wife (*fūm* or *qaum* of Khwāja Muḥammad. There is a word after the name of the builder, the reading of which is not certain beyond doubt; it reads like Aḥsak, though its meaning or significance is not clear. But there is no doubt about the reading Daulat Khātūn and the word designating her marital status.

Of the Mughal emperors, the list contains quite a few records, the earliest being of Humāyūn, No. 124, a fragmentary record without date and others of Akbar, Shāh Jahān, Aurangzeb and some later Mughal emperors. Akbar's epigraph, No. 161, from Lodrovā in Jaisalmer district of Rajasthan, noticed earlier (*Jour. Bih. Res. Soc.*, XLII, 1956, p. 249), has been, on examination, found to contain one more visitor's record viz Mir Muḥammad Ma'ṣūm Nāmī, a number of inscriptions carved by whom in his extensive travels have been listed from time to time in these reports. The records of Shāh Jahān and Aurangzeb are mostly from Rajasthan and are of some interest. No. 191, of Shāh Jahān is from Makrānā in Nagaur district—the place which supplied marble for the Tāj-Maḥal built by that emperor. This is the earliest epigraph of Shāh Jahān from the place (for others see *A.R. Ep.*, 1962-63, Nos. 236-39 of Appendix D).

Aurangzeb's inscriptions from Rajasthan are more in number and found in such different parts of the state as Jaisalmer (No. 157), Pokaran, District Jaisalmer (No. 163), Bari Khāṭu (Nos. 169-70) and Nāgaur (No. 187) in Nagaur district and Sojat in Palī district (Nos. 200-01). These range in their dates from A.H. 1083 (1673 A.D.) and A.H. 1099 (1688 A.D.) and, like a number of his other records from Rajasthan, indicate the acknowledgement of Mughal authority over almost the entire region. Of these No. 163, from Pokaran, recording the construction of a bastion of the fort in A.H. 1092 (1681 A.D.), furnishes the name of the officer in charge of the fort, namely Imām Qulī during whose tenure the construction took place. This Imām Qulī is perhaps different from his more illustrious name-sake who had received the title of Āghar Khān in the beginning of Aurangzeb's reign and had seen active service in Sind in 1659 and later on in Afghanistan (*Ma'āthir-i-'Ālamgīrī*, Calcutta, 1871, pp. 16, 136, 145, 196). Similarly Nos. 200-01, from Sojat, record the construction of a mosque and a reservoir with a fountain in A.H. 1092 (1681-82 A.D.) by Sardār Khān. The builder appears to be a local official, but is not known from any other

source. Another local official of the reign of Aurangzeb finds mention in No. 252, from Jaurāsi in Saharanpur district of Uttar Pradesh, where he built a mosque in A.H. 1086 (1675 A.D.) by the orders of the emperor. No. 265, from Kālnā, in Burdwan district of West Bengal, now stored in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, a published record of Aurangzeb, was erroneously assigned by Maulavī Shamsu'd-Dīn Ahmad to Nāṣiru'd-Dīn Maḥmūd Shāh II of Bengal said to have ruled in A.H. 896/1490-91 A.D. (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1933-34, p. 2, pl. I a; *Insc. Beng.*, vol. IV, Rajshahi, 1960, p. 138). Subsequently, Professor 'Abdu'l-Karīm challenged this view, suggesting that the epigraph bears the name of Ruknu'd-Dīn Bārbak Shāh (*Jour. As. Soc. Pakistan*, vol. XIII, No. 3, pp. 321-23). The epigraph, as has been shown conclusively elsewhere (*Bānglā Desh Itihās Parishad*, Proceedings, Third History Congress, Dacca, 1973, pp. 47-48, refers itself neither to Nāṣiru'd-Dīn Maḥmūd II nor to his son Ruknu'd-Dīn Bārbak but to 'Nāṣiru'd-Dunyā wa'd-Dīn Āurang Shāh'—this name and the date A.H. 1080 given in words being clear beyond any doubt. There is no doubt that the inscription belongs to the reign of Aurangzeb; it was the title Nāṣiru'd-Dīn used for the emperor in place of his usual Muḥyū'd-Dīn and the inability to decipher correctly Aurang Shāh (which Professor 'Abdu'l-Karīm wrongly deciphered as Bārbak Shāh) and the inability of both to decipher the date given in words as *thamānīn wa alf* which are responsible for the confusion. Likewise, the published version of No. 258, from Saugrām in Birbhum district of West Bengal (*Jour. As. Soc. Ben.*, vol. XVIII, No. 5, 1924, p. 517), is full of too many mistakes including that of the date read there as A.H. 1064 instead of regnal year 46 of Aurangzeb corresponding to A.H. 1113-14 (1702-03 A.D.). The wrong readings of names, particularly Shāh Shujā' Kirmānī instead of Shāh Sayyid Raḥmān, are likely to create unnecessary confusion.

The provincial dynasties represented in the group are those of Bengal, Gujarat, Ahmadnagar, Bijapur and Golkonda. In the case of Bengal Sulṭāns, as many as seven—of which five are new—of the nine records belong to 'Alāu'd-Dīn Ḥusain Shāh. The remaining two, Nos. 273-74, are published epigraphs of Nāṣiru'd-Dīn Maḥmūd Shāh, of almost identical purport, from Jangipur in Murshīdabad district (*Insc. Beng.*, IV, pp. 50-51). Their published readings are correct, except for one serious mistake in the reading of the designation of the builder Khān-i-Mu'azzam Ulugh Sarfarāz Khān, in No. 274. The published text calls him *Wazīr-Dūn dar Sharq* translated as 'Minister of the Exterior in the East', while the correct reading of the designation is *Wazīr-i-Diwān dar Sharq*, i.e. Minister of the Chancery in the East.

The five new records of Ḥusain Shāh, Nos. 257 and 261-64, are from Birbhum and Burdwan districts. According to No. 257, from Sākulipur in Birbhum district, a water-tank (*siqāya*) was excavated in A.H. 916 (1510-11 A.D.) by the orders of the king. Since this is the fourth record to come to light mentioning the excavation of a water-tank in this particular year, the remaining three being from the nearby Burdwan district (*Insc. of Bengal*, vol. IV, pp. 184-86), it may be reasonably taken to indicate scarcity conditions prevalent in this region in the said year. The remaining four new records of this Sulṭān are from Burdwan district. Nos. 261-63, are from Suātā, and No. 264, is a fragmentary and damaged record from Raikha. The Suātā records which were brought to our notice by Shri Siddheswar Mukherjee of village Sreepat Muluk, District Birbhum, are particularly important; executed in the typical,

but not as usually fine bow-and-arrow variety of Bengal, they are the only epigraphs known so far in this style to furnish the name of the scribes. No. 261 was inscribed by one whose name reads like Naṣru'd-Dīn and Nos. 262-63, by Qāḍī Mīnāzī. No. 261 assigns the construction of a Jāmi' mosque to the king in A.H. 908 (1502-03 A.D.) and No. 262 invokes prayer for the long life of the king, which again is a unique feature in Bengal, and even perhaps Indian, inscriptions in Arabic; it also gives, among other honorific titles of Ḥusain Shāh, the political one of 'conqueror of Kāmṛū and Kāmtā' found in some of his inscriptions including No. 264. One more important record of this Sulṭān is No. 267, a published inscription from Garḥ Mandāran in Hooghly district (*Jour. As. Soc. Ben.*, vol. XIII, 1917, p. 134), re-examination of which brings out for the first time the name of a scion of the royal family, namely Shāhzāda Mubārak, who carried out the construction of the gate of the Tomb, obviously of the famous saint Shāh Isma'īl Ghāzī on which it is found, in A.H. 904 (1499 A.D.). As is well known, Husain Shāh had three sons, viz. Nāṣīru'd-Dīn Nuṣrat Shāh (1519-31 A.D.), Ghīyāthu'd-Dīn Maḥmūd Shāh (1532-38 A.D.) and Prince Dānyāl. The correct decipherment of the epigraph under review seems to suggest that he had a fourth son also, Mubārak by name; the prefix Shāhzāda (lit. born of the king) used with his name in the text which contains the name of the king, should firmly indicate this; it may be remembered that Dānyāl also has been so called in his record (*Insc. Beng.*, vol. IV, p. 154).

The list contains no new record of the Gujarat Sulṭāns. One of their two listed published records, No. 89, from Ahmadabad, is found to refer to the reconstruction and not construction of a mosque (*Mus. Mon. Ahmadabad*, pp. 79-80) by Mallū Sulṭānī in A.H. 955 (1548-49 A.D.) in the time of Maḥmūd Shāh III.

A new bilingual record of the Nizām Shāhī kings of Ahmadnagar, No. 142, came to light. Now stored in the Central Museum, Nagpur, its place of find is not known and the writing also is unfortunately too damaged to provide any clue either to its purport or to the building on which it was set up. It however seems to belong to the reign of Burhān II, during whose reign, it will be remembered, about a dozen bilingual direction records were put up in different parts of the Nizāmshāhī dominion (*Ep. Ind. Ar. Per. Sup.*, 1970, pp. 45-62).

The only 'Ādil Shāhī entry under No. 135 is a published record, dated A.H. 1062 (1651-52 A.D.) from Ḍābhol in Raṭnagiri district, now stored in the Prince of Wales Museum, Bombay (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1933-34, p. 10, pl. V a). A serious discrepancy in its otherwise correct published notice that has come to light on re-examination is that the local officer at Ḍābhol, namely Shaikh 'Alī, was the deputy not of the 'Ādil Shāhī king Muḥammad 'Ādil Shāh as stated there but of Afḍal, i.e. the Minister Afḍal Khān.

The Quṭb Shāhīs of Golkonḍa are represented in the present group by four epigraphs, Nos. 1-2, 49-50, of which two are new. Among the latter, No. 1, now stored in the office of the Conservation Assistant, Golkonḍā fort, is a record, unfortunately fragmentary, of Ibrāhīm Quṭb Shāh, dated in the eighties

of the tenth century A.H. ; it assigns the construction of a mosque to one Mīrzā Buzurg. Its last location, the boundary-wall of a step-well inside the fort of Golkonḍā, should perhaps indicate that the mosque was situated there. The other new inscription, No. 50, is from Shaikhpet, not far from Golkonḍā, recording the construction of a mosque in A.H. 1089 (1678-79 A.D.). It is significant that the text refers itself to the reign of, but does not name, the reigning king, the last of the Quṭb Shāhs, namely Abu'l-Hasan. Of the two published records, both of the time of Abdullāh Quṭb Shāh, the published version of No. 49, also from Shaikhpet (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1935-36, p. 22, pl. XIII), makes the curious mistake of reading the date given in figure under the chronogram as (A.H.) 1042 (1632-33 A.D.) and making it conform to the date yielded by the chronogram, which is incorrect. The chronogram works out to A.H. 1043 (1633-34 A.D.) and not A.H. 1042 (as further stressed in *ibid.*, f.n. 2) and the figure is also clearly A.H. 1043.

The miscellaneous epigraphs, not specifically referring to the name of the reigning monarchs, listed here, contain some really important records. Taking these statewise, of the epigraphs of Andhra Pradesh, No. 21, from Hyderabad, may be termed an important discovery. It purports to be the epitaph of a poet whose literary talents have been highly extolled. According to this, Kāmī, 'a flower of the garden of knowledge', 'having no equal', the 'Creator of Ideas', who has left the 'pearls of his poems' as his memento, left this world in A.H. 1045 (1635-36 A.D.). This contemporary epitaph of a poet spoken of in such glowing terms is an important contribution, particularly since precious little is known about the life of a vast majority of the Persian poets of India, and more so since in most cases, the dates of their death and their last resting-places are not known. Of the poets bearing this *nom-de-plume*—Kāmī Lāhījī, Kāmī Qazwīnī, Kāmī Sabzwārī (also called Qumī) and Kāmī Shīrāzī, the last mentioned is the only poet who is known to have lived into the second quarter of the seventh century, from his epic poem entitled *Waqā'i'u' z-Zamān* or *Fathnāma-i-Nūr Jahān Begam* composed in A.H. 1035/1625-26 A.D. (C.A. Storey, *Persian Literature*, vol. I, London 1927, p. 563). This Kāmī Shīrāzī is almost certainly the person of the epitaph under review. He must have migrated to the Quṭbshāhī court at Hyderabad in Deccan from the north, fearing the displeasure of Shāh Jahan, after the latter's accession in A.H. 1037 (1628 A.D.), for having been a panegyrist of the latter's deadly enemy Nūr Jahān, and here he must have died a few years later. Kāmī does not appear to be new to Deccan, as is indicated by his poems (*Majalla-i-Ulūm-i-Islāmiyya*, vol. I, No. 1, June 1960, pp. 59-63). A large number of other interesting epitaphs was found in the Dāira of Mīr Mu'min at Hyderabad, the necropolis of the elite, where lie buried a number of people, mostly Iranian settlers, belonging to different walks of life including state service. Apart from Kāmī, another celebrated Persian poet Mīrzā Abū Turāb Riḍawī Maṣḥhadī also rests here : his epitaph containing a poem by his more celebrated son Mīr Raḍī Dānish and another by another poet Muẓaffar Husain is represented by No. 20. No. 13 records the death of Sayyid Mīr-i-Mīrān. It is difficult to say if he is identical with Mīr Asadu'llāh entitled Mīr-i-Mīrān, the Mughal general who died of gun-shot at the first siege of Golkonḍā by Aurangzeb's son Prince Muḥammad in 1656, for the year of death in the epitaph which has considerably weathered is not legible—it reads like A.H. 1067 (1657 A.D.). No. 16 refers to the death of Amīr Rustam Jang Khān who died in A.H. 1164 (1750-51 A.D.). He cannot be traced in available records, but the text credits him with versatile erudition

and great position ; he is stated to be particularly well-versed in different sciences: No. 17 purports to be the epitaph of Ḥakīm Mirzā Aḥmad entitled Muḥammad Ghīyāthū'd-Dīn Khān Bahādur Ghīyāthū'd-Daula Gilānī who died in A.H. 1207 (1792-93 A.D.). He is a known person : he was appointed Kotwāl of the city of Hyderabad on 14th November 1782 (*The Chronology of Modern Hyderabad from 1720 to 1890 A.C.*, Hyderabad, 1954, p. 73). His genealogy quoted in the epitaph proclaims him to belong to an illustrious family of Iranian origin. Some of the other deceased of Iranian connections mentioned in the epitaphs, ranging in their dates from A.H. 1011 (1602 A.D.) to A.H. 1253 (1838 A.D.) are Āghā Ḥusain (No. 22), Mir Muḥammad Mu'in Tafrīshī (No. 32), Khwaja Idrāk (No. 37), Maulānā 'Abdu' ṣ-Ṣamad (No. 18), Mullā 'Alī Naqī Māzandarānī (No. 31), Ḥājī Shāh (No. 25), Mir Murtuḍā (No. 23), Muḥammad Ḥusain 'Adasī Shīrāzī (No. 35), Ḥayā Khānam (No. 19), Muḥammad Zamān Iṣfahānī (No. 38), Muḥammad Mu'min Iṣfahānī (No. 36), Sayyid Mir 'Abdu'l-Qādir Mūsawī Shīrāzī (No. 24) and Mirzā Kuchak Kāshānī (No. 43). Lastly, Nos. 61-63, from Zafargaḥ in Warangal district, engraved on guns, dated A.H. 1188 (1774-75 A.D.) and A.H. 1193 (1779-80 A.D.), give the name of their manufacturer or caster as Muḥammad Qāsim, who is evidently the same as the one who cast the two guns in the Ihtishāmgāḥ fort at Nirmal in Adilabad district. These last-mentioned guns do not contain any date (*A.R.Ep.*, 1968-69, Nos. 4-5 of Appendix D), but from the inscriptions under review, it is clear that they were cast about this time.

Most of the epigraphs from Bihar listed below have been published but not always correctly or completely, as for example in the case of No. 67 and No. 68, from Rājmahāl in Santhal Parganas district. No. 68 is not completely or correctly read (*Corp. Bihar*, p. 304, pl. 62 a) ; the mosque referred to in this record was constructed not in A.H. 1113 but in A.H. 1103 (1691-92 A.D.) given both in figure and chronogram and the composer was Ḥāfiẓ Jafar, left unread (*ibid.*).

From Delhi comes, which may be described an outstanding discovery there in recent years, No. 76, engraved on the foot-side of the grave locally marked as that of Khwāja Taqīu'd-Dīn Nūḥ, a nephew of the celebrated saint Ḥaḍrat Niẓamu'd-Dīn, is in fact, not his epitaph but that of Khwāja Mubashshīr, one of the principal personal attendants (like personal assistants or major-domos of our days) of the saint. Containing a two line text of two Persian couplets, it states that the deceased Khwāja Mubashshīr, the man of spirituality, again fastened his belt in A.H. 737 (1336-37 A.D.) in the service of his Spiritual Guide (who had pre-deceased him by 12 years). There is therefore no doubt that the grave in question covers the remains of the Khwāja, and the uninscribed grave situated in the enclosure immediately to the west of Amīr Khusraw's Tomb, shown as his (*List Hin. Mus. Mon. Delhi Province*, vol. II, p. 170) is not his, but somebody else's. It is rather surprising how this epigraph remained unnoticed so far—it is not noticed in the otherwise exhaustive and well-prepared List of Delhi monuments just referred. Equally astonishing is the fact that the inscription on the grave on the west in the enclosure of Princess Jahān Ārā, No. 80, has been published more than once, but its date has not been read so far, with the result that there has been speculation about the identity of the person buried there. The grave in question is stated to be that of Mirzā Nīlī son of Shāh 'Ālam (*Memoir Arch. Sur. Ind.*, No. 47, p. 29 ; *List Hin. Mus.*

Mon., II, p. 153), which is impossible, as the epitaph clearly bears the year A.H. 1016, long before Mīrzā Nīli was born. We may also notice here one aspect of three more epitaphs of Delhi likewise published or noticed more than once (*Memoir Arch. Sur. Ind.*, 47, pp. 24-25; *List Hind. Muh. Mon.*, II, p. 175). Nos. 73-75 are inscribed on the graves in the Tomb of emperor Akbar's foster-father Shamsu'd-Dīn Muḥammad Khān also known as Atga Khān. None of the three epitaphs mentions any name, and only one, No. 73, the date. However, the central grave is believed, and correctly too as will be presently seen, to be that of Atga Khān himself for whom the Tomb was built, and that on the east, dated A.H. 1009 (1600-01 A.D.), has been identified with that of his wife Jijī Anga, probably because it bears the mark of a female grave and usually the wife was buried by the side of the husband. The third grave has not been identified so far. However, with the help of its inscription, No. 75, we can say that this grave covers the remains of Atga Khān's eldest son Yūsuf Muḥammad Khān who died in A.H. 973 (1565-66 A.D.) hardly four years latter than his father. Thus the inscription neither mentions the name nor the date, but such is also the case with No. 74 occurring on Atga Khān's grave. The latter's identification is corroborated—a point that has not been taken note of so far—by the religious text inscribed on his grave, viz., Sura XCI, verses 1-9 beginning with the words *Wa'sh-Shams*, which allude to Atga Khān's name Shamsu'd-Dīn (Muḥammad Khān). On this analogy, the Quranic text—verses 53-56 of Chapter XII which is entitled Yūsuf (Joseph)—the verse 50 also has 'Yūsuf'—can be safely taken to allude to the name of the occupant of the unidentified grave as being Yūsuf (Muḥammad Khān). Incidentally, we have at least two contemporary instances of such allusions, at Dholpur in Rajasthan, for which see *A.R.Ep.*, 1972-73, p. 20).

The miscellaneous records of Gujarat listed here include both new finds as well published ones. Among the latter, No. 113, from Peṭlād in Kaira district, is the oldest of the entire collection listed in Appendix D. Recording the death of a saint Shaikhu'l-Mashā'ikh Arjun in A.H. 633 (1236 A.D.), its published text (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1915-16, p. 16, pl. XIV a) read one of his two *nisbas* as Damawī, interpreting it as meaning 'of Damo' which was identified with Damoh in the present Sagar district of Madhya Pradesh, and its editor was inclined to comment that 'Damoh did not become part of the Delhi kingdom until 1383 A.D., but Muslim influence had begun to permeate India much earlier than that and Arjun Shāh (or his ancestor) may have come in the wake of an early Muslim conqueror from the North-West and later on settled at Damoh' (*ibid.*, p. 15). According to our reading, the phrase read as 'Damawī' is 'bin Damū or Dammū'; that is to say, Damū or Dammū was the name of the saint's father. Also, the name of the scribe of this extremely elegant epigraph has now been completely deciphered. No. 94, from Ahmadabad, recording the construction of a mosque in A.H. 1063 (1652-53 A.D.) during the governorship of Shāista Khān was also published earlier (*Mus. Mon. Ahmadabad*, p. 89, No. XLV b, plate). But curiously, the name and post of the builder were taken there to be an attribute of God, translated as 'the Defender of the intellect' with the result that the builder of the mosque in question remained unknown. The builder is Idrāk the *Nazir* (Superintendent or Major-Domo). This Idrāk also constructed another mosque at Vaṭwā, near Ahmadabad, in the same year, according to *ibid.*, No. XLV a, where too the phrase giving the name etc. of the builder was similarly understood. That the

builder was named Idrāk is clear beyond any doubt from another inscription occurring on the mosque built by him at Burhanpur in Madhya Pradesh, three years earlier, when he was also Nāzīr of Shāista Khān ; he is spoken of there as Khawāja Idrāk (*A.R.Ep.*, 1956-57, No. 133 of Appendix D).

Among the new records of Gujarat, No. 87, also from Ahmadabad, though put up, in all probability in recent years, contains a long poem in mystic strain in Urdū, with Horī (i.e. Holi) as its theme, which must have been composed in or about A.H. 1109 (1697-98 A.D.) by the saint Bābā 'Abdu' ṣ-Ṣamad Khudā-Numā on whose mausoleum it occurs. No. 101, from Pālanpur, in Banaskantha district, is a rare example of the text in a local dialect, inscribed in Arabic characters. Noticed in an Urdu work on the history of that erstwhile state as early as in 1911, this bi-scriptal epigraph, if we may call it so, recording the repairs carried out to the Gate called Dīn-Dwār (Gate of Religion) by the chief Kamāl Khān in 1692-93 A.D., recalls to mind a similar epigraph of Jahāngīr's period, from Gujarat, also occurring on a Gate (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1939-40, p. 5, pl. I c ; *A.R.Ep.*, 1974-75, No. 46 of Appendix D). No. 95, also from Ahmadabad, assigns the construction of a mosque in A.H. 1133 (1720-21 A.D.) to Ṣalābat Khān of noble lineage, by whom very probably Ṣalābat Khān Bibī, later on Faujdār of Vikramgam and father of the first Nawwāb of Junagadh, Sher Khān (M.S. Commissariat, *History of Gujarat*, vol. II, 1957, pp. 203, 405, 432, 435, 550), is meant. Another new record, No. 104, from Cambay in Kaira district, is interesting in that it furnishes some direct information relating to times when Gujarat was passing through uneasy times due to various factors including the rise of Maratha power. The inscription forms the epitaph of Mīrzā Amīn Baig who is stated to have been killed in A.H. 1189 (1775 A.D.) in a battle with Rāghū who must be a Maratha chief. Unfortunately, no details like the site of the battle, etc., are available, but the Mīrzā seems to have been a member of the forces of the Cambay Nawwāb, and very likely, if the name and the title Mīrzā are any indication, his relation too.

The state of Maharashtra is represented by few records only, some of them published. No. 139, originally from Gālnā in Nasik district is now in the Prince of Wales Museum, Bombay. Its published version (*Ep. Ind. Mos.*, 1929-30, pp. 5-6, pl. IV a) invests the minister Dastūr Khān who built a *sarāi* in A.H. 895 (1489-90 A.D.) with the cognomen Mukrī, which is wrong ; the intended phrase is Mukramī meaning 'generous'. Not without interest is No. 146, from Nāgpur, an epitaph of an East India Company official, George Forester who had come to Nagpur from Calcutta as the agent of the Company probably to conduct negotiations with the Bhosale Rajas or to assess the political situation. He is stated to have died—of natural causes, it is significantly added—on the 15th January 1790 A.D. at a comparatively young age of 39. Forester is believed to have come to Nagpur in October 1787.

The miscellaneous epigraphs of Rajasthan to be mentioned here are few. Nos. 172-81, from Nāgaur, are fragments of stone sarcophagi which were recovered from the part of the wall of the Nagaur citadel-fort, which collapsed due to heavy rains a couple of years back. Unfortunately too fragmentary to

admit of any purport, they can be safely assigned, on palaeographical grounds, to the 13th-15th century. Quite a few more sarcophagi, in fragments or entire, are still found built up on the standing walls of the citadel as also the only surviving part of the city-wall on the north. No. 188, one such, recovered recently from the latter, provides important historical information. It formed epitaph of a man of high political status, namely Isfahsālār Asadu'd-Dīn, who died in A.H. 798 (1396 A.D.). The deceased is reported to be an Afghān originally from Bhakkar and was at the time of his death the governor (*Wā'ilī*) of the town of Sodhat or Sodhit (which cannot be identified at present). Asadu'd-Dīn seems to have belonged to an illustrious family for, his father Buddhū entitled Ikhtiyāru'd-Dīn is also spoken of as having held the rank or title of Isfahsālār.

This year too, quite a few new inscriptions were copied from Uttar Pradesh. Of these, No. 232, from Jalesar in Etah district is important in more than one respect: firstly it gives the date—A.H. 954 (1547 A.D.)—of the construction of the Tomb of a local saint whom the text calls Mīrān Sayyid Ibrāhīm. Secondly it provides the name of two officials, Masnad-i-'Alī Rustam Khān, during whose governorship the work was carried out and the *Shiqdār* (whose name reads like) Bīlak, who was his retainer or trusted servant, as his appellation Rustam Khānī suggests. It also indicates that Jelesar was, as of to-day—it gives name to a Tahsil—a *pargana*. However, it is rather surprising that a person of the position of the Masnad-i-'Alī—a title held by prominent noblemen under the Lodīs and Sūr monarchs, does not find mention in historical works. Another important record is No. 255, from Pirān Kalyar in Saharanpur district, which records the construction of the tomb of Rāi Sher Khān son of Aḥmad in A.H. 1011 (1603 A.D.). The identity of the Rāi cannot be established, but it can be safely presumed that he was a man of local importance and belonged to the family of Rajput converts of which the district had a considerable population. The epigraph also furnishes the name of the artisan who was responsible for the job, namely Ustād Bhajjū the carpenter (*Darūdgar*), who hailed from—another interesting piece of information—Chatoṛara-Sādāt. Likewise, No. 230 from Aliganj and Nos. 245-46, from Kāsganj, both in Etah district, referring to the foundation of Aliganj and the construction of two mosques respectively, by the same man Yāqūt Khān, are noticed here for the first time. According to No. 230, Aliganj was founded in A.H. 1143 (1730-31 A.D.), the architect or mason (*m'imār*) being one Muḥammad, while No. 245 from the Jāmi' mosque of Kāsganj records the construction, evidently of that mosque, in A.H. 1150 (1737-38 A.D.); this mosque is stated to have been built in Yāqūtganj which was obviously the name intended for Kasganj, but it does not seem to have caught on. The other inscription, No. 246, also refers to the town (*qaṣba*) as Yāqūtganj and records the construction of the mosque of its Sarāi, four years later. According to the account given in the district gazetteer, Yāqūt Khān, an official in the employ of Farrukhabad Nawwabs, was killed in the battle of Dori against the Rohillas in 1748 and was buried in the Fort at Aliganj (*Gazetteers of the United Provinces, Etah District*, pp. 347-48), where according to Shri M.F. Khan who copied the epigraph, only remains of his tomb exist.

That Jalesar entertained quite a few foreign, mostly Iranian, new-comers or visitors, as late as the last decade of the twelfth century Hijra (1778-1785 A.D.) is indicated by a number of epitaphs which are being noticed here for the first time. Their names etc. make an interesting study: No. 233 records the demise of 'Iwaḍ Baig Khān son of Karbalā'i, born at Dīwān Tappe, died A.H. 1192 (1778 A.D.); No. 234, of Riḍā Qulī Khān of the Kārāmānli tribe, resident of Mashhad, died A.H. 1199 (1785 A.D.); No. 235, of Mahdī Baig Khān died A.H. 1192 (1778 A.D.); No. 236, of Muḥammad Ḥusain Baig, a native of Shirāz, died A.H. 1194 (1780 A.D.); No. 238, of Mīrzā 'Āshūr Baig son of Mīrzā 'Azīz Baig Ghaznawī, a resident of village Khudādād; and No. 243, of Āqā 'Alī of Sonshāhī tribe, died A.H. 1196 (1782 A.D.).

Among the miscellaneous records of West Bengal, only one may be mentioned. No. 270, from Mollā Simlā, in Hooghly district, was published more than once (*Ins Beng.*, IV, p. 39). But in the published text, there is a serious mistake of the reading of the date namely A.H. 777, while the correct year is A.H. 877 (1472-73 A.D.) This epigraph now occurring on a tomb actually records the construction of a mosque by Khān-i-A'zam Mukhlīṣ Khān.

A.—COPPER PLATES, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA					
	MYSORE DISTRICT					
	MYSORE TALUK					
1	MYSORE. — Copper-plates from the Director of Archaeology and Museums, Karnataka State, Mysore. No. 1. Findspot : Āne-kannambāḍi, Holenarasipur Taluk, Hassan District.	Hoysala	Vīra-Nārasimha	Śaka 1141, Bahudhānya, Pausha, Lunar eclipse = 1219 A.D., January 2, Wednesday. The Śaka year was current.	Sanskrit and Kannaḍa, Nāgarī	Gives the genealogy of the king. Records the tax-free grant, made by the king, of the <i>mahāgrahāra</i> Prāgguchchi also called Ballā [la]pura consisting of eight-six <i>ṽṛttis</i> , out of which six were assigned at the rate of two <i>ṽṛttis</i> each for the learning of Ṛig-Vēda, etc., for the teaching of <i>Śāstra</i> (<i>Śāstrā-ṽākhyāna</i>), for the village god Kēśava and the remaining eighty were assigned to the brāhmaṇas. The tank Chōlasamudra is referred to among the boundaries described in Kannaḍa language.
2	No. 2 Do.	Do.	Vīra-Sōmēśvara	Śaka 1165, Subhaktit, <i>Dvirīya</i> Bhādrapada,	Do.	Records the grant of the village Ānēyakallavā-ḍi mahāgrāma consisting of four villages Chākaraṣana-ṽiḍu, Mākabbēyahalli, Gurugujēyahalli and Maisūru in Koṅga-vishaya

to Kambayya-daṇḍāhipa, the son of Dēv-
apilla and Chrlādēvi and the grandson of
Ādiya, the ruler of Chāta in Toṇḍa-dēśa,
by the king from his camp at Vikramapura
for the purpose of creating an *agrahara*.
Further states that Kambayya who is said
to have served Narasiṅha, the king's father
gave this village renamed as Kambapura to
several brāhmaṇas and that the village was
divided into 120 *ṛittis* out of which 10
ṛittis were assigned as *sarvamānya* to the
deities of the village and for the teaching of
Ṛedas and the rest to the brāhmaṇas as
kaṭṭu-guttage-piṇḍāṇa stipulating the pay-
ment of 168 *gadyāṇas* and 3 *paṇas* into the
royal treasury. The contents are stated to
have been given in Karṇāṭa-bhāshā also.

It gives the genealogy of the king. The king is
stated to have made a grant, from his capital
Dōrasamudra, of the village Turuveyakere
in Niruguṇḍa-vishaya to his *pradhāna* Sōma-
chamūpa, son of Śaṅkara and grandson of
Harihara. This general endowed the 95
ṛittis in this village renamed as Vijaya-
Nārasimhapura to the brāhmaṇas on the
date cited first stipulating that the dues from
the ninety-five *ṛittis* and the income from
taxes such *siddhāya*, *apūrva-āya* etc., accruing
on 10 of these *ṛittis* should be remitted for
conducting the affairs of the deities Kēśava-

Amāvāsya,
Solar-eclipse
Sunday =
1242 A.D.,
September 26.
But the week-
day was Fri-
day and the
Śaka year was
current.

(1) Śaka 1181,
Kālayukta
Bhādrapada
śu. 12, Mon-
day = 1258
A.D., August
12. The Śaka
year was
current.

(2) Śaka 1195,
Āṅgīrasa,
Kārtika ba.
15, Amāvāsya
Monday =
1272 A.D.,

Vira-Nārasimhadēva III

Do.

3 No. 3 Findspot : Turuvekere,
Turuvekere Taluk, Tumkur
District.

3

A.—COPPER-PLATES, 1975-76—Concl'd.

Sl No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—Concl'd.					
	MYSORE DISTRICT—Concl'd.			November 21, f.d.t. '25. The Śaka year was current.		dēva. It further records the grant of five <i>vr̥ttis</i> in the villages Ānēmole, Chemdūru, and Dākēhalu in addition to the earlier grant village Vijaya Nārasimhapura making it totally hundred <i>vr̥ttis</i> to his <i>mahāpradhāni sandhi-vigrahi</i> Sōvaṇṇa-dannāyaka, who in turn endowed it to the brāhmaṇas on the date cited second. The contents are given also in Karṇāṭa-bhāṣhā.
	MYSORE TALUK—Concl'd.					

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH					
	CHITTOOR DISTRICT					
	KALAHASTI TALUK					
1	GUḌIMALLAM.—Paraśurāmēśvara temple, stone unearthened from the paved floor of the central shrine				Tamil . . .	Fragmentary. and damaged. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 10th century.
	GUNTUR DISTRICT					
	NARASARAOPET TALUK					
2	CHEJERLA.—Kapôtēśvara temple, <i>ardha-maṇḍapa</i> , pilaster, northern side. . . .				Telugu, Telugu-Kannaḍa	Records the name Sōma-siṅgambu, the grandson Toravi-bhatara. In characters of about the eighth century.

3	Another pilaster in the same place.				Do.	Records the name Emkaḍu-singambu. Do.
4	Do.				Telugu mixed with Sanskrit, Telugu-Kannaḍa	Records the loving donation by Chandrā-singambu, Sri-Bhōṭṭara and another individual (name not clear). Do.
5	Below No. above.					In shell characters. Reads <i>śa. dānīśvara-chalitaḥ. Do.</i>
6	Pillar excavated from basement around the central shrine, face of the octagonal shaft in the middle section.				Prakrit, Brāhmi	Reads : <i>Māḥaṭha Māracha.</i> In characters of about 3rd century A.D.
7	Another face				Sanskrit, South-ern	Reads : <i>Gandharvva-sammāha.</i> In characters of about the 5th century A.D. Another faintly engraved writing nearby seems to read <i>Vulēna raksha.</i>
8	Square face of the same pillar at one end.				Telugu, Telugu-Kannaḍa	Reads : <i>Jayamakhi.</i> Do. Another writing nearby in faint characters seems to read <i>Prishṭha. ṇa. Śrī.</i>
9	Square face of the same pillar at the other end.				Do.	Reads : 1. <i>Śrī Gaṇḍado-nāṇḍu</i> 2. <i>Kṛottaruri</i> In characters of about the 7th century.
10	<i>Maṅḍapa</i> to the right of entrance into the same temple, pillar.				Do.	Seems to state that this pillar (on which it is engraved) was contributed by Śrī Eḍḍaran. In characters of about the 8th century. Cf. <i>S.I.I.</i> , Vol. VI, p. 213, note 2.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—<i>Contd.</i>					
	GUNTUR DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	NARASARAOPET TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	CHEJERLA—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
11	Another pillar in the same place.			...	Telugu, Telugu-Kannada	Mentions the name Śrī Niraśriya-chakravartīty-anuma-muni. In characters of about the 9th century.
12	Another face of the same pillar.				Do.	Damaged. Seems to refer to the deity Tat-purusha. Do.
13	Stone set up in front of the central shrine.			Kālayukti. Mārgasīra śū. 10, Monday= 1798 A.D., December 17.	Telugu	Contains an enumeration of the number of shrines, images, pillars, wells, tanks etc. Refers to Śrī Namaśivayagāru as the foremost servant of god Kapōtēsvara of Cheruñ-jārla.

HYDERABAD DISTRICT

HYDERABAD TALUK

14 GOLCONDA.—Fort. Loose slab lying near Islah Khana. Reverse side. Impressions received from the Superintendent Epigraphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur (Acc. No. 6775).

Telugu : Persian, Naskh

Bilingual. Mentions Malik Sā A Alamat in the beginning. Seems to record the construction of a step-well (*pīṭhabhāvi*) at Gōlakonḍa. Other details are not clear. In characters of about the 7th century. For the Persian portion see No. 3 of Appendix D.

KURNOOL DISTRICT

NANDIKOTKUR TALUK

15 ŚRĪSAILAM.—Pillar with a broken Nandi image planted near the post office.

Telugu

Damaged. The portion following the date is completely damaged. In characters of about the 14th century.

16 One of the steps leading to the 'Bhīmuni kolanu'.

Do.

Do. Records the obeisance of Sātayya to the deity Mallikārjuna. In characters of about the 17th century.

17 Do.

Do.

Records the obeisance of Sīntana of Gīrīm-gāru to the deity Mallikārjuna. Do.

18 Nandi-pillar, one of the steps leading to the 'Bhīmuni kolanu'.

Do.

Records the gift of the pillar to the deity Mallikārjuna by Vōbhatya Kadirayya. In characters of about the 16th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—<i>Contd.</i>					
	KURNOOL DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	NANDIKOTKUR TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	SRISAILAM—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
19	By the side of two female and one male figures carved on one of the steps leading to the 'Bhimuni kolani'.				Telugu	Reads : 1 <i>Abhuluri Timaka</i> 2 <i>Ayapa</i> 3 <i>Kommaka anima. Do.</i>
20	Another step.				Do.	Records the obeisance of Sambburāyani Talun-gurāyaṇḍu to the deity Malaya (i.e. Mallikārjuna). Do.
21	Do.				Do.	Records the obeisance of Tatṭiye-nāyaṇḍu to the same deity. Do.

22	One of the steps leading to the 'Pāṭiḷagaṅgā'			Do. . .	Records the obeisance of Peṇḍyāla Anniseṭṭi and Vōbalaḱka to the deity Śrīparvata Liṅgana (i.e. Mallikārjuna of Śrīśailam). In characters of about the 17th century.
23	Another step			Do. . .	The portion following the date is effaced. It mentions Śrīparvata. Do.
24	Another step			Do. . .	Reads : 1. <i>Māṅgulūri</i> 2. <i>Karaṇam Māchi-</i> 3. <i>rāju śrī. [*] Do.</i>
25	Same step			Do. . .	Reads ; <i>śrī Tippi-seṭṭi. Do.</i>
26	Do.			Do. . .	Reads : <i>Vīrava. Do.</i>
MAHBUBNAGAR DISTRICT					
KOLLAPUR TALUK					
27	AYYAVĀRIPALLI.— Broken stone kept in the Śiva temple.			Do. . .	Fragmentary. After the date it mentions Ja.... peggaḍḷu and the village Ammagūru. Noticed in <i>A. P. A. R. Ep.</i> , 1966, No. B. 254.
28	CHINNA MARRŪRU.—Tiru-malanāthasvāmi temple, <i>maṇḍapa</i> , pillar.			Do. . .	Records the obeisance of Gaṅgana, son of Pedinēḍu of Paḱiḍipḍu to the deity Tiru-malanātha of Moladakallu. In characters of about the 17th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—Contd.					
	MAHBUBNAGAR DISTRICT —Contd.					
	KOLLAPUR TALUK—Contd.					
	AYYAVĀRIPALLI—Contd.					
29	Chennakēśvara temple, <i>maṇḍapa</i> , slab on the floor.				Telugu	Records the obeisance of Yellamikki Śēsham-bhaṭṭu. Do.
30	Same slab				Do.	Records the obeisance of Kāśivajhala Pāpā-bhaṭṭu. Do.
31	AÑCHALAKATTA.—Mādhava-svāmi temple, <i>maṇḍapa</i> , slab on the floor.				Do.	Records the obeisance of Dāmagaṭṭa Tirumala-bhaṭṭu and Kṛishnavēṇi to the deity Kēśa-vasvāmi. Do.
32	PEDDA MARRŪRU —Stone slab lying in a field locally known as 'mādigavāni Chēnu'.				Do.	Records the grant of (land) as <i>mānya</i> by Raṅgāreḍḍi to Guruvāṇḍi of Kētepalli. In late characters.

33	Broken stone slab lying in a field locally known as 'Gollavāni Chānu', about 2 1/2 miles from the village.	Cheṛaku	<i>Mahāsāmanta Immaḍi</i> Bollayaraḍi	Šaka 1221, Vikāri, Śrī- vaṇa śu. 1, Sīmhasaṅ- krāṁti, Wed- nesday = 1299 A.D., July 29.	Do. . .	Records the gift of brass-stands for perpetual lamps in the temple of Brahmēśvara of Ālāmpūru by Bācharē...gāru for long life, health and prosperity of <i>mahāsāmanta</i> Cheṛaku...Bollayaraḍi. It also records the gift of 2 <i>kha</i> of land in Maṛūru for supplying oil to the lamps.
34	PENTLAVALLI.—Slab planted near a well known as 'Girappa-bāvi' about 4 km. from the village on Kollapur road.			Šaka 1615, Āṅgīrasa, Vaiśākha śu. 5, Monday = 1752 A.D., April 7. The weekday was Tuesday.	Do. . .	Records the excavation of a tank, construction of a <i>maṇḍapa</i> and laying of a garden by Timmappa, son of Mōrram-śeṭṭi Limḡgaṅ-śeṭṭi and a resident of Kaṁḍdanavōlu for the merit of his maternal and paternal lineage.
35	RĀMATĪRTHAM.—Loose slab lying in front of the Śiva temple.				Do. . .	Records the gift of land by Dāmagatla Di[Ti]mmaya. In characters of about the 16th century.
36	Another slab.				Do. . .	Records the obciance of Yalarāyaśvara. Do.
37	SŌMASĪLA.—Pillar in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> of the Sōmēśvara temple.	Kākatīya	Pratāparudra	Šaka 1217 (<i>muni-charāndra- akshi-ravi</i>), Manmatha, Kārttika Vai- śṇava tithi (i.e. śu. 12) Satur- day. Irregular.	Sanskrit, Telugu.	Damaged. Records the grant of the village Prōlayapuri, situated in Koṁḍūru-dēśa, by Bolla, who was the son of Rudradēva and the grand son of Bollaya and who was described as <i>Kākētasēnāhīnātha</i> to the deity Sōmanātha of Sōmasīlā for the merit of his father. It also seems to record a certain gift, (details not clear) to Saṁkara-Śiva-chāryya. Also refers to the villages Tāḍima-dappali and Prōlayapalli and a certain Sōmaya.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	MAHBUBNAGAR DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	KOLLAPUR TALUK — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	SŌMAŚILA — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
38	Do.	Kākatya	Pratāparudra	Durmukhi, Māgha ba. 15, Thursday = 1297 A.D., January 24.	Telugu	Seems to record a grant of a certain privilege as <i>vritti</i> to Kāmana and Immaḍi Kommana by Bāchana-pragaḍa, Rudraya, Isvarājususa, Āyamalli-pragaḍa Sōmaya and Odayana-pragaḍa, who were all the officials (<i>pragaḍlu</i>) of the Somanātha temple. Śāṅkaraśivāchārya, son of <i>Rāchagurudēva</i> Prasannaśivāchārya also is mentioned.
39	TŪMUKUNTA.—Jaina image kept outside the Chennakēśava temple.				Do.	Damaged. Refers to the <i>nishāhi</i> of a <i>bhaṭāra</i> . In characters of about 11th century.
40	Pedestal of an image of a female deity kept in the same place.				Do.	Damaged and purport not clear. In characters of about the 10th century.

41	Image kept under a tamarind tree near the field known as 'barrevāni vāmpu'.		Khara, Āshā- dha, 5, Mon- day.	Kannaḍa	Refers to the <i>nishāhi</i> of Kuṛḡōti Pōliseṭi. In characters of about 13th century.
42	Fragment of a stone kept in the locality called 'Pochammagudi'.			Telugu	Fragmentary. Seem to record the gift (or construction) of one of the <i>saptā-samitatis</i> by Kannaya, son of Pōtunēḍu. In characters of about the 14th century.
43	Image kept in the same place.			Do.	Reads : <i>Pōmmekarē Rudraya</i> . In characters of about the 12th century.
44	Another image kept in the same place.			Do.	Reads : <i>Karachamimā</i> . In characters of about 15th century.
WEST BENGAL					
MIDNAPUR DISTRICT					
CONTAI SUB-DIVISION					
45	HUJLI.—Loose slab lying on the platform of the grave. Impressions from the Superintending Epigraphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur. (Acc. No. 6667).			Bengali; Arabic, Naskh	Bilingual. Purport not clear. For the Arabic portion see No. 272 of Appendix D.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	BIHAR					
	BHAGALPUR, DISTRICT					
	BHAGALPUR SUB-DIVISION					
46	BHĀGALPŪR.—Pedestal of an image of Tārā. This and the following items are from Antichak discovered at the excavated site.				Sanskrit, Nāgari	Begins with the Buddhist formula <i>Ye dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Records that the image is the gift of the great devotee <i>Paramō-pāsaka</i>) <i>prañhāra</i> Udayavara of the Mahā-yāna school, for the attainment of the supreme knowledge by all the creatures having in their front rank, the <i>āchārya</i> , the <i>upādhyāya</i> , mother and father. In characters of about the 12th century.
47	Pedestal of a bronze image of the Buddha in the <i>bhūmisparśamudra</i> . (From Photograph).				Do.	Mentions <i>Mahāsūtradhāra</i> Vāhākāya. Do.
48	Pedestal of seated images of the Buddha in the <i>bhūmisparśamudrā</i> . No. 1 (24 B).				Do.	Damaged. Records the Buddhist formula <i>Ye dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> etc. In characters of about the 11th century.

49	No. 2 (24 E).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Do.
50	No. 3 (24 U).	.	.	.	.			Sanskrit, (corrupt), Nāgarī	Do.
51	Pedestals of headless images. No. 1 (24 G).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Records the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
52	No. 2 (24 J).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Damaged. Records the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
53	No. 3 (24 N).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Records the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
54	No. 4 (1008).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Damaged. Records the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
55	No. 5 (1767).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>sōnāramā[ñchi]ka</i> . Do.
56	No. 6 (1824).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>sōnāramā[ñchi]ka</i> . Do.
57	No. 7 (2165).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Śrī Dhamma[ddha]ras</i> a. Do.
58	No. 8 (2169).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Badly damaged and worn out. Do.
59	No. 9 (2187).	.	.	.	.			Do. . . .	Damaged. Records the Buddhist formula.... <i>hētu prabhavā</i> . etc. Do.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	BIHAR—<i>Contd.</i>					
	BHAGALPUR DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	BHAGALPUR SUB-DIVISION — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	BHĀGALPŪR—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
60	No. 10 (2196).				Sanskrit, (corrupt), Nāgarī	Damaged. Records probably the gift of a person (name lost) described as <i>paramōpāsaka</i> . Do.
61	Back of mutilated images.No. 1 (115).				Do.	Do. Records the Buddhist formula... <i>hētu-prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
62	No. 2 (240).				Do.	Records the Buddhist formula <i>Ye dharmmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Do.
63	A stone slab.				Do.	Fragmentary. Mentions Sōḍhala-maṭha in line 1. Other details are lost. Do.

64	Terracotta seals. No. 1.				Do. . . .	There is a <i>dharmachakra</i> on a pedestal in the centre and is flanked by a deer on either side. Below is the legend in three lines which is partly worn out and damaged. Seems to mention a <i>mahāvihāra</i> (name not clear). Do.
65	No. 2				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) <i>mahā</i> (2) <i>srāmāṇa</i> Do.
66	No. 3				Do. . . .	Broken. Only the left side of the seal is preserved. Contains the figure of a deer. The legend is too fragmentary and reads : (1) <i>śrīmajja</i> ... (2) ...Do.
67	No. 4				Do. . . .	A figure of conch on its side is above. Below is the legend in one line. It reads : <i>mahaśrī</i> Do.
68	No. 5				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) <i>ārya</i> (2) <i>sāta</i> Do.
69	No. 6				Do. . . .	Reads : <i>dīna</i> Do. The symbol of a sun is found on the right side of the legend.
70	No. 7				Do. . . .	Legend in two lines, not clear. Do.
71	Metallic ring.				Do. . . .	Reads - <i>vāṅgākasya</i> . Do.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
72	<p style="text-align: center;">BIHAR—Contd.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">NALANDA DISTRICT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">BIHAR SHARIF TAHSIL</p> <p>NĀLANDĀ.—Slab found in the course of excavations.</p>		Prathamaśiva <i>alias</i> Pūrṇavarman)		Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Gives the genealogy of the king from Bhāśiva. Records the making of an image of Buddha by the king. The <i>prāśasti</i> was composed by <i>sāndhivigrahika</i> Durgadatta. It was engraved by Mādhava, the son of <i>nāgara-sūtradhārā</i> Vāmana. In characters of the 7-8th centuries A.D. published in <i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXIX.
73	<p>RĀJGIR.—Pedestal of a black stone image of a Jaina Tīrthāṅkara (Nēminātha ?) discovered in the ruins of a Jaina temple on Vaibhāra hill, and now kept in the shed.</p>		<i>Mahārājādhirāja</i> (Chandra ?)	Chaitra 20	Sanskrit, Brāhmī (Nail headed)	Badly damaged and worn out. Mentions <i>Āchārya</i> Gurudatta. In characters of about the 5th century A.D. Noticed in <i>A. R. ASI</i> , 1925-26, p. 125 and plate LVI; b. Cf. <i>Rajgir</i> , by A. Ghosh, p. 18.

PATNA DISTRICT

PATNA TAHSIL

74	PATNA.—Back of a stone image of the Buddha, now kept in the office of the Superintending Archaeologist, Mid-Eastern Circle. Findspot : Nālandā, Bihar Sharif Sub-division, Nālandā District.			Sanskrit, Nāgarī Records the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmā-hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. In characters of about the 11th century.
75	Image of Aparājita kept in the state Archaeological Museum. Left side, above. Findspot : Pachar, Gaya District. Museum No. 10650.			Do. . . Do. Begins with the Buddhist formula <i>Yē dharmā hētu prabhavā</i> , etc. Records that it is the gift of Riyāḍika, the son of the great devotee (<i>paramōpāsaka</i>) Maḍhumathana of the Mahājanajayina (Mahāyāna) school. In characters of about the 13th century.
76	A frieze in the same Museum. Findspot : Not known.			Do. . . . Records that the <i>pādikas</i> of Pārśvanātha were made by [Śhī]tamaṇa-śrāvaka, the son of <i>Ṭha°</i> Bhiṣhtha and the grandson of <i>Ṭha°</i> Bhara[h]alpāla belonging to Śrīmāla-jñāti and Dhōragōtra at the <i>adhishīlāna</i> of Kalikuḍa-tīrtha and were installed by the disciples (<i>chhātra</i>) of Kamalāśāmyami on the advice of Jinachāndra-sūri belonging to Kharatara-gaṇa and Jinabhādra-sūri-paṭṭa. The record was written by Vinayadhīra-gaṇi.
77	A lintel in the same Museum. Findspot : Not known. Museum No. 3700.			Do. . . . Vikrama 1524, Āshādha śu.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	BIHAR—Concl'd.					
	SANTHAL PARGANAS DISTRICT					
	RAJMAHAL SUB-DIVISION					
78	RĀJMAHĀL. —Maina Talso Near the tomb of Maina Bibi. Steps. Impressions from the Superintending Epigraphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur. (Acc. No. 6651).	...			Nāgari	Reads : <i>ha</i> . In late characters.
	DELHI					
79	NEW DELHI. —Broken slab Kushāṇa kept in the office of the Superintending Archaeologist, Excavation II, Archaeological Survey of India, New Delhi. Findspot : Kankālī Tilā, Mathurā, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh.	Kushāṇa	<i>Mahārāja Rājātrīrāja</i> Kanishka	[Śaka] year 5), Gri 4, di 10	Mixed dialect, Brāhmi	Records that it (the stone on which the present inscription is engraved) is the gift of Viśākhaimitā, described as Paśīni and Brah- mañjikā, the wife (<i>dhamapati</i>) of Vasuka the daughter-in-law (<i>vadhū</i>) of Kṛishṇabala and the daughter of Budhila of the Nirvarga community, belonging to Kotiya-gana, Bra- hmadāstya-kula and [Jachivāgu]rita-sākha for the well being of all sentient beings.

80	Pedestal of an image now kept in the same place. Findspot : Do.		[Śaka] year 85, gri 3, di. 8	Do.	Fragmentary. Mentions a person (name not clear) and another named Dvitasihila.
81	Sandstone beam kept in the same place. Findspot : Do.			Prakrit, Brāhmī	Fragmentary. Mentions [Vajsaikā. In characters of about the 2nd century A.D.
82	Copper-band with decorated triangular projections in the possession of Dr. Mrs. Debala Mitra, Director (Monuments), Archaeological Survey of India. Findspot : Cell No. 4 of monastery No. 1, Ratnagiri, Jajpur Tahsil, Cuttack District, Orissa, No. RTR 457.			Sanskrit, (corrupt), Nāgarī (East Indian)	Fragmentary. Records that a certain Dudhārā gave to one, something (details lost) who donated an umbrella decorated with snake-hoods. In characters of about the 10th-11th centuries A.D.
83	Terracotta tablet in the possession of the same person. Findspot : Compartmented verandah in front of cell No. 3 in the same place. No. RTR-2, 338.			Sanskrit, (corrupt), Gaudīya	Fragmentary and damaged. Mentions the figure 9[1]6 in line 3. In characters of about the 14th century A.D.
84	Pedestal of an image now kept in the National Museum. Findspot : Not known.		[Śaka] year 32, Hema 4, di 8	Mixed dialect, Brāhmī	Mentions <i>Bhikhu</i> (<i>Bhikshu</i>) Viragōsa. Other details not clear.
85	Base of a beautifully sculptured panel, the central figure of which is a seated Jina. Findspot : Kanākrī Tīlā, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh. Museum No. J 249.			Do.	Begins with an invocation to Arhantas (Arhats). Records the setting up of a tablet of homage (<i>āraṅgapaṭa</i>) by Sihanādika (Simhanādika), the son of the <i>vaiṭika</i> Simhaka and son of a Kōsiki (Kausikī), for the worship of the Arhantas (Arhats). In characters of about the 2nd century A.D. Lüders' List. No. 105.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	DELHI—Concl'd.					
	NEW DELHI—Concl'd.					
86	A pillar showing <i>Jātaka</i> stories kept in the same Museum. Findspot : Bhārhut, Nagod Tahsil, Satna District, Madhya Pradesh. Museum No. 68-161.				Prakrit, Brāhmi	Records that the pillar (<i>thabha</i>) is the gift of Uttaragidhika(Uttaragridhraka) from Karahākata(Karahakata). In characters of about the 2nd century B.C.
87	Another pillar showing the <i>Jātaka</i> stories now kept in the same Museum. Findspot : Do. Museum No. 68-162.				Do. . . .	Records the gift of Jātāmīta (Jitāmītra ?) from Mōragiri (Mayūrāgiri). Do. Cf. <i>CII.</i> , Vo. II, Part II, p. 24, No. A 26 and plate XXIV.
88	Sculptured slab kept in the same Museum (on loan from the British Museum, London). Findspot : Amarāvati, Sattena-palle Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.				Do. . . .	Records the gift of a coping stone (<i>upīsa</i>) by Ajuna (Arjuna), the grandson of the householder (<i>gahapati</i>) Mariti, the Akhasavādīcha (inhabitant of Akhasavāda). In characters of about the 1st century A. D. Luders' List, No. 1221.

<p>GOA</p> <p>PAÑAJI.—Government Museum, Stone set up in the museum. Findspot : Curdi, Bicholim Taluk.</p>	<p>..la-dēva . . .</p>	<p>Sanskrit, Nāgarī</p>	<p>Fragmentary and damaged. Contains part of the section introducing the genealogy of the king. In characters of about the 10th century.</p>
<p>89</p> <p>Another stone in the same place. Findspot : Pāla near Pai Usgaon, Bicholim Taluk.</p>	<p>....</p> <p>[Vijayanagara]</p>	<p>Sanskrit mixed with Kannaḍa, Nāgarī</p>	<p>Much effaced. Seems to record a grant to Siṃha-Jois. Contains a carving of the <i>gardabha</i> curse.</p>
<p>GUJARAT</p> <p>BANASKANTHA DISTRICT</p> <p>PALANPUR TAHSIL</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>Sanskrit, Nāgarī</p>	<p>Records the making of an image of Rīshabha-dēva in the Mahādēva-chaitiya by Mahīchamīdra-sūri probably on behalf of Mādrikēyā, the wife of Vyā° Jālā, the son of Vyā° Viradatta belonging to Prāgvāta-Jñāti.</p>
<p>91</p> <p>PALANPUR.—Meetha Baoli. Southern side wall. Impressions from the Superintending Epigraphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur (Acc. No. 7012).</p>	<p>Vikrama 1320, Māgha śu. 5, Thursday. Irregular.</p>	<p>Local dialect, Nāgarī ; Persian, Nastaliq</p>	<p>Bilingual. Mentions probably a person named Khān Kamālanata[j]gō Āsūda in connection with the constructions of the <i>dharmadwār</i>. For the Persian portion, see No. 101 of Appendix D.</p>
<p>92</p> <p>Gate in Bara Bazar. Slab fixed on the wall of the gate. Do. (Acc. No. 7017).</p>	<p>Vikrama 1750</p>	<p>Local dialect, Nāgarī ; Persian, Nastaliq</p>	<p>Bilingual. Mentions probably a person named Khān Kamālanata[j]gō Āsūda in connection with the constructions of the <i>dharmadwār</i>. For the Persian portion, see No. 101 of Appendix D.</p>

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
93	GUJARAT— <i>Concl.</i> MEHSANA DISTRICT PATAN TAHSIL PĀTAN.—Sindhia Gate, Right side. Do. (Acc. No. 7046).	Gaikwad of Baroda	Ānandarāva Gāyakavāḍa	Vikrama 1861, Jyēshtha ba. 13, Tuesday ; Saka 1727 = 1804 A.D., July 5.	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the making of the gate (<i>daravāia</i>) by Raghunātha Mahipatarāva.
94	HAMPI.—Lime stone block discovered during an excavation in front of Mahānavami-dibba.				Prakrit, Brāhmī	Fragmentary. Reads : (1) <i>tarasa putasa</i> (2) <i>.ā dānam</i> In characters of 1st and 2nd centuries A.D.

95	Broken stone slab discovered in the same place.	Chālukya of Kalyāna	[Vikramāditya VI]	Chālukya Vikrama year 1, [Nala], Bhādrapada ba. [1]3, Sunday, Irregular.	Kannaḍa	Damaged and incomplete. Seems to record a gift of 80 <i>Lokki-gadyāṅgas</i> in every year to the teachers who expound the <i>purāṅgas</i> in a <i>maṭha</i> (name not given) by <i>Mahāpradhāna Daṇḍanāyaka</i> Somēśvara-chaṭṭiṅpādhya.
96	Below the figure of an elephant on a stone block which is fixed to the <i>Mahānavami-dibba</i> .				Do.	Fragmentary. Contains portion of a record and seems to describe a certion <i>āchārya</i> and his disciples. In characters of about 13th century.
97	Slab fixed to the wall of a ruined shrine near Viṭhala temple.	Vijayanagara	Sadāsivadēva-Mahārāya	Śaka 1474, Paridhāvi, Phālguna śu. 1, Monday = 1553 A.D., February 13.	Do.	Registers the sale-deed (<i>Krayapatra</i>) made by Kāmbhañ Kāma-dikshita, son of Niṅgābhata of Puṭapariti in favour of Hiri Tirumalarājaya, son of Bāchiraja Venkataya-dēvamahā-arasu relating to the purchase of <i>Koḷaga hiriya-hitu-gōhina-sthala</i> situated at Kaṁchumāvina-kate for 100 <i>gadyāṅgas</i> . The latter is stated to have purchased the above mentioned land which was once gifted to Raṅgu-bhata son of Dōmana-jōyisa by Kṛishṇarāya-mahārāya. Also records that the former has made subsequent grants like 6 <i>muḍi</i> of land to the deity Ajuvāridēva the worship and the management of which was entrusted to the <i>sthānikas</i> Hiriya Valabhaya and Chika Valabhaya, sons of Ayi-Rāmā-ṅnujaya with a stipulation that they have to give 2 <i>paḍi</i> of <i>prāsāda</i> each to the person who prepares flower garlands and guards the temple.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—Contd.					
	BELLARY DISTRICT—Contd.					
	HOSPET TALUK—Contd.					
	HAMPI—Contd.					
98	Stone slab discovered by the side of the ruined temple near Viṭhala temple.	Vijayanagara	Sadāśivadēva-Mahārāya	Śaka 1481, Sidhārthi Kārttika śu. 12, Saturday= 1559 A.D., November 11.	Telugu	Records the gift of a house site to Chikkayā-chāryulu, son of Peddayāchāryulu and grandson of Śrī Parāśarabhaṭṭa Chikkayā-chāryula, belonging to Harita-gōtra, Āpas-tambha-sūtra and Yajus-śākhā by <i>Chātāni</i> Tirumalaya, son of Timmayagāru and grandson of Lakadāsari, and the <i>sthānika</i> who is stated to have constructed a temple of Modalaḷuvāru at Śrī Viṭhalaṃ. Further states that the donee also received a portion of a house-site from Śrī Raṅgarāju, son of Ōbularāju and grandson of Kuruchēṭi Bai-charāju, who had, in turn, received it from Lakkādāsari-Tirumalayyagāru.

99	Rock slope in front of the Vishṇu temple near the 'king's balance'.	Do. . . .	Vira Harihararāya, son of Bukkarāya	Śaka 1308, Kshaya, Māgha śu. 5, Thursday = 1378 A.D., January 24.	Kannaḍa	States that the images of Kshētrapāla, Saṁnuj-inātha were caused to be set up and a Sivālaya was caused to be constructed to the west of the temple of Nārasimha at Pam-pākshētra by <i>Sumikada</i> Hiriyataṁma Chikka-Tamma, son of Baiyicheja-seṭṭi.
100	Rock-floor at Chakra-tīrtha, No. 1.			Śaka .67, (ba.- <i>ritu-vāridhi</i>), Kārttika ba. 8.	Do. . . .	Damaged and worn out. Contains only the date portion. In characters of the 15th century.
101	No. 2.			Śobhakṛit, Kār-ttika ba. 8, Monday.	Do. . . .	Do. Mentions Sāluva Tīmmarasa and Lakshu-maya. Do.
102	Rock near Venkatapuram gate.			Kālayukta, Āshāḍha śu. 15.	Do. . . .	Records the grant of house-site in the inner area of the path leading to the well to <i>Jōngama</i> Sōmeyadēva of Sirusuganahali by Bulapa, son of Sōmāya-nāyaka, and his wife Bhayirāyi.
103	Outer wall, to the left side of Raghunātha temple No. 1.	Vijayanagara	Sadaśivarāyamāhārāya	Śaka 1470, Plavaṅga, Śrāvara ba. 1.	Do. . . .	Slightly damaged. Seems to record the grant of lease rights (<i>kāṇiyāchi</i>) of performing worship etc (<i>amgarānigabhōga</i>) in the temple of Raghunāthadēva with the monthly pay (<i>jīta</i>) of Chika ga 1/2 (<i>haṇa</i>), daily pay (<i>jīta</i>) of <i>prasāda paḍi</i> 2 and also some land to <i>Aṁṇa</i> -mallarāja, son of [Bhā]marāja of Kāśyapa-gōtra by Tīmmarāj, a son of Hiriyā Abbirāja of Kāśyapa-gōtra.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—<i>Contd.</i>					
	BELLARY DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	HOSPET TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	HAMPI—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
104	No. 2.	Vijayanagara	Sadāsivarāyamahārāya	Śaka 1477 (for 1470), Plavaṅga, Śrāvāṇa śu. 1	Kannaḍa	Records that Timmarāja son of Hiriya Abbirāja mentioned above in No. 103 made the grant of the lease rights (<i>kāṇḍiyāchi</i>) of the management (<i>adhikārike</i>) of the temple of Raghunāthadēva to Tiṃmarasa, son of Liṅgarasa, of Śrīvachchha-gōtra (Śrīvatsa), Āśvalāyana sūtra and (Rik)-śākhā, on a monthly salary of 3 <i>paḍi</i> and 2 <i>prātāpa-haṇa</i> , and daily payment of 2 <i>prasāda-paḍi</i> .
105	Outer wall, to the right side of the same temple.	Do.	Do.	Śaka 1476 (for 1470), Kilaka, Kārttika 12, Monday Irregular.	Do.	Records that the same donor mentioned above in Nos. 103-04 belonging to Kāśyapa-gōtra, Āpastambha-sūtra and Yajuś-śākhā, from Harige situated in Udayagiri made a grant of the lease rights (<i>kāṇḍiyāchi</i>) of the whole management (<i>sakala-pārupatya</i>) of the temple

of Raghunāthadēva to Bhadri-panḍita son of Chōka-Cherlla Nāga-panḍita of Ātrēya-gōtra and Āpastambha-sūtra, with an allotment of 1[4] *paḍi* of rice *prasāda* per day and 18 *pratāpa* (per month).

Damaged. Seem to record the construction of *majha*, *maṇḍapa*, *tōraṇa* and [*maḍu*] to the deities Ādinātha and Pragaṭanātha by Basa-vadañṛāyaka, the minister. The planets Moon, and Jupiter are stated to be in Mīna and Mēsha respectively and the Sun with the rest of the planets is stated to be in Viṛīśhika.

Incomplete. Seems to record the grant of land (?) to provide for the daily and special offerings to god Virūpākshadēva by Kāchappa, son of Sōmedannāyaka, belonging to Kāsyapa-gōtra and Ṛik-Sākhi.

Damaged. Records the gift of land, made in the presence of Kṛishṇarāya, for providing 2 *harivāṇa* of food offerings to god Virūpākshadēva made by Virāṇa-nāyaka to Linga-nārādhya, the *sthānika* of Virūpākshadēva for the merit of the donor's father Sindhapa [Sidda]mari-nāyaka. In character of about 15th century.

Badly damaged. and worn out. purport not clear. Do.

Damaged and worn out. Mentions *Kaliyuga* in line 1 and seems to record some gift to Narasim[ha*]dēva. Do.

Sanskrit,
Kannaḍa

Śaka 1428,
Mārgaśira,
śu. 11, Rēvati,
Wednesday =
1506 A.D.,
November 25.

Kannaḍa

Śaka 1328,
Vyaya, Śrā-
vaṇa, ba. 8,
Friday = 1406
A.D., August
6..

Do.

Khara, Pushya
śu.

Do

....

Do

....

Bukka

Do.

106 Floor in front of Āñjanēya temple near Kṛishṇa temple.

107 Rock-slope in front of Hēma-kūta temples near Virūpāksha temple, No. 1.

108 No. 2.

Vijayanagara

109 Continuation of No. 108 above.

110 Slab kept in front of Vishṇu temple, near 'Kings's balance'.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—Contd.					
	BIJAPUR DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	BAGEWADI TALUK					
111	MUTTAGE.—Stone block kept in the newly built Basavaṅṅa temple (formerly known as Basavaṅṅana-kattiṅge).	Rāshṭrakūṭa	Kṛishṅa III	Śaka 886, Rakṛākshi, Māgha śu. 1 (pāṭṭiva), Friday = 965 A.D., January 6.	Kannaḍa	Refers to the conferment of the Tardavāḍi 1,000 division by the king on Tailaparasa (i.e. Taila II of the Kalyana Chālukya family) bearing the epithets as <i>Samadhigata-panichamahāsābda Mahāsāmaniādhīpati</i> and Āhavamalla and records that the latter has conferred upon Rāchaṅṅaya, the office of <i>nāḷḷāmunḷḷu</i> and made a grant of 12 <i>matter</i> of land to a certain deity (name lost).
112	BIJAPUR. —Wall of a ruined mosque in the outskirts of the city.		Sulḷan Mahmad Sha	Śaka 1572, Vikṛita Vai- śakha śu. 10, Thursday= 1650 A.D., May 30.	Sanskrit mixed with Marāṭhi, Nāgari	In embossed characters. Slightly damaged. Seems to record the completion of a construction probably, of the mosque by Badē-mālik Hujūr.

DHARWAR DISTRICT DHARWAR TALUK	[10020th day ?]	Prakrit, Brāhmi (Southern)	Damaged. Seems to record the gift of pillar to the god <i>Mōla-Bhagavat</i> by Somayasas of <i>Kadapa-gōta</i> (<i>Kāśyapa-gōtra</i>), who is stated to have performed several sacrifices including <i>Vājapēya</i> and who hailed from [Sā]kēta. In characters of the 1st century B.C. — 1st century A.D. Noticed in ' <i>Progress of Kannada Research in Bombay Province</i> ', year 1941-46, pp. 4-5, 50-51, plate VIII (b).
113 Fragmentary stone kept in the same Museum. Findspot: Near Batterappa temple, Badami, Bijapur District.		Kannaḍa	Fragmentary. Begins with the mention of the capital city in the words <i>Svasti Śrīmad-Vijaya-Vāṭāpy-adhishihānē</i> & mentions Polekēsi-Yallabha as the performer of <i>asvamēdha</i> . In characters of the 7th century A.D. Published in <i>Karnatak Inscriptions</i> , Vol. 1, No. 1.
114 Another stone kept in the same place. Findspot: Western wall of the courtyard of the Virūpāksha temple at Paṭṭadakal, Badami Taluk, Bijapur District.		Do.	Records the royal grant of a stone throne or pedestal and of a bracelet or bangle to the temple of the god Lōkapālēśvara, which was built by Anantaḡaṇa. Published in <i>Ind. Ant.</i> , Vol. X, p. 165.
115 Do. No. 2		Sanskrit, Kannaḍa	Damaged. Contains the beginning portion. Refers to a devotee of Śāntinātha and mentions Vikramāditya. <i>Ibid.</i>
116 Do. No. 3	Śaka 997, Rākshasa, Chaitra śu. 15 (Puṅṅami), [lunar] eclipse = 1075 A.D., April 3. The weekday was Friday.	Kannaḍa	Do. Records the installation of Marolēśvara-dēva by <i>Perggaḍe Marūjīmāyā</i> and several gifts of land and money for various purposes such as <i>nandā-dīpa</i> , <i>aiga-bhōga</i> etc., to the temple by him and other persons including <i>Laṅḍanāyaka</i> Mallidēva in front of the thousand <i>mahājanas</i> of Lōkkigunḍi known as <i>Śrī Rāmara-dattiyagrahāra</i> .

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—<i>Contd.</i>					
	DHARWAR DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	DHARWAR TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	DHARWAR—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
118	Pedestal of an image kept in the same place.				Kannaḍa	Records that the image of Muni Subratadēva was caused to be made by Nāgiyakka, the wife of Vā[sa]śeṭṭi, son of Dharmme[ya] Samki-śeṭṭi, the disciple of Narēsvarasēna-Traividyadēva. In characters of about the 12th century.
119	Decorated slab, attached to the compound wall on the right side of the same <i>basī</i> .				Do. . .	Damaged and worn out, In two lines, refers to an ascetic and his disciple Basavayya. In characters of about the 12th and 13th centuries.
120	<i>Pīṭha</i> of the main deity.				Sanskrit, Kannaḍa	Damaged and incomplete. Seems to refer to <i>Yāpaniya</i> and an image. Do.

121	Slabs kept in the compound of the Museum. No. 1			Pushya, Amāvā- sya	Kannaḍa	Fragmentary and damaged. Seems to record a grant of 100 <i>gadyānas</i> and some lands for the worship and offerings etc., to god [Tel]-ligēśvaradēva. Refers to a piece of land granted for the purpose of <i>pādapije</i> of the <i>nālnūrvar</i> . Ittāge is mentioned in line 10. Do.
122	No. 2 Hero-stone discovered near Nannēśvara temple. . . .				Do. . . .	Damaged and top portion lost. Records the death of Piṭṭuga, a hero in a fight. Vaijanātha is stated to have composed the record. In characters of 10th century.
123	Beam of the Basavēśvara temple at Hāluguṇḍi. . . .	Chālukya of Kalyāna	Pratāpa Chakravarti Jagadēkamalladēva		Do. . . .	Slightly damaged. Extolls the thousand <i>Prāmukha-mahājanas</i> of Lokkiguṇḍi, which is known as <i>Śrī-rāmara-datti-mahāśrahāra</i> and <i>Perḡgaḍe Vasāntakramita</i> . The latter is stated to have made a gift of a golden plate valued at 12[.] <i>pan</i> , out of his income from <i>akkaśā-lad-achchāna-kēṇi</i> for offering <i>pāhamaṅḡage</i> to god Gavareśvaradēva. Also records some more grants to the same deity like 5 <i>paṇa</i> for the Sivarātri-pūjā by <i>sēṇabōva Kēśiyanna</i> etc. In characters of about 13th century.
124	Slab lying near a well belonging to Randi Nilakantappa. . . .	Do	Tribhuvanamalladēva		Do. . . .	Badly damaged and broken off. Contains the beginning portion mentioning the king and the <i>mahājanas</i> of Lokkiguṇḍi. In characters of about the 12th century.
125	Hero-stone fixed to a small stone structure in Karavērayya Kulkarni's field. . . .	Yādava	Vīra....dēva	Regnal year 22	Do. . . .	Do. Contains an eulogy of the <i>mahājanas</i> as in No. 124 above. In characters of about the 13th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—<i>Contd.</i>					
	DHARWAR DISTRICT—<i>Contd.</i>					
	GADAG TALUK					
126	LAKKUNDI. —Slabs lying in front of Jaina <i>basti</i> No. 1.	Chalukya of Kalyāṇa	Tribhuvanamallaḍeva (Vikramāditya VI)		Kannaḍa	Damaged, broken and incomplete. Eulogises the king (Vikramāṅka) and Bichiseṭṭi and enumerates the <i>sixteen gajas</i> of the Yāpanya-saṅgha and the lineage of the Jaina ascetic Nēmichandramuni. Mentions the <i>basti</i> of Kālīkāḍevi of the Nēmivāmi 'temple). Also refers to Remmisseṭṭi and Hāyiseṭṭi of <i>baḷagāra-vaiśyakula</i> who probably caused the construction of a <i>chaityagriha</i> for the deity Nēmīnātha, Do.
	KOLAR DISTRICT					
	KOLAR TALUK					
127	KOLAR. —Stone beam fragments discovered during the excava-	[Vijayanagara]		..67, Krōdhana Pushya ba 1	Do. . .	In three fragments. Seem to record some grant made by Baicheyanāyka and Lakumeyanā-

128	tion of the floor in the backyard of Sōmēśvara temple.	Do.	Virūpāksha	Monday= 1445 A.D., December 27. The <i>tithi</i> was '14	yaka to the deity Sōmeyadēva of Kōlāla. Māradēvanahalli in Kāḍikeya-bhāge of Mukkanna-Jiya in Keḷāla-naḍu is also mentioned.
129	Do.	Do.			In two fragments. Records the grant by Kasavi-seṭṭi son of Appiṣetti, of 1 <i>leṭṭe</i> areca-nut, betel leaf etc., for offering the <i>nīṭya-tāmbūla</i> probably to the deity mentioned above. Refers to a person (name lost) described as <i>mahāsāmanā</i> . In characters of about the 15th century.
130	Back side wall, at the bottom, of the same temple.	Do.			In two fragments. Records the <i>sarvamānya</i> grant of probably, some land in which a house was to be built for the merit of Sāluva Narasiṅgayamahārasu. Do.
	MULBAGAL TALUK				
131	ĀVAṆI.—Rāmēśvara temple, Gaṅḡi-maṇḍapa, front wall to the right side of entrance.	Do.			Fragmentary. Seems to contain the description of land probably donated. In characters of the 11th century.
					Do. Mentions Paḷḷikoṇḍāṅ Kuralaiya Sundaraof Nariyanūr. Refers to Avaniyanūr in Āvaniyanāḍu in Nigarisōḷa-maṇḍalam. In characters of the 14th century. Published in <i>Ep. Carn.</i> Vol. X, part II, Mulbāgal No. 42 (a).

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Concl.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA—<i>Concl.</i>					
	KOLAR DISTRICT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	MULBAGAL TALUK —<i>Concl.</i>					
	ĀVAṆĪ—<i>Concl.</i>					
132	Rāmēśvara temple, Gañji- maṇḍapa, front wall to the right side of entrance.		..	Śaka 1...., Chittirai	Tamil	Do. Contains only the date portion.
133	Kāmākshiamma temple, wall to the right side of the entrance.				Do.	Do. Seems to record the provision made for the maintenance of a twilight lamp and for food offerings to a deity (name lost) at the rate of 6 <i>nāḷi</i> of paddy per annum. Do.
	NORTH KANARA DISTRICT					
	HALYALA TALUK					
134	MADANAHALLĪ.—Hero-stone lying near a ruined temple in				Kannāḍa	Damaged. Top portion is lost. Records the death of Saptaya-[nāyka], son of Gaṅgeya-

135	the village. Rock of the side of a field in the village.			Do	nāyaka in a cattle-raid and the gift of 1 <i>paṇa</i> to the sculptor (ōja) and 2 <i>paṇas</i> and other dresswares (<i>aḍaḷe</i> , <i>hoda-kupusa</i> and <i>telesutu</i>) to Kadaṇṇamma. In characters of 12th and 13th centuries.
136	MANGAḶAVĀDA.—Hero-stones lying in a place called Chōlappa-ōmanna kuji. No. 1			Do.	Reads; line 1, <i>ūrōḍe tōṭa</i> line 2, <i>haḷḷa sime</i> . In characters of about 14th 15th centuries.
137	No. 2.			Do.	Badly damaged. Mentions in line 3 Nāgādēva-rāṇya. In characters of about the 12th and 13th centuries.
138	NURUKWĀDA.—Slab kept near the ruins of Ísvara-temple.	Chālukya of Kalyāṇa	, śu. 5, ... day	Do.	Purport not clear. Purport not clear. Mentions some epithets of a chief in line 14. In characters of about the 12th century.
139	PĀḶA.—Hero-stones lying near a ruined Ísvara temple. No. 1	Do.	Regnal year 14, Vikīri, Chattra śu. 8, Saturday Irregular.	Do.	Fragmentary. Records the death of Vayjārāvuta, son of Vuḍeya Va. niye in a battle at Maṇali after killing many horses. Refers to Dēvaṇahe [ga]ḍe.
140	No. 2.			Do.	Fragmentary and damaged. Seems to refer to the death of a hero (name lost) when there was a battle between Dēvaṇa-heggaḍe and the whole army of Halasiḡe. In characters of the 12th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	KARNATAKA— <i>Concl.</i>					
	NORTH KANARA DISTRICT — <i>Concl.</i>					
	HALYALA TALUK— <i>Concl.</i>					
	PĀḶA— <i>Concl.</i>					
141	No. 3				Kannaḍa	Fragmentary and damaged. Seems to refer to the death of a hero (name lost). Contains the last imprecatory stanza. In characters of about the 11th century.
142	No. 4				Do.	Do. Seems to record the death of a hero (name lost) son of [. .] iya-nāyuka. Contains the last imprecatory stanza. Do.
143	No. 5	Chālukya of Kalyāna	[Tribhuva] namalladēva	Regnal year 17, Krōdhi	Do.	Do. Seems to refer to the death of hero (name lost) who was probably a devotee (<i>pāda-padmārādhaka</i>) of [Mūla*]sthānadēva. Do.
144	RĀYAPATTANA.—Pieces of the inscribed slab lying near a ruined temple.			[Śaka] 1001, Pīṅgala, [Kā]rttika śu 5.	Do.	Fragmentary. Mentions Kādamba family and Bamarāja. Contains imprecatory portions of a grant.

145	TERAGAON.—Outer door jamb, to the right side in the Rāma temple.				Do.	Do. Seems to be a portion of a grant. Contains part of the imprecatory stanza. In characters of 11th-12th centuries.
SUPA TALUK						
146	JOGALBET.—Stone slab lying near the Virakta <i>Maṭha</i> in the village.				Do.	Damaged and worn out. Records some gift to the Virakta <i>Maṭha</i> by Mārayya and probably Basalinga-gauḍa and others. In late characters.
147	ULVI.—Left and right sides of the image of <i>Nandi</i> , kept in front of ruined <i>Īsvara</i> temple.				Do.	Do. Mentions Rēvaṇasiddhēśvarādēva. Do.
TUMKUR DISTRICT						
GUBBI TALUK						
148	KADABA.—Outer wall of the Rāma temple.	[Hoysala]		ba...	Tamil	Fragmentary. Seems to record the gift of land for food-offerings to a deity. In characters of the 13th century.
149	In the same place.	Do.			Do.	Do. Refers to the deity Vishnuvardhaṇa-Vinṅa-gar-emberumāṇ. Do.
150	Inner wall of the same temple.	Do.		x	Do.	Do. Seems to record the grant of land by some individuals. Do.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
151	<p style="text-align: center;">KERALA</p> <p style="text-align: center;">TRICHUR DISTRICT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">TRICHUR TALUK</p> <p>CHEVOOR.—Rock on the north western corner of the Pārvati-Gaṇapati temple complex, outside the temple compound.</p>				Malayālam	Records the name of one Tonma.—Nārāyaṇaṇi. In late characters.
152	<p>OORAKAM.—Bhagavati temple, first <i>prākāra</i>, inside, west wall, stone fixed in the wall.</p>				Tamim Vaṭṭe- Juttu.	Records the agreement (<i>kachcham</i>) made by the <i>ūrār</i> assembling in the temple (<i>mukkāl-vaṭṭam</i>) at Puriyāpur to maintain nine daily services (specified) including the recitation of the <i>Mahābhārata</i> , performance of dances etc., in the temple of the goddess Bhaṭāri of the locality. In characters of about the 11th century.

153	Same temple, stone slab built into the platform near the <i>dhvaja-stambha</i> .			Kollam 722, Jupiter in Makara, <i>Simha</i>	Malayālam	Records the construction of the temple i. stone by Kōmēttā Rāman.	
154	TRICHŪR.—Vaḍakunnaāthan temple, subsidiary entrance in- to the first <i>prākāra</i> pillar on the left side, eastern face, above the figure of a standing devotee in <i>añjali</i> pose.				Do.	Reads <i>Cherama-kattaḷi Kṛishṇan</i> In characters of about the 16th century A.D.	
155	Main entrance to the same <i>prākāra</i> , pillar on the right side, southern face, by the side of a standing figure of a devotee in <i>añjali</i> pose.			Kollam [74]5, Jupiter in Tula	Do.	Gives the name, Paramēśvara Elayattip-Pich- chaṅ of Tāmarachchēri, obviously, of the person represented by the figure.	
MADHYA PRADESH							
GWALIOR DISTRICT							
GWALIOR TAHSIL							
156	GWĀLIOR.—Fort Niche of Dhōṇḍa Paur. Impressions from the Superintending Epi- graphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur (Acc. No. 7065).	Tōmara	<i>Mahārājādhirāja Rājā</i> Mānasyamgha-dēva	Vikrama 1552, Āśvina śu. 2.	Sanskrit and Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the making of the image of <i>Dhōḍhā-dēva</i> . Also records the renovation of the <i>pauri</i> of Dhōḍhā by the ruler. The record was written by <i>Sājasutradhāri</i> Dharama- chāmdū.	

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH—Contd.					
	GWALIOR DISTRICT—Concl'd					
	GWALIOR TAHSIL—Concl'd					
	GWALIOR—Concl'd					
157	Pillar shaft in the inner pavilion of Urwai Paur. Do. (Acc. No. 7062)	Tōmara	<i>Mahārājādhirāja Rājā Mānasyamgha-dēvā.</i>	Vikrama 1553, Āshādha śu. 13, Thursday = 1496 A.D., June 23.	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the construction of the <i>pauri</i> of Uravāi by Sāyēkha, the executive (<i>ājñakāri</i>) of the king. Mentions also <i>Dhōḍhā-sūtradhāri</i> Pahēsu, Gadhamita-Syamgha Dharmā-chāmḍa, etc.
129	Pillar Shaft in the outer pavilion of Urwai Paur. Do. (Acc. No. 7066).			Vikrama 1611, Āsvina śu. 5, Friday=1555 A.D., Septem- ber 20. f.d.t. '07.		Records the construction of <i>Pruī</i> (for <i>Pauri</i> ?). Mentions the masons Bhōgachāmḍa and Karamachāmḍa.

HOSHANGABAD DISTRICT

HOSHANGABAD TAHSIL

159 HOSHANGĀBĀD.—Sati stone kept under a banyan tree opposite the P.M.G.'s office and near the State Bank of India.

Vikrama 1253,
Pausha śu. 5,
Thursday=
1196 A.D.,
December 26.

Mahākumāra Hariścha-
mradēva .

Paramāra of
Mālwā .

Sanskrit, Nāgarī

Damaged at the end. Records probably the death of Tāh[a], the wife of Tāmvasiha, the son of Rājagasiha.

SEHORE DISTRICT

BUDHANI TAHSIL

160 PĀNGURĀRIA.—Boulder near a rock shelter.

Piyadasi (Aśoka)

Maurya

Prakrit, Brāhmī

Damaged and worn out. Contains the Minor rock edict No. 1 of the king. Records the order of the king conveying his message of piety through Kumāra Śamva, during the pilgrimage of the king to the Upunitha-vihāra at Maṇmadēśa. Mentions the numerical figure 256 at the beginning of the edict.

VIDISHA DISTRICT

BASODA TAHSIL

161 UDAIPUR.—Slab set up in the front wall of an old shrine now converted into a cattle shed belonging to Daulataram Ghatayali near the Udayēśvara temple.

....

....

Sanskrit, Nāgarī

Contains ten verses in praise of the Sun god. In characters of about the 11th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA					
	AKOLA DISTRICT					
	AKOLA TAHSIL					
162	AKOLA.—Purānā Qubarastan near the Mehta mill. Headstone of a grave. Other side. <i>Impressions from the Superintending Epigraphist, Arabic and Persian Inscriptions, Nagpur</i> (Acc. No. 6916).			Vikrama 1950, Mārgaśirsha ba. 2, Saturday=1893 A.D., November 25.	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Carelessly written. Purport not clear. Appears to mention Rahamatu[lā].
163	Obverse. Do. (Acc. No. 6915).			Vikrama 1988, Māgasara (Mārgaśirsha) ba. 2, Saturday, Hijra 1350, Šobān 16=probably 1931 A.D., December 26. The date of Šobān month was however 15).	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Bilingual. Carelessly written. Purport not clear. The figure of a crescent moon is engraved above.

AMRAVATI DISTRICT

AMRAVATI TAHSIL

164 AMRAVATI.—Hyderpura. Old
graveyard. Headstone of a
grave. Do. (Acc. No. 6925).

Vikrama 1[7]00

Do.

Do. Mentions Nanāji Nāyēkana of
Pam̄dharapura.

165 Headstone of another grave. Do.
(Acc. No. 6926).

Vikrama 1900,
Hijra 1260,
Ramzan 13=
1844 A.D.,
September 26.

Do.

Records probably the death of a person named
Āllānāyēkīna Sōmavāri belonging to Pam̄ta-
rapura.

MALKAPUR TAHSIL

166 MALKĀPUR.—Lal Bagh Baoli.
South wall. Do. (Acc. No.
6920).

Śaṣa 1714
Virōdhakṛit,
Chaitra,
Vikrama 1847

Do.

Records probably the construction of a well in
Malakāpura. Mentions Ahmadābada, Rāma-
rāya, Harajāṛāya etc.

MEHKAR TAHSIL

167 CHŌTĀ KUND.—Step on the
western side. Do. (Ac. No.
6935).

....

Do.

Reads. *nālā*. In late characters.

168 Step on the north side. Do.

....

Do.

Illegible and worn out.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—<i>Contd.</i>					
	AMRAYATI DISTRICT—<i>Contd.</i>					
	MEHKAR TAHSIL—<i>Contd.</i>					
	CHŌTĀ KUNḌ—<i>Concl.</i>					
169	Floor slab in front of Papareshtar Mandir. Entrance. Do. (Acc. No. 6937).				Local dialect, Nāgarī.	Illegible and worn out.
170	Above the Chōṭī-Dhār, Bhikhu Nauras. Entrance. Do. (Acc. No. 6936).				Do.	Do.
171	LŌNĀR.—Loose slab in Dutt Sudand Mandir. Do. (Acc. No. 6933).				Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Fragmentary and damaged. Mentions Mārasimgha in line 5. In characters of about the 10th century. Cf. <i>Hiralal's List</i> , (2nd ed.), No. 265.

172	Slabs on the floor in front of. Brahmakunḍ Mandir in the same place, East side, No. 1. Do. (Acc. No. 6934).				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) [Śrī dhōtrumarasā ātrī (2) [gōtrī] In late characters.
173	Do. . . .				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) Śrī dhōtrumarasā (2) ātrī gōtrī. Do.
174	No. 2		...		Do. . . .	Reads : (1) Śrī Kamarasī ātrī (2) gōtrī Do.
175	No. 3				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) [Śrī] dhōkamarasā (2) atrī gōtra Do.
176	No. 4				Do. . . .	Reads : Śrī Kumarasā atrī Do.
177	No. 5				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) [Śrī] [Kumarasā] (2) atrī gōtra Do.
178	No. 6				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) [Śrī] dhōrūma (2) atrī gōtra Do.
179	No. 7				Do. . . .	Reads : Dhōkusara[sō] atrī. Do.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	Language	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—Contd.					
	AMRAVATI DISTRICT—Contd.					
	MEHAKAR TAHSIL—Contd.					
	LONAR—Contd.					
180	No. 8				Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Reads : (1) Śrī ō kumarasā (2) [a]trī gōtrī Do.
181	No. 9					Reads : (1) Śrī dhō [ku]marasa ātrī (2) gō[trī] Do.
182	No. 10					Reads : Kumarasā. Do.
183	No. 11					Reads : (1) [Śrī]dhō kuma[rasa] (2) ātra gō. Do.

184	No. 12	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : . . . <i>marasa</i> . Do.
185	No. 13	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) <i>Śrī ō Kumarasa</i> (2) <i>atrī gōtra</i> Do.
186	No. 14	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) [<i>Śrī</i>] <i>ō ka.rasa</i> (2) <i>a. gōtra</i> Do.
187	No. 15	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) <i>atrī</i> (2) . <i>trī</i> Do.
188	No. 16	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) <i>Śrī āñō . . . ra[īsa]</i> (2) <i>atrī gōtra</i> Do.
189	No. 17	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) . <i>dhōkanara[sa]</i> (2) <i>atrī gōtrī</i> Do.
190	No. 18	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) . <i>dhōkanarasā</i> (2) . . <i>gōtra</i> Do.
191	No. 19	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : <i>Atrī . tra</i> , Do.
192	No. 20	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : . <i>trī gōtrī</i> . Do.
193	No. 21	.	.	.	.	.	.	Do. . .	Reads : (1) <i>Śrī [ō] Kumarasā</i> (2) <i>atrī gatrī</i> Do.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—Contd.					
	AMRAVATI DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	MEHKAR TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
	LŌNĀR—Concl'd.					
194	No. 22				Sanskrit, Nāgari	Reads : . <i>dhō Kumarasā atri</i> . Do.
195	No. 23				Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Atri gōtra</i> . Do. Below is sketched the figure of a person with folded hands.
196	No. 24				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) [<i>Śrī</i>] <i>dhōkumarasa</i> (2) <i>atri gōtri</i> . In late characters.
197	No. 25				Do. . . .	Reads : (1) . <i>dhōkumarasā</i> (2) <i>a. gōtra</i> Do. Below is sketched the figure of a person with folded hands.

198	No. 26					Do.	Reads : (1) <i>atī gōtrī</i> (2) <i>śrī</i> . Do.
199	No. 27					Do.	Reads : [<i>Śrī</i>] <i>dhōkumara</i> , Do. Below is sketched the figure of a person with folded hands.
200	MEHKAR.—A well in the river bed. Slab on the west side. Do. (Acc. No. 6939).				Vikrama 19[3]5, Śaka 1800	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Bilingual. Mentions <i>Rśādōdina</i> in line 1. Purport not clear.
201	Another slab on the west side. Do. (Acc. No. 6940).				1900 A.D.	Local dialect, Nāgarī ;	Mentions <i>Gaṅgāsāgara</i> in line 1. Purport not clear.
NAGPUR DISTRICT							
NAGPUR TAHSIL							
202	NĀGPUR.—A grave in the graveyard in the civil lines. Northern side. Do. (Acc. No. 6702).				[Vikrama ?] 1741	Do.	In embossed characters. Purport not clear.
203	A slab in the State Museum. Findspot : Not known. Do. (Acc. No. 6697).			... <i>Paramēśvara</i> Burhān [Nizām Shāh]		Local dialect, Nāgarī ; Persian, Naskh.	Bilingual. Badly damaged and worn out. Purport not clear. For the Persian portion see No. 142 of Appendix D.
SINKHED RAJA TAHSIL							
204	SINKHED RAJA.—East side of a <i>samādhī</i> in front of the <i>samādhī</i> of Lakhūji Jadav. Do. Acc. No. 6942).				Śaka 1637, Manmatha, Āsvina śu. 10	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records probably the performance of sati by <i>Sōrabā bāi</i> , wife (?) (<i>aḥhadhangī</i>) of ... <i>Shadhōji Yādhava</i> . Mentions at the end two servants (<i>sēvaka</i>) by name <i>Tejaji</i> and <i>Nārāyanaji Jādhē</i> .

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—Concl'd.					
	NAGPUR DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	SINDKHED RAJA TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
	SINDKHED RAJA—Concl'd.					
205	Grand <i>samādhi</i> of Lakhujī Jādv. Right side of the main entrance. (Acc. No. 6941).				Local dialect, Nāgarī	Mentions the names of a number of persons with the title of Jādhava. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 18th century.
206	Pillar in the east in the Nīlakaṇ- thēśvar Mandir. Do. (Acc. No. 6943).			Śaka 1808, Śr- āvaṇa śu. [.]	Do. . . .	Records probably some renovation work. Mentions one Dēshamusha(kha) of the Śrīyapura-pargaṇa.
207	Floor slab inside the same Mandir. Do. (Acc. No. 6944).				Do. . . .	Indifferently written and worn out. Purport not clear. In late characters.

<p>RAJASTHAN JAIPUR DISTRICT JAIPUR TAHSIL</p>	<p>208</p>	<p>ĀMBER.—A slab in the Amber Fort Museum. Do. (Acc. No. 6863).</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>Vikrama 1722, Śrāvāṇa śu. 2.</p>	<p>Local dialect, Nāgarī ; Persian Nasta'liq</p>	<p>Bilingual. Purport not clear. Mentions one Rāmadata, <i>dīvāna</i> and <i>mahārāja</i>. For the Persian portion see Appendix D No. 153.</p>
<p>NAGAUER DISTRICT DIDWANA TAHSIL</p>	<p>209</p>	<p>DAULATPUR.—Inner wall to the right of the gate of the fort. Do. (Acc. No. 6906).</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>(1) Vikrama 1896, Kār- tika (2) Vikrama 1900, Kār- tika ba. 13, Saturday = 1843 A.D., October 21.</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>Local dialect, Nāgarī</p>	<p>Begins with an invocation to Jalāndharanātha. Refers to the rule of Mahārāja-sāhaba. Vāvaḍa-sāhaba, the son of Ajaṁta-bahādura sirādāra on the first date. Probably records an order of the government detailing the several items of levy in cash.</p>
<p>TAMIL NADU CHINGLEPUT DISTRICT KANCHIPURAM TALUK</p>	<p>210</p>	<p>KĀNCHĪPURAM.—Karukkiṇṇil amardava! temple, central shrine, west wall, tiers.</p>	<p>[Chōla]</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>....</p>	<p>Tamil</p>	<p>Beginning lost. Records the tax-free gift of some land in favour of the goddess Bhaṭṭāraki. Obviously of the temple, by the <i>mahā-nagarattār</i> of Kachchippēdu following the royal order (<i>tirumugam</i>) issued at the instance of the [queen] Kōdaiṇṇiṇṇi and executed by Vijayanalluṅ of Ālappākkam. The boundaries of the gift land included Karukkamarnda-Bhaṭṭāraki temple at Kiḍan-daperumāṣēri, Perungōvaraiyar-tali, Lāvā-niśvara [temple] at Mahindrapādi. In characters of about the 11th century A.D.</p>

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
211	TAMIL NADU—Contd.					
	CHINGLEPUT DISTRICT —Concld.					
	KANCHIPURAM TALUK—Concld.					
	KĀNCHĪPURAM—Concld.					
211	Same place.	Chōla	Uḍaiyār Rājendra Chōla	Regnal year 13, and 79th day	Tamil	Engraved in continuation of the above. Reports to be a copy of the king's order received from the <i>irumandirav-ol-i Śāṅka[ra]ṅ</i> Gāṅgēyakulakāḷaṅ, conferring the <i>archanā-hlōga</i> of the temple on Viçchādīraṅ Jñāna-siva-piḍāraṅ and his heirs. It is said that the beneficiary had earlier enjoyed a position in the temple of Karukkamarnda-piḍāriyār at Kānchīpuram, a city in Eyiḱkōttam included in Jayaṅkoṇḍaśōḷa-maṅḍalam. In characters of about the 11th century A.D.
212	DHARMAPURI DISTRICT					
	DENKANIKOITAI TALUK					
212	BAIRAMAṄGALAM.—Rock called Naiguṭṭa in a field belonging to Sri Marappa, son of Nagappa.	Vijayanagara	Harihara II	Śaka 1303, Durmati, Tai 22, Sadayam, Friday=1382 A.D., January 17.	Do.	Records the gift of land by some individuals, including Chokkadēvar who was doing the <i>nāyakam</i> of Rājendraśōḷa-nāḍu and Aṅṅūṭṭru-vār. The land is described as a <i>kaṭṭuk-kuḍāṅgai</i> of Mudali Chetṭi.

	Hero-stone called <i>Iruia-dēvasthā-</i> nam.	Hoysala	<i>Vīra-Rāmanātha</i>	Regnal year 31, Kārttigai	Do.	Records that Anṇāmalai, son of Vairattoṟuvā- lan, a resident of Vāḷilimāngalam killed a tiger in the course of a hunt and died. Refers to a number of persons including Akaṇka- mallan and Chērakudaiyāḷvār who probably set up the stone in the year Jaya.
213						
214	DENKANIKÓTTAI.—Sudarśana pillar lying in the compound of the Mṛigayā Venkaṭeśa- perumāḷ (also called Bētarāya- svāmi) temple.			Śaka 195 .na, Kārttika ba. 30, Monday.	Kannada	Incomplete. Records the grant of lands in Deṁkanikōta by Śikkarasa, the <i>Śīraḷpra-</i> <i>dhāna</i> of <i>Mahāmaṇḍalēśvara</i> Huliya Rāmay- yadēva-mahārasu under the orders (<i>nīripa</i>) of Rāmarāja-oḍeya. It states that the village Deṁkanikōta in Morasu- <i>nāḍu</i> in Deṁkani- kōṭa-sthala is said to have been obtained by Rāma-rāja-oḍeya as <i>amara nāyamikara</i> from Narasīngarāja-oḍeya.
215	ERUDUKÓTTAI.—Inscribed slab lying in a field.				Tamil	Records the construction of the temple of Chittiramēḷi-vinṇagar—emberumāṅ at Eṇḍa- kōttai in Kuṇṇappaṟṟu in Kallaga-nāḍu in Rājarājachōḷa-valanāḍu, a sub-division of Muḍiṅṇachōḷa-maṇḍalam by Aṇḍāl, the wife of Eḷḷumūrti, son of Aḷkoṇḍapillai of Vembaṟṟūr-Māngalūr, for the merit of <i>Mudā-</i> <i>ḷiyār</i> —Tāmattālvār <i>alīas</i> Pūrādarāyaṅ (Pūr- vādhirājaṅ) in the month of Aḷpasi (Aḷpasi) in the year Dundubhi. The temple along with the <i>tiruvaiyāṭṭam</i> lands is stated to have been entrusted to Vengapōyi-āḷvār as a <i>pṛitti-dāna</i> by Aḷkoṇḍapillai. The protec- tion of the <i>Ḷerīya-nāḍu</i> was invoked. In characters of about the 12th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU—Contd.					
	DHARMAPURI DISTRICT —Contd.					
	DENKANIKOTTAI TALUK—Concl'd.					
216	KĀRANĀDAPALLI.—Slab lying behind the Basaveśvara.	[Hoysala]		Vibhava, Vaikāsi	Tamil	Records the death of a person (name lost), son of Kāliyāṇḍi . . . Pamma-gāmuṇḍan after rescuing the cattle when Vichchūranpaḷli in Kunṛappaṇu was destroyed, men were taken captive (<i>chirai</i>) and cattle (<i>toru</i>) were lifted by Sōmidēvan of Periyakūṭichchi in Kallaganāḍu in Muraśu-nāḍu. The event is stated to have happened during the regime of Kaṇḍar Sūriyan Tribhuvanamalla-Pūradarāyan (Pūr-vādhirāja) Tāmattālvār. Do.
217	MUCHCHADIRAM.—Rock in a big tank.	Chōla	Kulōttuṅga I	Regnal year 45	Do.	Damaged. Begins with the <i>prasasti Pugaḷ-nāḍu viḷaṅga</i> etc. Seems to record the grant of lands at Kulōttuṅgaśōḷanallūr for four brāhmanas as <i>agara (agrāhāra)</i> . Mentions Sēlaipuran in Rējendraśōḷa-vaḷṅnāḍu in Muḍi-ḡoṇḍaśōḷa-maṇḍalām.

HARUR TALUK

218	ACHCHALAVĀDI.—Herostone in the Vēḍiyappaṅ temple			Do . . .	Refers to the death of Taṅṅimāraṅ in the course of the capture of buffaloes at Pulikkal. In characters of about the 10th century.
219	ELLAPPUDAIYĀNPATTI.—Hero-stone in the Maṅavāḷaṅ-kuṭṭai-Vēḍiyappaṅ temple.	Pallava	Vijaya-Siṅgavinnapparumar	Tamil, Vaṭṭe-ḷuttu	Records the death of Mondaḷaḷ Komārasattiyāru, the ruler of Kalappāḷur in a fight at Mokkaṅpāḍi in Puḷamalai-nāḍu. In characters of the 6th century.
220	KATTARASAMPATTI.—Hero-stone in the Vēḍiyappaṅ temple.	Western Gaṅga	Śivamāra	Do . . .	Records the death of Vānigachchadīyaḷṅṅār [Vēḷṭṭakkiyār, a servant of Teḷiyān-Iḷaijār died probably in the course of a battle at Kūḍal, while Kandavānnadi-araiṅṅār was ruling over Puḷamalai-nāḍu. In characters of the 8th century.
221	KIRAPPATTI.—Inscribed slab with Gaḷalakshmi panel lying in the field of Rahim khan.	Chōla	Kulōttuṅga (III)	Tamil	Contains representations of Chittiramēji symbols. Partly damaged and illegible. Seems to record a grant of the village of Chittiramēḷinallūr alias Muḷḍuḷmuṅaiyūr. Other details not clear. In characters of about the 13th century.
222	MATTIYAMPATTI.—Hero-stone in the Vēḍiyappaṅ temple at the confluence of Vāniyār and Pennār.	Prithvi-Gaṅgas of Paṅgalanaḍu	Kaṭṭinaiparumar	Tamil Vaṭṭe-ḷuttu	Records the death of Vēḷachchattānār, servant of Amaranilaiyār after rescuing the cattle in the course of a cattle-raid by Aruttiraiyār when Kandavānnadi-araiyār was ruling over Puḷamalai-nāḍu. In characters of the 7th-8th centuries A.D.
223	MENASI.—Hero-stone in the Vēḍiyappaṅ temple in the land of Chinnasāmi—uḍaiyār.	Chōla	Rajendra	Tamil	Refers to Puḷamalai-nāḍu and mentions Rāmaṅ, the son of Pēraraiyaṅ. In characters of the 11th century.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU—Contd.					
	DHARMAPURI DISTRICT Contd.					
	HARUR TAHSIL—Contd.					
224	MUTTĀNŪR.—Hero-stone lying in the tank called Mayilan Ēri.	Western Gaṅga	Siripurisaparumaṅ (Śripurusha)	Regnal year 15	Tamil, Vaṭṭe- juttu	Refers to the death of Vaḍamachchāttanār, a servant of Amaraḍakkīyār in the course of a cattle-raid at Koṭṭamaṅgalaṃ by Kāmaiyanār of Vēlal-nāḍu when Amaraḍakkīyār was ruling the western division of Puṅamalai-nāḍu. In characters of the 8th century.
225	Hero-stone lying in the tank called Poṅṅēri.	Nolamba	Aṅṅiyaṅ Vira-Nulambaṃ	Śaka 847, year 2	Tamil	Records the death of <i>gāmuṅḍar</i> Maḍaiyar Māṅiyamaṅar of Poṅṅaiyūr in the course of the cattle-raid by the Vallavaraiyar and Nāṭṭiār after rescuing the cattle.
226	PĀPPĀMBĀDI.—Fragmentary stone lying in the village.			Regnal year 11	Tamil	Mentions Pāppāṅbādi. In characters of the 13th century.

227	PERIYA PAN̄NIMADUVU. — Hero-stone lying in the field of Sri Ardhanārīchettiyar on the roadside near the Vāpi river bridge.			Tamil, Vaṭṭe- luttu	Records the death of a hero whose name is not clear. Mentions Ayappadēvaṅ(?) and Puṛamalai-nāḍu. In characters of the 9th century.
228	Another hero-stone in the same place.		Śivamāra Saigoṭṭa	Tamil	Illegible. Seems to record the death of Uḍaiyār Aṟu-Māṟaṅ and mentions Eḷūr-nāḍu. In characters of the 8th-9th centuries A.D.
229	TĪRTHAMALAI. —Around Sūrya image kept at the entrance of Tirthamalai Īśvara temple.			Do.	States that Īśānamūrti Kuratti consecrated (the image on which the record is engraved). In characters of the 11th century.
230	Stone sculpture of a goddess in a shrine in the Śiva temple on the hill.			Tamil, Vaṭṭe- luttu	Mentions Bhagavati <i>Kuṟuchchīli</i> . In characters of the 9th century.
231	HOSUR TALUK BENNEKALLU alias TAMB- ĀNDRAPALLI.—Slab in afield belonging to Shri Ellappa, son of Ramaiah.		Vibhava, Tai	Do.	Refers to the reign of Kaṅḍar Sūriyan Tribhuvanamalla Pūrādirāyar Dharmattālvār of Muraṣu-nāḍu. Seems to refer to the death of Periyatamman, son of Āḷudaināyan Śivadēvar and his son (name lost) in the course of a fight (<i>pūśal</i>). In characters of the 13th century.
232	Slab in front of the Gōpālasvāmi temple in the same village.	Vijayanagara	Dēvarāya Voḍeya	Do.	Badly damaged and worn out. Mentions <i>Mah[daṅḍal]hāyaka</i> Mācheyanāyaka probably as administering Hariyanāḍu and Morasā-nāḍu. Seems to record a gift of land for the purpose of worship and offerings (<i>naivēdya</i>) to a certain deity (name lost).

Śaka 1335,
Nandana,
Pushya śu. 10,
Monday =
1412 A. D.,
December 14.
The Śaka year
was current.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU—Contd.					
	DHARMAPURI DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	UTTANGARAI TALUK					
233	NALLĀPURAM.—Airāvateśvara temple, central shrine, west wall.				Tamil	Records the gift of a place called Chetttikalku-tar-anai at Kūḍal by Muḍigoṇḍaśōlakarḱaḱa-mārāyar pumāvarāṇayaṅ for a <i>sandhi</i> to the deity Veļļāṇai-viṭaṅkar. In characters of the 13th century.
234	In the same place.				Do.	Records the grant of wet and dry lands at Māvēndal by Āḱaiyūr-Māḱālvaṅ for food-offerings during the <i>Vaṅṅiyamaḱkaļṅvaṅ-sandhi</i> to the deity Veļļāṇai-viṭaṅkar. Do.
235	Do.	Hoysala	Rāmanātha	Regnal year 12, Āḱi	Do.	Records the grant of garden lands in Śurarāvānpalli and Puttur by Tittānapālan of Chūļaiḱirai, who was administering (<i>nāyakaṅ-jeyvāṅ</i>) Rājarājaitumaḱi-nāḱu, for maintaining two perpetual lamps to god Veļļāṇai-viṭaṅkar. The gift was entrusted to Śūriyabhāṭṭaṅ who agreed to maintain the endowment from the beginning of the month of Āḱi.

236	Vināyaka shrine in the same temple, base tier.			Do. . . .	Fragmentary. Refers to a grant made over as <i>dēvadāna</i> to the deity Vellānai-viṭṭankar. In characters of the 13th century.
237	Steps leading to the Airāvātēśvara temple.			Marāṭhī (?), Nāgarī	Mentions Mādhava Pāgaṇe of Kōnyēri and Akhalōji of Mōhile family. In late characters.
238	Do. . . .			Do. . . .	Mentions Rakhamāji Kōha and Dēū Dēsa-mukh.
239	Do. . . .			Do. . . .	Reads <i>Hārji Jāmcha</i> . In characters of the 17th-18th centuries A.D.
240	MADRAS.—Back of a bronze Jaina image. Impressions from the Director, Government Museum, Madras. Findspot; Not known.		Vikrama 1541, Māgha, śu. 3, Thursday= 1484 A.D., January 1.	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Records the making of an image of Dharmānatha by Jīṇadāsa and Gunapāla, the sons of Śrē° Jōgā and his wife Sōnāi belonging to Śrīmāla-jñāti and Vra(Bra)hmāna-gachha. The image was installed by Budhisāgara-sūri belonging to Vimalasūripaṭṭa and a resident of Śitāpuri.

MADRAS DISTRICT

MADRAS TALUK

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76 - *Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU—<i>Contd.</i>					
	NORTH ARCOT DISTRICT					
	POLUR TALUK					
241	TIRUMALAI. —Jaina temple. Two pieces of loose slab, kept within the compound of the temple complex.			Śaka .[9]3	Tamil	Middle portion lost. Records a gift of ten <i>poḷi</i> by Aṅgātaḍigaḷ <i>alīas</i> Śatrukulāntakaṅ and refers to the two priests of the Jaina temple (<i>poḷli</i>) at Tirumalai in Vaigavūr in Paṅgala-nādu. In characters of about the 10th century A.D.
242	Loose slabs within the same compound.	[Chōḷa]		Regnal Year 23, and 175th day.	Sanskrit and Tamil ; Grantha and Tamil	In six fragments. The Sanskrit portion (in verse) describes an emperor (<i>sārvabhauma</i> , name lost) as world famous. Seems to record an undertaking by the <i>ūrār</i> of certain place (name lost) to remit 4726 and odd <i>kalam</i> of paddy to the Tirumalaippaḷḷi at Vaigavūr. It is said that the transaction was entered in the revenue register on the date given in the presence of some persons, including Uttamaśōḷa Brāhmanārāyaṅ, Rājēndraśōḷa-Atimūrkkachcheṅgīrai, Rājēndraśōḷa Māvaiḷivānarāja] etc. In characters of about the 11th century A.D. Cf. <i>A.R. Ep.</i> , 1907, No. 68 ; <i>S.I.I.</i> , Vol. XXIII, No. 68.

243	Same temple, stone set up near the steps of the first <i>gōpura</i> .			1915 A.D. Rākshasa, Purattāsi	Tamil	Commences with an obeisance to the deity Nēmsvara and records that the steps, near by, were built by Aḷammāl, who was a daughter of Kuppusvāmi Upādhyāya of Tachchāmpādi, the wife of Śikhāmaṇi Sāstri of Tirumalai, and mother of Adichakravartti.	
TIRUPPATTUR TALUK							
244	BOMMIKUPPAM. —Perumāi temple, lintel of the <i>mahāmaṇḍapa</i> .			Saumya, Āṇi 7	Do.	Records the construction of the <i>maṇḍapa</i> by Amaṭṭa Ammāl. In late characters.	
245	KADIRAMAPAṬṬI. —Loose-stone lying in the compound of Vēṅgōpālakṛishṇasvāmi temple (S. No. 182/1).			Virodhikṛit, Chittirai 1	Do.	Incomplete. Seems to record some agreement among the Āḷmīr of the Kṛishṇasvāmi temple at Kadirampaṭṭi, Tirumala Śaivachāriyār, <i>Archaḷakar</i> Nārāyaṇan Ayyaṅgār. In late characters.	
246	Rock (S. No. 210) in the tank called 'Pāppāṅ-kuttai'.	Chōla	Rājādhirāja II	Regnal year 9	Do.	Records the construction of a pond, called Duggappāṭṭar-kuttai by Vanṇāṅ poṭṭi; a resident of Mādappaḷli and granting it as a <i>dēvadāna</i> to the deity Aṅgakkāṛisvaram-uḍaiyanayanār. A copy of this record is also found engraved in an adjacent village Kōnērikupam (See No. 248 below). In characters of the 12th century.	
247	KONḌAPPANĀYAKKAN-PAṬṬI. hamlet of NARIYA-NĒRI.—slab in a field on a cart track. (S. No. 267/2).				Do.	Records that it was a high way (<i>peruvaḷi</i>) of Adiyamāṅ and the distance to Nāvartivaḷam is 29 <i>kādam</i> from the spot. In characters of the 12th century.	
248	KŌNERIKUPPAM. —Rock in Survey No. 89 in the village.	Chōla	R. jādhirāja II	Regnal year 9	Do.	A copy of No. 246 above. Do. In characters of the 12th century.	

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU— <i>Contd.</i>					
	NORTH ARCOT DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	TIRUPPATTUR TALUK— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
249	NĀYAKKANŪR.—Stone slab in the Vēdiyappaṅ temple in the village.	Chōla	Rājarāja I	Regnal year 18	Tamil	Damaged. Mentions Nettekayam in Eyi-nāḍu of Rājarāja-Mummudichōḷa-rājyam. Seems to record the death of Pēlai Maṅikaṇḍaṅ.
250	In the same place.	Do.	Do.	Regnal year 19	Do.	Incomplete and damaged. Refers to a person (name not clear) described as the son of Chuṅakkaṅ Chāttayaṅ of Pajjūr in Viriyūr-nāḍu and to Rājarāja Mummudichōḷa-rājyam and to Vāṅakōppāḍi on the southern bank of river Pennai.
251	PĀRANDAPALLI.—Slab in a field bearing Survey No. 654/3.				Kannaḍa	Badly damaged and worn out. Seems to refer to a grant of land. In late characters.

252	Slab lying in the field belonging to Abbas Saheb (near the flour mill).			Do.	Do. Seems to refer to the name of a king.
WANDIWASH TALUK					
253	WANDIWASH (VANDAVĀŚI). — Jalakanthiśvara temple, broken loose slab near the first <i>gōpura</i> , inside, lower portion. (A small piece containing part of the record is built into the wall nearby).		(1) 1885 A.D., April 2, Pārthipa. (wrong for Tārara) Paṅguṇi 21. (2) 1888 A.D.	Tamil	Records that Kaṇaka Ammāl, the wife of Vāṇi Saravaṇa-śeṭṭi of Vandavāśi donated on the first date 100 Rupees to burn one lamp near the <i>duyastambam</i> (<i>dhvajastambha</i>) in the Jalakanthiśvara temple and one lamp near the Geruḍa-kambha in the Raṅganātha temple; that however, under some bad influence she herself subsequently denied the gift; and that the same was restored on the second date following the decree of the Magistrate's court at Āraṇi to that effect.
THANJAVUR DISTRICT					
NANNILAM TALUK					
254	TIRUCHCHENGĀTTĀNGUḌI. — Uttarāpatīśvara temple, four sides of a loose slab kept near the Sūtikāmbā shrine.	Pāṇḍya	Regnal year 9, Tai 29th [Saturday], [Aviṭṭam] Probably = 1344 A.D. January 24. The <i>nakshatra</i> was Kṛittikai.	Do.	Fragmentary and mutilated. Seems to record the exemption from certain taxes as decided in the <i>niyāyas</i> or assemblies of the Valaṅgai and Iḍaṅgai communities probably in favour of the deity Gaṇapatiśvaramuḍaiyār, at Tiruchchengāṭṭāṅkuḍi in Marugal-nāḍu included in Gēlyā* Jmāṅjikka-valānāḍu.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
255	TAMIL NADU— <i>Contd.</i> THANJAVUR DISTRICT — <i>Contd.</i> NANNILAM TALUK— <i>Concl'd.</i> TIRUCHENGĀTTĀNGUḌI — <i>Concl'd.</i> Stones built into the east wall (outside), of the same shrine. Stone No. 1.	[Chōla]		ba. 9, Wednesday....	Tamil	Fragmentary. Seems to be part of a bigger record registering some sale for 700 <i>kāṣū</i> . Certain persons (name lost) father Kājarāḷap ..., Aḷuḍaiyāṅ, certain Chōiḍyāṅḍi's daughter (name lost), an inhabitant of Vaṅgai-nagar in Puṅṅakarambai-nāḍu, and Arayaṅ Aṅkoṅ-dān of Kaḍuvaṅkuḍi are referred to probably as signatories. In characters of about the 12th century.
256	Stone No. 2.	Do.	Tribhuvanachakravartti Vīra...			Do. Contains a part of a record and refers to Jananāthan. Kaḍuvaṅkudi in Marugal-nāḍu, Aṅkoṅḍanāyaka-bhatṭaṅ and his younger brother (name lost). Do.

257	TIRUPPAṆAIYŪR.—Saundarēśvara temple, Natarāja shrine, north wall.	Pāṇḍya	Mājavarmaṇ Parākrama-pāṇḍya	Regnal year 5, Simha śu. 8, Wednesday, Anusham. Probably = 1340 A.D. August 2. The <i>tīthi</i> ended at '93 on the previous day.	Do. . .	Records that Ādichanḍēśvaradēvarkaṇṁigaḷ of the temple of the deity Aḷagiya-nāyanār, in Tiruppaṇaiyūr gave 30 <i>kuḷi</i> of house-site at Tiruppaṇaiyūr to their counterparts of the temple of the deity Muḷuvaṅkkiśvaramuḍaiyār in Kīramāṅgalam in Paṇaiyūr-nāḍu in the Kulōttuṅgaśōḷavanāḍu in exchange for one fourth (of a <i>vēḷi</i>) of land received from the latter.	
258	West wall of the same shrine.	Vijayanagara	Dēvarāya	Śaka 13[3]3	Do. . .	Indifferently engraved and badly damaged. Seems to record a sale of land as <i>irunāmat-tukkāni</i> by the <i>ūrār</i> of a place in favour of the deity Aḷagiyanāyinār in Tiruppaṇaiyūr in Kulōttuṅgaśōḷavanāḍu. Puduḥchēri-uḍaiyāṇ, Narāsiṅgadēvaṅ etc. figure as signatories.	
THANAYUR TALUK							
259	VALLAM.—E. Gauriyammaṅ temple, <i>maṇḍapa</i> in front of the central shrines, pillar.	Chōḷa	R. jarāja I	Regnal Year 1[6]	Do. . .	Commences with the <i>meḷkkīrti</i> of the king, <i>Tirumagaḷ pōla</i> etc. Records an undertaking given by the <i>pārasavas</i> of the fort in the locality including Aḷattīraḷ Virasōḷaṅ <i>alias</i> Śōḷanpērachārriyaṅ to contribute one <i>uḷakku</i> of a ghee out of the produce from their lands for a perpetual lamp to the deity Kāla-piḍāri Kaitalaipūsāl-Naṅgai at <i>Karuvuḷaḷā</i> Vallam in Eriyūr-nāḍu. This arrangement is said to have been approved by the king from his day-time throne at Viṇṇaṇēri at the request of Kambaṅ-Maniyaṅ <i>alias</i> Vikrama-siṅga-mūvēndavēḷaṅ of Chūrālūr in Chūrālūr-kūḷṭṭam.	

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76 — *Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU— <i>Contd.</i>					
	THANJAVUR DISTRICT — <i>Concl.</i>					
	THANJAVUR TALUK— <i>Concl.</i>					
	VALLAM— <i>Concl.</i>					
261	Same pillar.				Tamil	Engraved in continuation of the above. Fragmentary. Gives the details of four boundaries of some land, obviously gifted. Śāvatat-Nakkar temple is referred to. In characters of about the 12th century.
261	Another pillar.				Do.	Seems to record an undertaking to supply one <i>uḷakku</i> of oil per month in the street Akalanka-perunderuvu at Vallam to burn a <i>sandhi</i> lamp to the goddess (<i>nācchiyār</i>) of the temple. In characters of about the 13th century.
262	Entrance of the same <i>maṇḍapa</i> . Western door-post.	Chōla	Parāntaka I	Regnal year 40	Do.	Records the gift of 96 sheep by Anantan-kkāri <i>alīas</i> Pirāntaka-Muttaraiyaṅ of Vadakulatuḷuppāḍi in Eriyūr-nāḍu to burn a perpetual lamp to the goddess Bhaṭṭāraki at Vallam. Kuvāvam-Piramaṇ received the sheep and undertook to supply daily one <i>uḷakku</i> of ghee to the lamp.

263	Front entrance in the same temple, right wall.	[Nāyaka of Thānjāvūr]		Do. . . .	Indifferently engraved, badly damaged and mutilated. Describes Achchutappanāyakarayan, as Sivappa-nayaka's agent. Seems to refer to the construction of a four pillared pavilion (<i>pandal</i>) and an <i>ardhamanḍapa</i> etc., at the request of some people. In characters of the 17th century.
TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT					
TIRUCHENDUR TALUK					
264	TIRUCHCHENDŪR.—Subrahmanya temple; east <i>gōpura</i> , entrance, south wall.		Kollam 739, Rudhirodgāri, Aippaṣi 15	Do. . . .	Damaged. Records the gift of 300 <i>paṇam</i> to the treasury of the temple of the deity Ilayaperumāl (i.e. Subrahmanya), in Tiruchchendilūr <i>aṭṭas</i> Tribhuvanamahādevichchaturvēdimangalam in Kuḍa-nāḍu by [V]irupparā Nāyakkar Pappaya-Ellappa-Nāyakkar, a <i>kavāḍai-nāyakkar</i> for supplying garlands, and for burning a perpetual lamp for the deity.
265	Same entrance, north wall.		Kollam 757 Kārttigai 15, ba. 5, Punarpūṣam, Tuesday, = 1581 A.D., November 14. f.d.t. '61. . . .	Do. . . .	Do. Seems to record an undertaking given by the accountants of the treasury of the temple of Ilaya-nāyanār at Tiruchchendilūr in Kuḍa-nāḍu to provide for food offerings and garlands to the deity on the occasion of the festival in the month of Āvaṇi in lieu of 60 <i>paṇam</i> received by them from Taṇḍalai Pillai Vēḷār Piḷḷaip-perumāl...piḷḷai.
266	Same wall.			Do. . . .	Records the obeisance of Śaṅkaraṇ. In late characters.

B.—INSCRIPTIONS ON STONE AND OTHER MATERIALS, 1975-76—Concl'd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	TAMIL NADU—Concl'd.					
	TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	TIRUCHCHENDUR—Concl'd.					
	TIRUCHCHENDŪR—Concl'd.					
267	Slab fixed in the south east corner in the second <i>prākāra</i> in the same temple.	Nāyaka of Madurai	Viśvanātha Nāyakkara ayyaṅ Tirumalai Nāyakkara	Śaka 1575, Kollam 829, Vijaya, Tai 23, Trayōdaśi, Friday, Puna- pūṣam = 1654 A.D., January 20.	Tamiḻ	Records that the king (<i>svāmi</i>) graced the place by his visit to protect Vaḍamalai[ya]ppa Piḷḷai. Also records the perpetual obeisance of Pūdanūdaṅ (Bhūtanāthaṅ).
268	Loose slab kept near the same place.	...		(1) 1845 A.D., March 26. (2) 1845 A.D., June 9, [Kollam*] 1020, Vaikāśi 29, Monday, Pūṣam.	Do.	Records that the repairing work of the kitchens, both of the pōttis and Nayinārs in the temple was commenced on the first date and ended on the second date when the same were consecrated.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE 1945-46 COLLECTIONS — *Contd.**

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	BENGAL WEST					
	CALCUTTA DISTRICT					
	CALCUTTA TAHSIL					
4110	CALCUTTA.—A pillar-base in the Indian Museum (M 2f). Findspot : Jamālpur mound, Mathurā, Mathura Tahsil and District, Uttar Pradesh.	...		[Śaka] 77, Gṛi. 4, di. 2 [9]	Mixed dialect, Brāhmī	Records the gift of Dēvila, the priest at the shrine of Dadhikarṇa. Published in <i>Mathurā Inscriptions</i> (ed. K.L. Janert), p. 70, No. 34 and plate.
4111	A stone slab. Findspot : Near the great temple at Bōdh-Gayā, Gaya Tahsil and District, Bihar.		Aśōkavalladēva	Lakṣhmanasēna year 51, Bhādrapada 29.	Sanskrit (corrupt), Gauḍīya	Begins with the Buddhist creed 'yē dharmā etc.' Describes the king as a <i>paramōpasaka</i> and as an adherent of the excellent Mahāyāna school (<i>pravaramahājānāyāvi</i>). Records that a <i>vihāra</i> was caused to be constructed along with an image of the Buddha by <i>bhaiṭa</i> Dāmōdara, <i>bhaiṭa</i> Paduma, <i>śiṣṭa</i> Rāghava and Mahipūkāla, with the assent of the king, at the instance of the <i>Kāsmira paṇḍita bhadanta Guchapathī, Rājagura(ru)-paṇḍita</i>

BIHAR									
PATNA DISTRICT									
BIHAR SHARIF TAHSIL									
4112	NĀLANDĀ.—A stone image of Bōdhisattva, discovered in the Stūpa mound. (Reg. No. 87). ¹				Sanskrit Siddha- māṭṛikā	Contains the Buddhist creed 'Yē dharmmā cte.' and records that this (the image) is the gift by Appaṭikā, the daughter of Rambhu. In characters of about the 8th century.			
DELHI									
4113	DELHI.—Inscriptions on the eastern wall of the third storey of the Kutub Minār. No. 1.				Nāgarī	Reads : <i>Sūtra. Lashamaṇa.</i> In characters of about the 12th century.			
4114	No. 2.				Do.	Reads : <i>Saha dyau suta Harinamdi.</i> Do.			

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	GUJARAT					
	JUNAGADH DISTRICT					
	JUNAGADH TAHSIL					
4115	CHŌBARI.—Inscriptions in a well No. 1					Reads : <i>Dēdā</i> . In characters of about the 14th century.
4116	No. 2					Reads : <i>Śrī</i> . Do.
4117	No. 3					Reads : Do. Do.
4118	No. 4					Reads : <i>Ghośkī</i> . Do.
4119	No. 5					Reads : <i>Līri</i> . Do.
4120	No. 6					Reads : <i>Sāta</i> . Do.
4121	No. 7					Reads : Do. Do.

SABARKANTHA DISTRICT

IDAR TAHSIL

4122 VADALI.—A pillar in the compound of Vaidyanātha temple.

....

Vikrama 1165,
Āṣō (For
Āsvayuja) ba.
3, Saturday =
1108 A.D.,
September 25
f.d.t. 22
(Friday and
not Saturday)

Sanskrit, Nāgari

Records the construction of the pillar by Sādhu, the son of Lashā(sha)maṇa, for the removal of karma.

KARNATAKA

BIJAPUR DISTRICT

BIJAPUR TALUK

4123 BIJAPUR.—Alikhan-ki-bāvaḍi near Ibrahim Roza.

....

Sulātāna Mahamadaśāha

Saka 1170
(for 1150 ?)
Sarvadhāri,
Chaitra śu. 1.

Do.

In embossed characters. Records the construction of a well (*prapā*) by the royal physician (*rājābhishag*) Viṭhalapamḍhari for the benefit of the people.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH					
	GOONA DISTRICT					
	MUNGAOLI TAHSIL					
4124	KADWĀHĀ FORT.—A loose stone slab found in the debris of the Hindu monastery.			(1) [Vikrama] 84 (2) [Vikrama] 135	Sanskrit (corrupt), Nāgarī	Probably a pilgrim's record. That this was written by <i>Pani</i> ^o Shē (Kshē)mañdhara, the son of <i>Pani</i> . Gaṅgādhara, who was the son of <i>Pani</i> ^o [Pī]lha ^o . in characters of about the 12th century. Cf. <i>An. Rep. Arch. Dept., Gwalior State</i> Samvat 1996, No. 2.
4125	Second loose stone slab.			Vikrama 1384, Mā [gha] śu. 10, Saturday = 1328 A.D., January 23.	Prakrit Nāgarī,	Contains a verse in the <i>upagiti</i> metre. Purport is not clear, but seems to refer to a night scene in Vasānta. The writer was Hōñdēva. Cf. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 8; <i>Abhilekh</i> , No 163.
4126	Third loose stone slab.				Do.	Fragmentary. Mentions the name Viramubhaṭṭa. In characters of about the 12 century. Cf. <i>An. Rep. Arch. Dept., Gwalior State</i> , Samvat 1996, No. 4.

4127	Fourth loose stone slab No. 1.			Vikrama 1540	Nāgarī	Probably a pilgrim's record. Cf. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 6; <i>Abhilēkh</i> , No. 321.
4128	No. 2			Vikrama 1551, Pushya śu (<i>tithi</i> omitted).	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Do. Contains the name of the writer Vēnī Achhūtipurī. Do.
4129	No. 3			Vikrama 1552	Do.	Do. Do.
4130	The still of a window in the second storey of the Hindu monastery.			Vikrama 1499,	Do.	Purport not clear. Mentions one Auṃ Rāya as the son of a person (name not clear). Cf. <i>An. Rep. Arch. Dept.</i> , <i>Gwalior State</i> , Samvat 1996, No. 23.
4131	A slab in the pavement of Bhūtēśvar temple in the Garhi.	Khalji	<i>Mahārājādhirāja Alauddin</i>	Vikrama 1366, Māgha śu. 11, Thursday = 1309 A.D., February 20. f.d.t., 33	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Records that the sage (<i>tapādhana</i>) Bhūtēśvara, worshipped the Mahālinga of Mūlāyatana when the world was harassed by the Mlēcchas. Also records that he did severe penance after the Mlēcchas had committed sins (<i>pātakas</i>) nineteen times and he made a new <i>jalādihāra</i> , when the previous one was broken by the Mlēcchas. The writers of the record were <i>Pam</i> Vatsarāja and <i>Pam</i> Kshēman-dhara. <i>Ibid.</i> , Samvat 1997, No. 4; <i>Abhilēkh</i> , No. 181.
4132	Loose stone slab.				Local dialect, Nāgarī	Fragmentary. Left side is broken and missing. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 12th century. <i>Ann. Rep. Arch. Dept.</i> , <i>Gwalior State</i> , Samvat 1996, No. 12.
4133	Another loose stone slab.				Do.	Do. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 15.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	GOONA DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	MUNGAOLI TAHSIL—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	KADWĀHĀ FORT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
4134	A ceiling slab of the Hindu monastery.	...		Year 1234	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Begins with a obeisance to Gaṇapati Purport not clear. Refers to Gōsurākāya. Ibid., No. 28.
4135	Foot of an image unearthed in debris of the Hindu monastery.				Do. . .	Reads : <i>Bhāṭṭāraka Śrī [Vakrasādhu ?]</i> In characters of about the 10th century. Ibid., No. 29.
	INDORE DISTRICT					
4136	SUNEL.—Inscriptions in the wells. No. 1.			(1) Saṁmat 1934 (2) Saṁmat 1937 (3) Saṁmat 1939 (4) Saṁ 1954	Hindī, Nāgarī	Fragmentary. Purport not clear. Gives different amounts in rupees, annas and pais against each of the years given and mentions a well (<i>vāvaḍī</i> 1.5) and Mukūṁdamādhava (1.6).

4137	No. 2					Do.	Do. Mentions certain <i>paṭēla</i> named Ratna . . . sīghaji.
4138	Sati stones in the same village No. 1.					Do.	Carelessly written. Mentions one Gautam (1.2) and seems to record the performance of <i>sati</i> (1.4).
4139	No. 2					Sanskrit, Nāgari	Seems to record the performance of <i>sati</i> by Mandā, the wife of the Dubē Mamgā.
4140	No. 3					Local dialect, Nāgari	Purport not clear. Mentions <i>Sahā Kānhēya</i> (1.3) and <i>Sōhaḍa</i> (lines) 4 and 5).
4141	No. 4. Findspot : Manje-Narain- khedi.					Do.	Seems to record the performance of <i>sati</i> . Men- tions <i>Sā</i> . Lālaji, <i>Rāja</i> Udaji and <i>Sitāji</i> .
4142	No. 5. Findspot : Lalagaon.					Do.	Damaged. Mentions śrī Saṁvahaji. Other details lost.
4143	No. 6. Findspot Sangalia.					Hindi, Nāgari	Mentions a certain <i>Mahārāja</i> [Rājma and Narasīgajīrāma. Seems to record the perfor- mance of <i>sati</i> by . . . mārīji.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH—Contd.					
	INDORE DISTRICT— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	SUNEL— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
4144	Inscriptions in the Krishna Mandir. . . .				Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Records the obeisance of Limvāditya. In characters of about the 11th-12th centuries.
	MANDASORE DISTRICT					
	GAROTH TAHSIL					
4145	DASORIA.—A <i>sati</i> stone in the village. . . .			Samvat 1556	Hindi, Nāgarī	Records the performance of <i>sati</i> probably by Dhamā (Dharmā) daughter of Vijā, a <i>sūtra-dhāra</i> .
4146	GARŌTH.— <i>Bania Sati</i> stones in the locality. No. 1. . . .		...	Satiya [r*] 1553 (?)	Do. . . .	Indistinct. Seems to refer to a <i>Sādhu</i> and to record the performance of <i>sati</i> probably by ..kalā.

4147	No. 2.			Vikrama 1555, Vaiśākha śu. 5, Wednesday = 1498 A.D., April 25, f.d.t. '70.	Local dialect, Nāgari	Records the death of the <i>sāha</i> Dēvō, son of <i>sāha</i> Chōhatha and the performance of <i>sāi</i> by his wife Dēvaladē.
4148	HANMATYĀ.—Stone in the Lakshminārāyaṇa temple.			Vikrama 1927, Śaka 1792, Chitrabhānu, Uttarāyaṇa, Vasantarītu, Vaiśākha śu. 3, Tuesday, Rōhiṇī = 1870 A.D., May 3.	Do.	Gives the details of the date only. Other details are perhaps lost.
4149	Inscription in the temple of Śiva.			Vikrama 17[9]8, Phālguna śu. 5, Saturday = 1742 A.D., February 27, f.d.t. '49.	Do.	Seems to record the completion of the construction of Kāmēśvararāji temple and mentions several individuals such as Rāpūji Saṃgrāmasīgha, Jagatasīgha etc., some along with their wives.
415	MAILKHEDA.—Inscriptions in a Jaina temple.			Vikrama 1925, Vaiśākha śu. 13, Monday = 1868 A.D., May 4.	Sanskrit, Nāgari	Records the installation of [the image of] the <i>bhaiṭāraka</i> Siddhasēna on the date given, by the <i>bhaiṭāraka</i> Harichandraji, the head of the Kandakundāchāryāmnaya of Balātkārā-gaṇa of the Sarasvatī-gachchha and Mūlasīgha in the village Mēlakhēdā. Also gives the <i>pañjāvālī</i> of the said <i>āmnāya</i> .

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS —Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH — Contd.					
	MORENA DISTRICT					
	MORENA TAHSIL					
4151	MITĀVALI.—Chauki (entrance) of Ekōttaraso Mahādēva temple.				Nāgarī	Refers to Saptamī, Śrīkrīṣṇa ... and Ākrīṣh- īnāthā. In characters of about the 13th- 14th century. S. a. <i>An. Rep. Arch. Dept., Gwalior State, 1942-43, No. 9.</i>
4152	Do.			Saṁvat 1565	Do.	After the date seems to read <i>Dasalōyō Sapta.</i>
4153	A slab found in the same temple, while digging.		<i>Mahārāja Kīrtti- sīnghadēva Rāisingha- dēva</i>	...	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Seems to refer to the king's reign. In characters of about the 15th century. <i>An. Rep., Arch. Dept. Gwalior State, 1942-43 No. 11.</i>
	REWA DISTRICT					
4154	Silaharā near Dhārsagar. Inner wall of the Durvāsā cave.		Sāmidata		Prakrit, Brāhmi	Records that Mogaliputa Mūladeva a Vatsa (Vachha) who was the son of Sivamita, grandson of Sivadata and the great grandson of Sivānamdi raised a garden (<i>arāma</i>) on the hill (<i>pavata</i>). In characters of about the 1st century A.D. Published in <i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXII, No. 1, p. 36.

4155	The inner wall of the Chēri-Gōdaḍi cave. Inscription No. 1			Do. . . .	Fragmentary. Mentions the son of Sivamīta, the grandson of Sivadata and the great grandson of Sivānāṁdi. Do. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 3, p. 36.
4156	Inscription No. 2			Do. . . .	Records the making of a cave (<i>silāgahā</i>) by the minister (<i>amachena</i>) Mogaliputa Mūla-dēva who was the son of Sivamīta, the grandson of Sivadata and the great-grandson of Sivānāṁdi of Vatsa-gōtra. Do. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 2, p. 36.
4157	Inner wall of the Sitāmāḍi cave.			Do. . . .	A copy of the above. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 4, p. 36.
4158	A pillar in the same cave.			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Yuvati-māle</i> . In characters of about the 2nd century A. D. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 6, p. 36.
5159	East wall of the same cave.			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Uḍaya tārā</i> . Do. <i>Ibid.</i> , No. 7, p. 36.
VIDISHA DISTRICT					
4160	BESNAGAR.—Inscriptions in the Museum. No. 1			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Gū[ṇa]nasa</i> . In characters of about the 2nd century B.C.
4161	No. 2			Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Balagutasa, dā[ṇam*]</i> In characters of about the 1st century A.D.
4162	No. 3			Do. . . .	Fragmentary. Reads : ... <i>ṣaam[ā]tusa</i> .. Do.
4163	No. 4			Do. . . .	Reads : 1 <i>Amimāp[ī]tānāmī</i> 2 <i>kupi</i> . In characters of about the 1st century B.C.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS —Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
4164	MADHYA PRADESH— <i>Concl'd.</i> VIDISHA DISTRICT— <i>Concl'd.</i> BESNAGAR— <i>Concl'd.</i> No. 5 MAHARASHTRA AURANGABAD DISTRICT KANNAD TALUK ELLŌRA.—Seat of the Pārśvanātha image in the temple, on the northern spur of the hill.		...		Prakrit, Brāhmi	Reads : <i>Supratish[ī]ā</i> . In characters of about the 9th century A.D.
4165	ELLŌRA.—Seat of the Pārśvanātha image in the temple, on the northern spur of the hill.			Saka 1156, Jaya, Ph'lguṇa śū. 3, Wednesday= 1235 A.D., February 21.	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Extols Chakrēsvara, son of Mhālugi and Svarnnā, and the grandson of Rānugi at Śrī[va]*rdhanāpura. Records that Chakrēsvara constructed a <i>chātīya</i> for Pārśvanātha on a hill and converted the Chāranādri into a holy place (<i>tīrtha</i>) by making (<i>virachya</i>) a number of images (<i>bimba</i>) of the <i>Jinas</i> . Published in <i>Inscriptions from the caves, temples of Western India</i> , pp. 99-100. Noticed in Kielhorn's Southern List, No. 973.

NASIK DISTRICT							
CHANDOR TALUK							
4166	CHANDOR.—In the temple of Rēṇukā.				Śaka [1]673, Prajāpati, Āśvina śu. 10, Thursday = 1751 A.D., September 19.	Do. . . .	Records the construction of a <i>dharmasālā</i> obviously at Chandrapura by Mōrśvara <i>alias</i> Mēujōgi of the Kauśika-gōtra and the Bahvṛicha-śākhā. Gives the donor's genealogy. Chandrapura is said to have included 160 villages.
YEOLA TALUK							
4167	ANKAI TANKAI.—Pedestal of the image No. 3 in cave No. 6.					Do. . . .	Records the obeisance of Lashumana (Lakshmana). In characters of about the 14th century.
4168	Pedestal of the image No. 2 in cave No. 8.					Do. . . .	Reads : <i>Kō[itu]sēṭhi. Do.</i>
4169	Pedestal of the image No. 5 in cave No. 8.					Do. . . .	Reads : <i>...sēṭhi. Do.</i>
4170	Pedestal of the image No. 4 in cave No. 8. Inscription No. 1.					Do. . . .	Seems to record the obeisance of one Śri-Ka- [ṛṇa]. Do.
4171	Inscription No. 2.					Do. . . .	Records the obeisance of Śriyo(yaḥ)pati Sēṭhi. Do.
4172	Inscription No. 3.					Do. . . .	Records the obeisance of a person whose name appears to be Mālasēṭhi. Do.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
4173	<p>MAHARASHTRA—<i>Concid.</i></p> <p>POONA DISTRICT</p> <p>JUNAR TAHSIL</p> <p>JUNNĀR.—The right hand wall outside the verandah between the octagonal pilaster and the doorway into the next verandah in the unfinished <i>Chaitiya</i> at Mānmoḍi hill.</p>				Prakrit, Brāhmi	Fragmentary. Mentions a lay-worshipper (<i>upāsaka</i>) the merchant (<i>nēgama</i>), the son of Satamala and (son of) Virabhuti. In characters of about the 2nd century A.D. S.a. Lüders' List, No. 1172.
4173	<p>PUNJAB</p> <p>KANGRA DISTRICT</p> <p>NURPUR.—Stone slab on the Rainon kā Thākur-dvārā.</p>		Virasimha	<p>Vikrama 1870</p> <p>(<i>kha-dharā-</i> <i>bhrit-nāga-</i> <i>prīhvī</i>), ...śu. Monday</p>	Sanskrit, Nāgari	Records the renovation (<i>saṁskāra</i>) of a temple (<i>dēvalaka</i>) of Śiva at the town Nūra by one Jvālānandanaka of Rājānavāṁsa. Noticed in <i>PRAS.</i> , N.C. 1904-05, No. 1.

RAJASTHAN

KOTAH DISTRICT

4175 BADVĀ.—*Yūpa* posts in the village. No. 1.

Maukhari

Mahāsēnāpati Sōmadēva,
son of Bala

Kṛita year
(i.e. Vīkrma)
295, Phālguna
śu. 5.

Sanskrit,
Brāhmi

Records that the pillar in question is the sacrificial pillar (*yūpa*) of Sōmadēva in connection with the *Trirātra* sacrifice with the sacrificial fees of thousand cows. *Ep. Ind*, Vol. XXIII, p. 52, No. B and plate.

4176 No. 2

Do.

Mahāsēnāpati Balasimha,
son of Bala

Do

Do.

Contains a similar record in connection with the *yūpa* of the *Trirātra* sacrifice of Balasimha. *Ibid.*, No. C and plate.

PALI DISTRICT

BALI TAHSIL

4177 SEVADĪ.—Lintel of cell No. 28 in the Mahāvira templ.

....

....

Saṁvat 1296

Sanskrit, Nāgari

Damaged. Records the construction of some part of the temple which is not clear.

4178 Beam of cell No. 12 in the same temple.

....

....

Saṁvat 1198,
Āsvija ba.
13, Sunday=
1141 A.D.,
August 31;
or 1142 A.D.,
October 18.

Sanskrit,
(corrupt),
Nāgari

Records the depositing (*nishēpa*) of (certain amount) by the members of a committee (*gōshṭhi*) for the construction of a chamber (*apavarikā*) to the east of (the image or shrine of) Arishānēmi and a door for an entrance (*dvāra-yatra*) on a wall (*bhitti*) in front.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Contd.					
	SIKAR DISTRICT					
	DANTARAMGARH TAHSIL					
4179	JIN-MĀTĀ.—A pillar in the Jīn-Mātā temple.			Samvat 1520, Bhādra ba. 2, Mondy— 1463 A.D., August 1. The month was <i>Pūrṇi-</i> <i>mānta</i> .	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Mentions Lashamaṇa, the son of <i>Ṭha</i> . Hara- dāsa and grandson of <i>Ṭha</i> Saraga of Māṇṇikabhaṇḍārī- <i>vanīśa</i> . Noticed in <i>PRAS</i> , <i>W. Circle</i> , 1909-10, p. 11, No. 2510.
	SIROHI DISTRICT					
	ABU ROAD TAHSIL					
4180	MOUNT ĀBŪ.—Vimalashah temple. Lintel of cell-shrine No. 47 in the corridor.			Sam̄ [vat*] 1245 . . .	Do.	Records the construction of a temple for Nami by the <i>manirīn</i> Yaśovīra, who was a son of Udaya and a disciple of Śāntisūri. belonging to the Yaśobhadrasūri-samtāna of Shañ- dēra- <i>gachchha</i> . Published in <i>Arhuda</i> <i>Prāchīna Jaina Lēkha Saṁdōha</i> , part II, p. 59, No. 151.

4181	Vastupāla and Tejahpāla temple. Front wall of cell-shrine No. 42 in the corridor.		Vikrama 1288	Do. . . .	Contains the date only. Probably a part of the another inscription. Cf. <i>ibid.</i> p. 149, No. 365.
4182	Below the above No. 4181.			Do. . . .	Records the details of the <i>tīthi</i> and month of the <i>pañcha-kalyāṇas</i> of śrī-Suvīdinātha. In characters of about the 12th century. <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 149-50, No. 357.
4183	Vastupāla temple. A pilaster in the <i>chandan śilā-maṇḍapa</i> .		Samvat 1361	Do. . . .	Records the obeisance of Jayasēnōpādhyāya who was the disciple of Varddhamaṇa-sūri of the Chaitra-gachchha, to Ādinātha and Nēminātha. <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 155, No. 384.
4184	Vastupāla and Tejahpāla temple. Base of an image of Pārśvanātha in a small-shrine (top most).		Samvat 1389, Phālguna śu. 8, Monday= 1333 A.D., February 22.	Do. . . .	Records the making of a pair (<i>yugala</i>) of Jina (images) by <i>Mahamī</i> Dhāmānala, the son of Pūmnaśiṭha and Pūnasiri, the former being the son of <i>Mahamī</i> Kūmarā in the Mahāvira chaitya of Muṇḍasthala belonging to the Kōreṃṭakīya-gachchha and Nannāchārya-saṃtāna, along with his brothers Mūlū, Gēhā, Rūdā, for the merit of his elder <i>bāndhava</i> (brother) <i>Mahamī</i> Dūdā. The images were consecrated by Nannasūri and Kakkasūri
4185	Vimalashah temple. Base of the standing image of Pārśvanātha in the inner <i>maṇḍapa</i> .		Samvat 1408, Vaiśākha śu. 5, Thursday= 1352 A.D., April 5.	Do. . . .	Records the installation of two images of Jina (<i>Jina-yugala</i>) in the Yugādidēva-prāsāda by Mā° Dhādūke for the merit of the members of his family (names given), all belonging to Kōreṃṭaka-gachchha and Nannāchārya-saṃtāna. The images were consecrated by Kakkasūri. Published in the <i>Arbuda Prāchīna Jaina Lēkha Sandōha</i> part II, p. 12, No. 10.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS — *Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	SIROHI DISTRICT—<i>Cont'd.</i>					
	ABU ROAD TAHSIL—<i>Cont'd.</i>					
	MOUNT ABŪ—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
4186	Another standing image of Pārśvanātha in the inner hall of the Vimalashah temple.			Do. . .	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Contains a copy of the above with slight variations. Ibid., p. 13, No. 11.
4187	Vastupāla temple. Parapet of upper <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Samvat 1417, Āshāḍha śū. 5, Thursday = 1360 A.D., June 18. f.d.t. '45	Do. . .	Records the obeisance and visit of Jayasīnhasūri who was also known as Vādisīnha and who belonged to the Kṛishṇarīshi-gachchha to Nēminātha. Ibid., p. 154, No. 381.
4188	Actual position not known.			Do. . .	Do. . .	Records the perpetual obeisance of Muniyāyaka the disciple of Muniśekhara-sūri of Bṛihad-gachchha, to Nēminātha. Ibid., p. 154, No. 380.

4189	Do.				Saṃvat 1484, Vaiśākha ba. 9, Saturday= 1427 A.D., April 19, f.d.t. '35.	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the obeisance of <i>Sūtra</i> ° Gopāli etc. to Nēmayiṇa i. e. Nēmi Jina.
4190	Vastupāla temple. A pillar in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> .				Vikrama 1528 Mārgasara be. 7	Do.	Seems to be a pilgrim record. Mentions <i>Sūtra- dhāra</i> Lāshā of Dhīrī (i. e. Delhi) and of Nāgrādi-gōtra (i. e. Nāgara-gōtra). Ibid., p. 157, No. 393.
4191	Probably a pillar in the same temple.				Saṃvat 1531, Vaiśākha ba. 2	Do.	Records the perpetual obeisance of <i>Saṃghavī</i> Rājā a resident of śrī-Maṇḍapadurgga, to- gether with his wife, Suhava, and the other members of the family, to Nēminātha. Ibid., p. 155, No. 387.
4192	Right-side of the above No. 4191.				Saṃvat 1531, Vaiśākha śu. 2, Monday= 1474 A.D., April 18,	Do.	Records the perpetual obeisance of <i>Saṃghavī</i> Vēla who belonged to the Prāgvātapura, to- gether with his wife Arashū, their son <i>Saṃ- ghanāyaka Sani</i> ° Jēsīm[ga°], his wife Māṇiki and their daughter <i>Sami</i> ° Jivini along with the other important members of the family, and the members of the Mālavīya-saṃgha, to Nēminātha in Arbudagiri-tirtha. Ibid., p. 156, No. 388.
4193	A pillar in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> .				Vikrama 1551, Śrāvaṇa ba, 14.	Do.	Seems to record the name Toghā of a pilgrim.
4194	Probably a pillar in the same temple.				Do.	Do.	Mentions Tolhā and others obviously pilgrims, Published in <i>Arbuda Prāchīna Jaina Lēkha</i> <i>Sandōha</i> , Part II, p. 157, No. 392.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Contd.					
	SIROHI DISTRICT—Contd.					
	ABU ROAD TAHSIL—Contd.					
	MOUNT ABŪ—Contd.					
4195	Corner pilaster of the raised platform in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Samvat 1563	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the making of the images of Nēminātha and Dharamanātha by Sa° Kēlhā Duṅgara and the members of his family. Ibid., p. 155, No. 383.
4196	Probably a pillar in the same temple.			Samvat 1613, Vaisākha śu. 9	Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Records the obeisance of Munivijayadēva who was a disciple of <i>Bhaṭṭāraka</i> Pūnyaprabhāsūri of the Brīhad-gachchha, to Nēminātha. Ibid., p. 156, No. 389.
4197	A pillar in the lower <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Samvat 1617, [Vaisākha] ba. 3, [Thursday] = 1561 A.D., May 1. f.d.t. '23	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Records the pilgrimage by Narayaṇa <i>i.e.</i> Nārāyaṇa) and others to Virapura. Ibid., p. 157, No. 396.

4198	Probably a pillar in the same <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Saṁvat*] 1655, Phāguṇa ba. 5	Do. . . .	Records the pilgrimage of Vuhārā, Hāmsā, and Manāutra who were probably the residents of Sirāhi (Sirāhi). Mentions <i>Sūtra Nēta</i> , <i>Rāuta Shāmasi</i> and others. Ibid., p. 156, No. 391.
4199	A pilaster near the shrine-door.			Saṁvat*] 1740, Jētha (Jyēshtha) śu. 3	Do. . . .	Records the pilgrimage of <i>Sūtra Jesaṅgha</i> . Ibid., p. 181, No. 461.
4200	A pilaster of the raised platform in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Saṁvat 176[5], Savaṇā (Śrāvaṇa) ba. 6 . . .	Do. . . .	Seems to record the pilgrimage of Ajabasiṅghaji etc. Ibid., p. 154, No. 379.
4201	Pavement of the upper <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Saṁvat 1850, Saita (Chai- tra) ba. 1, Monday = 1794 A.D., March 17.	Do. . . .	Mentions <i>Sūtra Tārāchanda</i> and <i>Sūtra Rūpā</i> of the Bhādraja (Bhāradvāja)-gōtra and the residents of Sādari and <i>Sūtra Virā</i> of Vasēsa (Vasishṭha)-gōtra who was the resident of Kāparalā. Ibid., p. 155, No. 386.
4202	Probably a pillar in the <i>maṇḍapa</i> .			Saṁvat 1911, Āsōja (Āsvijayuja) ba. 11, Saturday = 1855 A.D., October 6.	Do. . . .	Mentions Sōmapura <i>Sūtra Haranātha</i> , his son Ōshī and the latter's brother Idā of the Vachcha(Vatsa)-gōtra. Other details are not clear. Ibid., p. 155, No. 385.
4203	Vastupāla and Tējapāla temple. Front wall of cell-shrine No. 37.				Sanskrit, Nāgari	Enumerates the month and <i>tithis</i> of the <i>pañcha-kalyāṇakas</i> of śrī Abhinandana. In characters of about the 13th century. Ibid., p. 145, No. 356.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE 1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Concl'd.					
	SIROHI DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	ABU ROAD TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
	MOUNT ABŪ—Concl'd.					
4204	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 36 in the corridor.				Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Enumerates the months and <i>tithis</i> of the <i>pañcha-kalyāṅkas</i> of śrī Saṁbhavanātha. In characters of about the 13th century A.D. Ibid., p. 141, No. 351.
4205	The wall of cell-shrine No. 40 in the corridor.				Do.	Contains similar details regarding the <i>pañcha-kalyāṅkas</i> of śrī Supārśvadēva. Do. Ibid., p. 148-49, No. 364.
4206	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 45 in the corridor.				Do.	Contains similar information of śrī Vāsupūjyadēva. Do. Ibid., p. 151-52, No. 373.
4207	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 35 in the corridor.				Prakrit, Nāgarī	Gives similar information of śrī Ajitadēva. Do. Ibid., p. 139, No. 344.
4208	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 43 in the corridor.				Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Gives similar information regarding the <i>pañcha-kalyāṅkas</i> of śrī Sitaladēva. Do. Ibid., p. 150, No. 369.

4209	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 44 in the corridor.			Do. . . .	Contains similar details of the <i>pañcha-kalāvā- śākas</i> of śrī Srēyāmsadēva. Do. Ibid., p. 151, No. 371.
4210	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 46 in the corridor.			Do. . . .	Gives similar details of the <i>pañcha-kalāvāśākas</i> of śrī Vimalanātha. Do. Ibid., p. 152, No. 375.
4211	Front wall of cell-shrine No. 39 in the corridor.			Do. . . .	Records similar details of the <i>pañcha-kalāvāśākas</i> of śrī Padmaprabha. Do. Ibid., p. 148, No. 362.
UTTAR PRADESH					
ALLAHABAD DISTRICT					
MANHANPUR TAHSIL					
4212	PABHŌSĀ.—West wall of the cave.			Mixed dialect, Brāhmī	Gives the genealogy of the king and records that (a cave) was caused to be made by Aśhāḍhasēna. In characters of about the 1st century B.C. Published in <i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. II, pp. 240 ff., No. II and plate.
JHANSI DISTRICT					
LALITPUR TAHSIL					
4213	CHANDPUR NEAR JAHAS- PUR.—A square column near the lake.			Sanskrit, Nāgari	Partly lost. Extols Lakshmidhara, foremost among brāhmanas (<i>vīpramukhya</i>) and descri- bes him as the son of Sādhāraṇa and the grandson of Sōlēnayāka of the Kausika- gōtra. In characters of about the 12th cen- tury.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH— <i>Concl'd</i>					
	LUCKNOW DISTRICT					
	LUCKNOW TAHSIL					
4214	LUCKNOW.—Pedestal of a standing figure of a Buddha in the Provincial Museum (B. 10). Findspot : Kaiṛā mound, Mathura District.			[Śaka] 280	Sanskrit, Brāhmi	Records the gift of the Śākya <i>bhikṣuṇī</i> (nun) Jayabhāṭṭā at the Yaśōvihāra dedicating the merit (of the gift) for the attainment of supreme knowledge by all sentient beings. Published in <i>Mathurā Inscriptions</i> (ed. by K.L. Janert), pp. 34-35, No. 8, and plate,
4215	Probably pedestal of an image in the Museum, No. IJ. 787.			Saṁvat 1093, Āsā(śhā)- dha śudi [6, Wednesday] = 1036 A.D., June 2.	Local dialect, Nāgarī	Seems to mention <i>sūtra</i> . Maṇa. Purport not clear.

MATHURA DISTRICT

MATHURA TAHSIL

4216	MATHURĀ.—Pedestal of an image of a seated Bōdhisattva broken vertically into two pieces in the Museum (No. 2740). Findspot : Not known.	Kushāna	Kanishka	[Śaka] 16, Va 1, di.	Prakrit, Brāhmī	Fragmentary. Records the gift of an image of the Bōdhisattva by the monk ((<i>bhikkhu</i>) Nāgadatta, a resident of the <i>vihāra</i> , in the Kashīka (Kashīkiya) <i>vihāra</i> in his own Chaityakuṭī.....together with the resident of the <i>vihāra</i> , for the workshops of all Buddhas (and) for welfare and happiness of all sentient beings, for the acceptance of the Mahāsaghiya (<i>Mahāsāighika</i>) teachers. Published in <i>Mathura Inscriptions</i> , pp. 191-92, No. 157 and plate.
4217	Raised rim over the front relief of a fragmentary Jina (?) image in the same museum. Findspot: Not known.	Do.	Huvishka	[Śaka] 50, Hē, di. [2]	Mixed dialect, Brāhmī	Damaged. Purport not clear. Noticed in Lüders' List, No. 51.
4218	Base of a pillar in the same Museum. Findspot : Jamālpur mound, Mathura District.			[Śaka] 77, Va 11	Prakrit Brāhmī	Reads : <i>Dattya 20 6</i> preceding the date. Published in <i>Mathurā Inscriptions</i> , pp. 72-73, No. 37, and plate.

C.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE 1945-46 COLLECTIONS — Concl'd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language A and alphabet	Remarks
4219	<p style="text-align: center;">FOREIGN COUNTRIES BANGLA DESH</p> <p>JHEWARI. — Pedestal of a metal image of the Buddha.</p>				Sanskrit, Gauḍiya	Records the gift (<i>dāyadharmma</i>) of <i>Muhira</i> Subhadatta for the attainment of knowledge by all sentient beings beginning with his parents. In characters of about the 10th century A.D.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHERA PRADESH					
	HYDERABAD DISTRICT					
	HYDERABAD TAHSIL					
1	GÖLKONÐĀ.—Fort. Loose slab lying in the office of the Conservation Assistant, Archaeological Survey of India. Findspot : Boundary wall of the Imliwālī-Bāōlr in the Fort.	Quṭb Shāhi	[Ibrāhīm]	A.H. 97 x (words)	Persian verse, Thulṭh	Fragmentary. Records the construction of a mosque by Mirzā Buzurg.
2	Do. Slab fixed in the ground near the door of the Ambār Khāna.	Do.	'Abdu 'llāh	A.H. 1052, Rajab = 1642 A.D., September- October	Persian, Nasta'liq	Assigns the construction of the granary (Ambār Khāna) to Khairāt Khān. Published, <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1907-08, p. 27 (without plate) and 1913-14, 57, pl. XVIII b.
3	Do. Loose slab lying near the Salāh Klāna. Obverse and reverse.				Persian, Naskh; Telugu	Bilingual. Damaged. Records the excavation of a well in the name of twelve Imāms and its endowment (for public use) by Shāh 'Alīshah son of Shah Wali son of Shāh (name lost). In characters of about the 10th century.

4	HYDERĀBĀD.—Graveyard called Dāira Mir Momin. Headstones of graves. No. 1, obverse.		A.H. 1225 Dhu'l-Qa'da 7, Wednesday = 1810 A.D., December 4 (Tuesday)	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of the late Mir Muḥammad Mahdi Khān.
5	Do. Reverse.		A.H. 1225 (& chronogram) = 1810 A.D.	Persian prose & verse, Nasta'liq	Do. Further describes him as a follower of Ḥasanain (i.e. Ḥasan and Ḥusain grandsons of the Prophet). Composed by Ja'fari.
6	No. 2		A.H. 1225 (& chronogram), Muḥarram 5 = 1810 A.D., February 10.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Contains the death-record of the wife (Name not mentioned) of Nawwāb Khān-i-Zamān (lit. Khān of the Time).
7	No. 3		A.H. 1134, Ṣafar 3 = 1721 A.D., November 12.	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Shāhr Bānū Begam.
8	No. 4		A.H. 1[0]85 = 1674-75 A.D.	Persian, Naskh	Records the name Gauhar Sulṭān daughter of Muḥammad Sharif.
9	No. 5		A.H. 1258, Jumādā I 12, night of Thursday = 1842 A.D., June 21 (Tuesday).	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Sa'ādātū'n-Nisā Begam <i>alias</i> Phatrū or Pathrū Begam.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—Contd.					
	HYDERABAD DISTRICT —Contd.					
	HYDERABAD TAHSIL—Contd.					
	HYDERĀBĀD—Contd.					
10	No. 6			A.H. 1081, Ramaḡān 17 = 1671 A.D., January 18 .	Persian, <u>Thulth</u>	Refers to the death of some one (name not given).
11	No. 7			A.H. 1264, Ramaḡān 25= 1848 A.D., August 25 .	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the demise of a lady named Karima Bi.
12	No. 8			A.H. 1221 (& chronogram), Ṣafar 15, Monday= 1806 A.D., May 4 .	Persian verse, Naskh	Records the death of Riḡā Begam.

13	No. 9				A.H. 1067(?), Rabi'II 19= 1657 A.D., January 25	Records the death of Mir-i-Mirān, a Sayyid.
14	No. 10				A.H. 1262, Shawwāl 2= 1846 A.D., September 23	States that Hāji Bilāl died on the given date.
15	No. 11				A.H. 1086 1675-76 A.D.	Records the death of Mir Ahmad son of Mir Ismā'il.
16	No. 12				A.H. 1164 (& chronogram) =1750-51 A.D.	Records the death of Khān Rustam Jang, a great noble and a man of erudition. Composed by Siik.
17	No. 13				A.H. 1207= 1792-93 A.D.	Records the demise of Hakīm Mirzā Ahmad entitled Muḥammad Ghīyāthū'd-Dīn Khān Bahādur Ghīyāthū'd-Daula son of Hakīm Ghīyāth son of Mirzā Baqir son of Hāji Ghīyāth son of Nizāmu'd-Dīn Ahmad entitled Nawwāb Hakimu'l-Mulk Gilāni.
18	No. 14				A.H. 1059 (words)= 1649-50 A.D.	Records the death of Maulānā 'Abdu's-Ṣamad.
19	No. 15 (Loose).				A.H. 1087, Rajab 17= 1676 A.D., September 15	Records the death of Hayā Khānam.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
20	ANDHRA PRADESH—Contd. HYDERABAD DISTRICT —Contd. HYDERABAD TAHSIL —Contd. HYDERĀBĀD—Contd. No. 16				Persian prose & verse, Nasta'liq	Incomplete, the lower portion of the tablet having been built up in the ground. The extant portion refers to it as the epitaph of (the famous Persian poet) Mirzā Abū Turāb Riḍāvi Maṣḥadī, with the pen-name Fīrat. Further quotes the Quatrain (<i>rubā'i</i>) (composed by him) which was on his lips at the time of death, and another one composed by his son (also a famous Persian poet) Mirzā Raḡī with the pen-name Dānish. Only one hemistich of the Fragment containing the chronogram of the former's death, composed by another poet Muzaḥfiar Ḥusain, by name, is visible. In characters of about the 17th century. Published only partly in <i>Landmarks of the Deccan</i> (Hyderabad, 1927), p. 49.

21	No. 17			A.H. 1045 (& chronogram)= 1635-36 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Eulogises the poetical talents of Kāmi, the 'Creator of Ideas' and the 'sovereign in (the realm of) ideas' and records his death.
22	No. 18			A.H.1011, Rabī'ī, night of Wednesday= 1602 A.D., August (Monday).	Persian, Nasta'liq	States that Āghā Husain died after one <i>pahar</i> and five <i>ghari</i> had elapsed on the given date.
23	No. 19			A.H. 1075 (words)≠ 1664-65 A.D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh	Records the death of Mir Murtaḡā.
24	No. 20			A.H.1104, Dhu'l-Hijja 19=1693 A.D., August 11	Arabic, Naskh	Records the death of the venerable Sayyid Mir 'Abdu'l-Qādir son of Mir Muḥammad Mūsawī Shirāzi.
25	No. 21			A.H. 1071 (chronogram), Muharram= 1660 A.D., September- October	Persian verse, Thulth	Records the death of Hāji Shāh.
26	No. 22			A.H. 1086, Ramaḡān= 1675 A.D., December 8	Persian, Naskh	Records the death of Mir Sharafu'd-Dīn Ibrāhīm.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—Contd.					
	HYDERABAD DISTRICT—Contd.					
	HYDERABAD TAHSIL—Contd.					
	HYDERĀBĀD—Contd					
27	No. 23				Persian verse, Thulth	Incomplete, lower portion of the slab having been built up in the platform. Records the death of Ghulām 'Alī, a man of generosity and amiable disposition. In characters of about the 17th century.
28	No. 24			A.H. 1150 (& chronogram), Rajab 22 = 1737 A.D., November 4	Persian, Thulth	Records the death of Maulavi Hāji Muḥammad 'Alī son of 'Alī.
29	No. 25			A.H. 1116 (& chronogram) = 1704-05 A.D.	Persian verse, Thulth	Incomplete, lower portion of slab having been built up in the platform. Records the death of a person who is spoken of as a descendant of the Holy Prophet.

30	No. 26				Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of 'Aziz Begam.
31	No. 27			A.H. 1205, Jumādā I 19 1791 A.D., January 24	Arabic, Naskh	Records the death of Mulla 'Ali Naqī al-Māzandrānī.
32	No. 28			A.H. 1062 (words)= 1651-52 A.D.	Persian, Naskh	Records the death of Mir Muḥammad Mu'in Tafrishī son of Mir 'Abdu'l-Hakīm Tafrishī.
33	No. 29			A.H. 1014, Sha'bān = December 1605- January 1606 A.D.	Persian, Nasta'liq	States that Mir Husain 'Ali Khān obtained martyrdom on the given date.
34	No. 30			A.H. 1225, Jumādā II 5= 1810 A.D., July 8	Arabic, Naskh	Records the death of the son of the late Muḥammad Rafī.
35	No. 31			A.H. 1039 (words), Shawwāl 3, Thursday = 1630 A.D., May 6	Persian, Thulth	Records the death of Muḥammad Husain 'Adasī Shirāzi.
				A.D. 1077, Muharram 1, night of Friday = 1666 A.D., June 24		

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH					
	HYDERABAD DISTRICT —Contd.					
	HYDERABAD TAHSIL—Contd.					
	HYDERĀBĀD—Contd.					
36	No. 32			A. H. 1093, Rabi'II 1 = 1682 A. D., March 30 .	Persian, Naskh	Records the death of Muḥammad Mu'min Iṣfahāni.
37	No. 33			A. H. 1022, Shawwāl = 1613 A. D., November- December .	Arabic, Naskh	Records the death of Khwāja Ikārp.
38	No. 34			A. H. 1089 (& words), Sha'bān 12 = 1678 A. D., September 19	Persian, Thulth	Records the death of Muḥammad Zamān son of Mirzā Hādr [I]ṣfahāni.

39	No. 35				A.H. 1118, Rajab 5, Wednesday = 1706 A.D., October 2	Persian, Naskh	Records the demise of Hāji Muhammad <u>Shakib</u> .
40	No. 36					Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Nād-i-'Alī</i>). In characters of about the 18th century.
41	No. 37					Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Do. (Shiite <i>Durūd</i>). In characters of about the 17th century.
42	No. 38. (Loose). reverse.				A.H. 1017 (chronogram) = 1608-09 A.D.	Persian verse, <u>Thulth</u>	Records the death of Abu'l-Qāsim, a greatly popular person.
43	On a grave, same place.				A.H. 1253, <u>Shawwāl 28</u> = 1838 A.D., January 25	Persian Nasta'liq	Records the death of Mirzā Kūchak <i>alias</i> Muḥammad 'Alī son of Mirzā Ishāq Baig <u>Kāshāni</u> .
44	On another grave, same place.				A.H. 1254 (words), Ramaḍān 2 = 1838 A.D., November 19	Do.	Records the death of Mirzā Wali Baig son of <u>Jamshīd</u> Baig.
45	On the door of a walled enclosure in the same compound.				A.H. 1262 (& chronogram) = 1845-46 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Mu'īnu' d-Daula. Composed by <u>Sukhan</u> .

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	HYDERABAD DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	HYDERABAD TAHSIL— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	HYDERĀBĀD— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
46	Graveyard in Maḥalla 'Īdi Bazār, outside old Nāka. Headstones of graves. No. 1. Obverse and reverse.			A. H. 1077 (& chronogram), Safar 7, Mondy = 1666 A.D., July 30	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Naskh	Records the death of a lady name (?)Ṣāliḥa.
47	No. 2.			A. H. 1232 (& chronogram) 1816-17 A. D.	Persian verse, Nast'liq	Records the construction of a mosque and a high platform by way of a memorial to Ḥasan Muḥammad.
48	Graveyard called Māmā Kulthūm in the same Maḥalla. [Headstone of a grave.]			A. H. 1266, Shawwāl 1 = 1850 A.D., August 10	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Records the death of a lady (Begam).

49	SHAIKHPET. — Mosque called <i>Shaiḫ-kī-Masjid</i> . On seven panels of the central <i>miḥrāb</i> (one lying loose).	Quṭb Shāhi	'Abdu 'llāh	A.H. 1043 (& chronogram) = 1633-34 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Assigns the construction of the mosque to the king. Inscribed by Lufu'llāh al-Ḥusaini a't-Tabrīzī who also strove for its completion Cf. <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1935-36, p. 22, pl. XIII.
50	Sarāwāli-Masjid, to the west of the village. In the central <i>miḥrāb</i> .	Do.	[Abu'l-Ḥasan]	A.H. 1089 (& words) = 1678-79 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Thulth	Records the construction of a mosque (builder's name not given). Written by Ḥusain 'Alī.
51	Tomb to the south of the above mosque. On the top and sides of the grave.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter III, verse 17, Chapter I, Chapter II, verses 1-4 and part of verse 5 and 255 and Chapter IX, part of verse 33). In characters of about the 17th century.
52	Do. Above the southern doorway.		...		Arabic, Thulth	Records a saying to the effect that one who denies (Prophet) Muḥammad's status as the best of mankind is an infidel. Do.
53	Do. Below the outer western arch.			...	Do.	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i>) Chapter XXIII, part of verse 116). Do.
54	Do. Above the northern doorway.				Do.	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XXIII, verse 118). Do.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—Contd.					
	MAHBUBNAGAR DISTRICT					
	KOLLAPUR TALUK					
55	SŌMAŚĪLA.—Stone planted in front of Kamālu'd-Din Bābā Dargāh near the Sōmēsvara temple. (Impression from the Chief Epigraphist, Archaeological Survey of India, Mysore.)			A.H. 1052= 1542-43 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thuth</u>	Records the death of Sayyid Kamālu'd-Din.
	NIZAMABAD DISTRICT					
	BODHAN TALUK					
56	BODHAN.—Mosque called 'Alamgīr-kī-Masjīd, near the Civil Hospital. On a pilaster to the south of the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .	Mughal	Shāh Jahān	A.H. 1065 (chronogram) 1654-55 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that this mosque was built by Prince Aurangzeb on the site of a temple through the efforts of Ilāh Yār, an official of the king. Composed by Mashhādī and written by Firūz. Published, <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1919-20, pp. 17-18, pl. XV a.

57	On a pilaster to the north of the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .	Tughluq	[Muḥammad Shāh]		Arabic, Naskh	Fragmentary. Extant portion contains the titles of the king and benedictory prayers for the perpetuity of his reign and increase of his power and authority. In continuation of No. 58. below.	
58	Mosque called Patthar kī-Masjid, inside the mud-fort near the Girl's Middle School. Loose slab.	Do.	Do.		Do.	Do. Refers to the construction of an auspicious building in the reign of the king. Earlier part of No. 57 above. Cf. <i>ibid.</i> , 1919-20, p. 17, pl. XVI b.	
WARANGAL DISTRICT							
WARANGAL TALUK							
59	WARANGAL.—Fort. On the two minars of the gate of the 'Āshūr Kḥāna.			A.H. 1232 = 1816-17 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that Mir Muḥammad 'Alī built the sanctuary of (Prophet's grandson) Ḥusain son of 'Alī.	
60	Do. Loose slab in an enclosure near the Khurshid-Mahal.	Mughal	Shāh 'Ālam II	A.H. 1217 = 1802-03 A.D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Records the construction of the gate of (the building to house) the Panja (i.e. the replica of the Palm of the hand) of Murtaḍā 'Alī (the fourth Caliph), by Ghulām Ḥusain, during the time of Mir Nizām 'Alī Khān Bahādur, Vazīr of the province (<i>ṣūba</i>) of Dakan (i.e. Deccan). <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> 1931-32, p. 32, pl. XXI b.	
61	ZAFARGARH.—Gun lying near Primary School. On the muzzle.			A.H. 1188 = 1774-75 A.D.	Persian, Nasta'liq	Contains only the name (of the caster) Muḥammad Qāsim.	
62	Gun lying in the compound of the Jāmi' mosque. On the muzzle.			A.H. 1193 = 1779-80 A.D.	Do.	Do.	

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	ANDHRA PRADESH—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	WARANGAL DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	WARANGAL TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	WARANGAL—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
63	Gun lying on a bastion, to the west of the village.			Do. . . .	Persian, Nasta'liq	Contains only the name (of the caster) Muhammad Qasim.
	BIHAR					
	BEGUSARAI DISTRICT					
	BEGUSARAI TAHSIL					
64	NURPUR.—Jāmi' mosque. Above the central doorway.			A.H. 1213 (& chronogram) = 1798-99 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque by 'Azizullāh by the side of the grave of Miran 'Alī for the latter's merit. Composed by Rāḡī.

MONGHYR DISTRICT							
LAKHSARAI TAHSIL							
65 SHEIKHPURĀ.—Jāmi' mosque above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .		Arabic, Naskh	A.H. 1281 = 1864-65 A.D.				States that this was inscribed at Madina in the presence of Sayyid Baṣṣārat Karim Qādīrī, who was there as a pilgrim (<i>zā'ir</i>).
66 Above the central doorway, same place.		Persian verse, Nasta'liq	A.H. 1265 (& chronogram) 1848-49 A.D.				States that Baṣṣārat Karim repaired the old mosque.
SANTHAL PARGANAS DISTRICT							
RAJMAHAL TAHSIL							
67 RĀJMAHĀL.—Baṣī-Masjid in Mahalla Qasāipura. Above the entrance of the Hujra.		Arabic & Persian, Naskh	A.H. 964 (& words), Shawwāl 3(?), Friday = 1557 A.D., July 30				States that Masnad-i-'Alī Ibrāhīm Khān Ghāzī son of Amin Khān Sūr (?) who was endowed with good nature and piety, obtained martyrdom, in the prime of youth, while fighting the infidel insurgents, at two and a half <i>pās</i> (<i>prahar</i>) of the day on the given date. Cf. <i>Insc. Beng.</i> , Vol. IV, p. 241 : <i>Corp. Bihar</i> , p. 149, pl. 31.
68 Chhoṭī-Masjid. Above the central entrance.		Persian verse, Nasta'liq	A.H. 1103 (& chronogram) = 1691-92 A.D.	Aurangzeb	Mughal		Assigns the construction of a mosque to Shaikh 'Abdu'l-lāh. Composed by Ḥāfiẓ Ja'far. Cf. <i>Corp. Bihar</i> , p. 304, pl. 62 (a).
69 Tomb of Mainā Bibī. On the western wall, outer face.		Arabic, Thulth in Tughrā					Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i>), Chapter LXI, verse 13, Chapter XII, part of verse 64, Chapter XIII, part of verse 13, Chapter XLVIII, verses 1-3) In characters of about the 15th century.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	DELHI					
70	DELHI.—Qadam Sharif, in Maḥalla Pahārganj. Sides of a grave in the central chamber.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, verse 255). In characters of about the 17th century.
71	Bastī Nizāmu'd-Dīn. Tomb of Shamsu'd-Dīn Ataga Khān, to the east of the Dargāh of Ḥaḍrat Nizāmu'd-Dīn Auliya. Above the southern doorway.			A.H. 974 (words)= 1566-67 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	States that the building was completed on the given date under the supervision of Ustād Khudā Qulī. Published, <i>List. Hin. Mus. Mon. Delhi Province</i> , Vol. II, p. 175.
72	Panels on the left and right of the same doorway.			A.H. 974= 1566-67 A.D.	Arabic verse & prose, <u>Thulth</u>	Part only. Contains Arabic verses in praise of God. Written by Baqī Muḥammad al-Kātib (lit. Scribe). For the full text, see <i>Arch. Sur. Ind. Memoir</i> , No. 47, p. 24, Nos. 9-12.
73	Top and sides of three graves in the same Tomb. No. 1, easternmost (believed to be that of Jijī Anaga).			A.H. 1009= 1600-01 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, verse 255). <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 25, No. 17.

74	No. 2 (in the centre, that of Ataga Khān).			Arabic, Naskh & Naskh in Tughrā	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter III, part of verse 184, Chapter XCI, verses 1-9, Chapter LV, verses 26-27). In the same hand as No. 71 above. <i>Ibid.</i> , Nos. 14-16.
75	No. 3, to the west of No. 2.			Arabic, Thulth	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XII, verses 53-56). In the same hand as No. 71 above. <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 25, Nos. 18-19.
76	Grave of Ḥaḍrat Taqī'u'd-Dīn Nūh, to the north-east of the above Tomb. Footside.		A.H. 737 (words) = 1336-37 A.D.	Persian verse, Naskh	States that the man of spirituality, Mubashshir taken into God's mercy, whose face was to men like a bright moon, again girded up his loins for the service of (i.e. passed away and joined) his Spiritual Guide (i.e. Ḥaḍrat Nizāmu'd-Dīn).
77	Tomb of Ḥaḍrat Nizāmu'd-Dīn. Headstone in northern wall.		A.H. 970 (chronogram) = 1562-63 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq	States that the tomb of the saint was constructed by the Khān of great dignity, a Mir and Sayyid of Hāshimī descent (name not specified) through the efforts, also of a person of Hāshimī descent. Composed by Farīdūn and inscribed by Ḥusain (son of) Aḥmad Chishtī, Published, <i>List. Hin. Mus. Mon. Delhi Province</i> , Vol. II, p. 146.
78	Do. Jamā'at Khāna. On the facade, southern side.		A.H. 725 (chronogram) = 1324-25 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of 'Nizām (lit. organisation) of both the worlds' (i.e. Ḥaḍrat Nizāmu'd-Dīn). In characters of about the 16th century. <i>Ibid.</i> p. 152.
79	Enclosure containing the grave of Jahān Ārā, to the south-east of the above. Headstone of a grave.		A.H. 1092 = 1681-82 A.D.	Persian verse & prose, Naskh	Records the famous Persian verse prohibiting the covering of the grave except grass and the name of (Princess) Jahānārā, daughter of (Mughal emperor) Shāh Jahān Bādshāh Ghāzī and disciple of the Khwājagān-i-Chishtī (i.e. Chishtī order). <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 153.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	DELHI					
	DELHI					
80	Do. On the top and sides of the grave to the west of the above.			A.H. 1016 = 1607-08 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, verse 255, Chapter LV, part of verses 26-27 and First Creed). Cf. <i>Memoir Arch. Sur. Ind.</i> , No. 47, p. 29, Nos. (2), (3) and (4).
81	Kālī-Masjid, in Bastī Nizāmu'd-Dīn. On the eastern entrance.	Tughluq	Firūz Shāh	A.H. 772 (words) = 1370-71 A.D.	Persian, <u>Naskh</u>	Assigns the construction of the mosque to Junāshah Maqbūl, entitled Khān-i-Jahān, son of Khān-i-Jahān. <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 179.
82	ADCHINI.—Mosque near the Lodi Tomb of Bibī Hūr and Nūr. Above the doōrway.	Lodi	Sikandar Shāh	A.H. 915 (words), Rajab 12, Saturday = 1509 A.D., October 26	Do.	Records the construction of 'the blessed edifice' (i.e. the mosque) of Malikū'l-'Ulamā (lit. king of Learned men) Miyān 'Abdu'llāh son of Ilahdād Tālanbī. Published, <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1919-20, p. 9, pl, V a.
83	MAHRAULI. Dargāh of Quṭb Shāhib. On the northern gate.	Sūr	Sher Shāh	A.H. 948 (words) = 1541-42 A.D.	Persian verse, <u>Nasta'liq</u>	Records the construction of the gate under the supervision of Shaiikh Khahlū'l-Haq. Published, <i>List Hin. Mus. Mon. Delhi Province</i> , Vol. III, p. 26.

84	Do. Chhatrī near the Rājōn-kī-Bā'in. On the southern lintel.	Lodi	Sikandar Shāh	A.H. 912 (words), Rajab 1 = 1506 A.D. November 17	Persian, Naskh	Records the construction of the tomb (<i>gumbad</i> , lit. dome) by Daulat Khātūn Ahsak (?) wife of Khwāja Muḥammad. Cf. <i>Ep. Ind. Mus.</i> , 1919-20, p. 7, pl. III a.
85	Do. Tomb of Shāh 'Abdu'l-Haqq Dihlawī on the north-west bank of Haqq Shamsī. Below the dome, north side, inner face.			(1) A.H. 958 (Muḥarram) = 1551 A.D. (2) A.H. 1052 = 1642-43 A.D.	Do.	Gives particulars and details of the life and academic and religious career of Shāh 'Abdu'l-Haqq Muḥaddith of Delhi a great Traditionist and author of about 100 books on various subjects comprising in all 500,000 lines. He is stated to have acquired proficiency in the Science of Tradition (<i>Ḥadīth</i>) in the Holy Cities (i.e. Mecca and Madina) under celebrated teachers and divines and taught in India for 52 years. First date that of his birth and the second that of his death. In characters of about the 17th century. Published, <i>List Hin. Mus. Mon. Delhi Province</i> , Vol. III, p. 71.
86	Do. In the west wall of the same Tomb.				Arabic, Thulth	Contains religious text (First Creed). Do.
87	AHMADĀBĀD.—Dargāh of Maulānā 'Abdu's-Ṣamad Khudā Numā, Lāl-Darwāza. In the south wall.			A.H. 1109 = 1697-98 A.D.	Urdū verse, Nasta'liq	Contains a poem (<i>qasīda</i>) in mystic strain with Hori (Holi) as its theme, composed by the saint Bābā 'Abu's-Ṣamad Khudā Numā Bābā Ṣāhib. Date either that of composition or of the saint's death. In recent characters.

GUJARAT

AHMADABAD DISTRICT

AHMADABAD CITY TALUK

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	GUJARAT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	AHMADABAD DISTRICT <i>Concl.</i>					
	AHMADABAD CITY TALUK—<i>Concl.</i>					
	AHMADĀBĀD—<i>Concl.</i>					
88	Bībī Miṣrī-kī-Masjid, in Jān Šāhib-kī-Galī, same locality.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (First Creed). In characters of about the 18th century.
89	Khajuri-Masjid, Maḥalla Ḍhāl-garwāḏā. Above the central <i>mīḡrāb</i> .	Sulṭāns of Gujarat	Maḥmūd Shāh III	A.H. 955 (words) = 1548-49 A.D.	Do. . . .	Records the re-construction of the mosque by Mallū Sulṭānī, entitled <i>Khawwāṣu'l-Mulk</i> . Cf. <i>Mus. Mon. Ahmadabad</i> , pp. 79-80, No. XXXV (without plate).
90	Graves in the compound of Shīrāzī-Masjid, Maḥalla Aṣṭo-dīā. No. 1.			A.H. 1280 (& chronogram) = 1863-64 A.D.	Persian prose & verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Ṣadru'd-Dīn <i>alias</i> Sayyid Miḡyān.
91	No. 2.			A.H. 1276 (& chronogram) = 1859-60 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Najibu'n-Nisā Begam. Composed by Ṣabā.

92	Murghā-Masjid, near Delhi Darwāza. Above the central mihrāb.			Arabic, Naskh	Fragmentary. Contains religious text ((<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XXXVI, parts of verses 37-38, 47, 54-55, 66-67). In characters of about the 15th century.
93	Shukru'llāh-Masjid, Maḥalla Kālūpur. Headstone of a grave in the courtyard.		A.H. 1193 (& 3 chronograms) = 1779-80 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of a perfect saint (<i>Faḡīr-i Mukammal</i>).
94	Mullā Jīwan-ki-Masjid, Maḥalla Pānchpatti. Above the central mihrāb.		A.H. 1063 (& chronogram) 1652-53 A.D.	Do.	Assigns the construction of the mosque to Idrāk the Superintendent (<i>Nāẓir</i>) in the time of the governorship of Shā'ista Khān. Composed by Hādī. Cf. <i>Mus. Mon. Ahm.</i> , p. 89, No. XLV b (plate).
95	Nabi-ki-Masjid, Maḥalla Daryāpur. On a pillar in the verandah.		A.H. 1133 (& chronogram) 1720-21 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of a mosque by Ṣalābat Khān of noble lineage.
BANASKANTHA DISTRICT					
PALANPUR TALUK					
96	PĀLANPUR.—Baḡī Bazār-ki-Masjid. Above the central mihrāb.		A.H. 1180 (& chronogram) = 1766-67 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Naskh	Refers to the construction of the mosque.
97	Dev Bāi-ni-Masjid, Sunnī Borwād. On the wall near the Ablution-tank.		A.H. 1299 (& words) = 1881-82 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of the portico (<i>Dahlīz</i>) of the mosque of Dev Bāi by the Sunnī Bohras.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	GUJARAT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	BANASKANTHA DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	PALANPUR TALUK—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	PĀLANPUR—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
98	Loose slab in the office of the Rānī-Bāgh Housing Society. Originally from the 'Idgāh of the town.			A.H. 1060 (& chronogram) =1650 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of an 'Idgāh by Mujāhid Khān.
99	Ināyat Bāwā-ki-Masjid, Maḥalla Purānā Dāira. the facade.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter CXII) arranged in the tabular form of a talisman. In characters of about the 19th century.
100	'Ālam Bāwā-ki-Masjid, Maḥalla Nayā Dāira. Loose slab.				Do.	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter LXXII, verse 18). Do.
101	Gate of Rāj-Gaḍhī in Moṭī Bazār, opposite the State Bank of India. In the wall.			V.S. 1750= 1692-93 A.D.	Local dialect & Persian (in verse), Nāgari & Nasta'liq	Records the repairs carried out to the gate called Dhīn-(Dīn-) Dwār by Kamāl Khān. The Nāgari version has Dharma-Dwār.

102	<i>Dil-Kushā Bāgh, Mahalla Kamālpūra. To the south of the main gate.</i>			A.H. 1105 (& two chronograms)= 1693-94 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Assigns the laying out of a garden with reservoirs and streams to Kamāl Khān. Composed by Ni'matullāh.
KAIRA DISTRICT						
CAMBAY TALUK						
103	CAMBAY.—Tomb adjoining the Jāmi mosque to its south. On one of the two graves—the same grave as one mentioned in <i>A.R.Ep.</i> , 1956-57, No. 45. of Appendix D.				Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XXXVI, verses 29-42, 72-78). In characters of about the 14th century.
104	Graveyard near the Bus Stand. Headside of a grave.			A.H. 1189, Rabi'II 7= 1775 A.D., June 7	Arabic & Persian, <u>Naskh</u>	States that this is the grave of Mirzā Amin Baig who was killed on the given date in the battle with Rāghū.
105	Lāl-Mahal, in Lāl Bāgh. On the western wall of the main hall.			A.H. 1107 (chronogram & words)= 1695-96 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the date of the laying out of the garden of Mirzā Bāqir.
106	Graveyard near the Tomb of Sayyid 'Alī. Headstones of graves. No. 1.			A.H.....,29, Sunday	Arabic, <u>Naskh</u>	Badly damaged. Records the death of some one (details lost). In characters of about the 15th century.
107	No. 2					Damaged and fragmentary. Details lost. Do.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	GUJARAT—<i>Contd.</i>					
	KAIRA DISTRICT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	CAMBAY TALUK—<i>Concl.</i>					
	CAMBAY—<i>Concl.</i>					
108	No. 3			A. H. 841 (words). Jumādā II, 3 Monday= 1437 A.D., December 2	Arabic, Naskh	Damaged. States that this grave belongs to Ḥājī of the two Holy Cities Khwāja Kamālu 'd-Dīn son of late Khwāja Ibrāhīm son of late Ḥājī Amīnu'd-Dīn son of late Ḥājī 'Alī (?) al-Ḥayātī (?) al-Baṣrī who died on the given date.
109	No. 4				Do. . . .	Fragmentary Details lost. In characters of about the 15th century.
110	No. 5				Do. . . .	Do.
111	No. 6				Do. . . .	Do. In characters of about the 14th century.

112 No. 7	PETLAD TALUK			Do. . . .	Do. In characters of about the 19th century.
113	PETLĀD.—Dargāh of Arjun Shah. Headstone of the grave.			A.H. 633 (words), middle of Rajjab (i.e. 15), Mondy =1236 A.D., March 25	States that the grave belongs to Shaikhul' Mashā'ikh Arjun (son of) Damū al-Akhsi who died on the given date. Written by Abū Bakr son of Mahmūd son of Ismā'il al- Jauharī, Cf <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1915-16, p. 16, pl. XIV a.
114	Do. On the northern wall, inside.	Tughluq	Gh̄iyāthu'd-Dīn Tughluq Shāh	Persian, Naskh; Sanskrit, Nāgarī	Bilingual. Fragmentary. Records the construc- tion on the given date of a well in the town (<i>qaṣba</i>) of Petlāwadar (i.e. Petlād) in the neighbourhood of the Tomb of Shaikhul- Mashā'ikh (name lost), by Hāji Ismā'il (son of) 'Uthmān Shīrāzī, for public use. The builder also obtained a grant of 20 <i>kumbhias</i> of land from Sayyidu'l-Umarā, Badru'd-Dīn [Abū] Bakr, Amir-i-Kūh, the Muqṭa' of Petlāwadar for its upkeep so that the public, local or outsider, may derive comfort and rest therefrom. Also enjoins upon the future Amirs, Maliks and Hākims to continue the grant of the said land. <i>Ibid.</i> , 1915-16, p. 17, pl. XIV b.
115	Do. To the left of the entrance.	Khalji	'Alāu'd-Dīn	A.H. 713 (words), Ramaḍān = 1313 A.D., December 1314 A.D., January	Fragmentary (a little portion in the middle missing). States that the construction of 'this mosque' was completed on the given date during the time of the governorship (<i>naubat</i>) of the munificent Khān Alp Khān and during the administration of Sayyidu'l- Umarā Iḥṭiyāru'd-(Dīn) Balāramī (?), through the good efforts of the latter's ser- vant Badru'd-Dīn Dīnār. Cf. <i>ibid.</i> , 1917-18, p. 33, pl. XI b.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	GUJARAT—<i>Contd.</i>					
	MEHSANA DISTRICT					
	PATAN TALUK					
116	PĀṬAN.—Mosque in Maḥalla Jakshī-wāḍā. Loose slabs. No. 1			A.H. 844 (words), Rabi'II 22 = 1440 A.D., September 20	Arabic, Naskh	States that this is the grave of Ḥāji 'Isā son of Malik Mir who died on the given date. The year is prefixed by the term <u>Shuhūr-i-Sana</u> .
117	No. 2			A.H. 862 (words)= 1457-58 A.D.	Do.	States that this noble edifice (i.e. a mosque) was built by Bāyazīd son of Ḥāji son of Naṣru'llāh.
118	No. 3				Do.	Contains religious text (First Creed and a Tradition of the Prophet in praise of mosques). In characters of about the 15th century.

119	Chendyā Gate. On the left Side.	Gāikwāds (of Baroda)	Anand Rāo	A.H. 1220, Rabi' I 27 = 1805 A.D., June 25	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of the magnificent gate during the reign of the chief who is described as Srimant Anand Rāo Gāikwār Senā Khāskhail Shamshe Bahādūr and during the deputyship (i.e. governorship) of Raghū Nāth Mahipat Rāo.
120	Khokhar's Tomb near the Rail-line on the road to Sahasraling Tank. Above the southern entrance.			A.H. 1177 (& chronogram), Jumādā I 25, Friday = 1763 A.D., December 1	Arabic & Persian, Naskh	States that Jang Khān was buried at noon-time on the given date.
121	Do. Above the eastern entrance.			A.H. 1177 (& chronogram) =1763 A.D.	Persian prose & verse, Naskh	Assigns the construction of the tomb of Jang Khān Khokhar to his son 'Ināyat Khān. Also eulogises the deceased as a leading man of Paṭṭan (i.e. Pāṭan). Date that of death.
VADODARA DISTRICT						
VADODARA TALUKA						
122	VADODARĀ.—Pānch Bibī-kī-Masjid. Above the central mithrāb.		..		Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter III, verse 95 and part of verse 96). In characters of about the 15.h century.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MADHYA PRADESH					
	GUNA DISTRICT					
	MUNGAOLI TAHSIL					
123	CHANDERI.—Qaṣṣābon-ki-Masjid. On the entrance.				Persian, Naskh	Fragmentary and damaged. Refers to the construction of the mosque. In characters of about the 15th century.
	GWALIOR DISTRICT					
	GWALIOR TAHSIL					
124	GWĀLIOR.—Fort. In the eastern rampart wall, midway between Gujri-Mahal and Sās-Bahū Temple.	[Mughal]	[Humāyūn]	...	Do.	Fragmentary. The extant portion refers to the construction of a mosque.

125	Do. On the frieze of the southern entrance of the Gujri-Maḥal.	Rājas of Gwālīor	Mān Singh		Arabic & Persian, Naskh	Records a prayer invoking assistance (?) for Rājā Mān Singh son of Rāja Kalyān Mal.
126	Do. In the western wall of the southern-most quarter of the Kacheri, near the 'Ālamgīri Gate.				Arabic, Naskh	Fragmentary. Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, part of verse 255). In characters of about the 15th century.
HOSHANGABAD DISTRICT						
HOSHANGABAD TAHSIL						
127	HOSHANGĀBĀD.—Graveyard near the Railway line. Loose headstone.			A.H. 1217, Šafar 5= 1802 A.D., June 7	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the demise of Fājima Bī daughter of 'Abdu'l-Hafīz K̄hān native of Jabalpur (?), then residing at Hoṣhangābād.
VIDISHA DISTRICT						
VIDISHA TAHSIL						
128	VIDISHĀ.—Tomb on the Lohāngi Hill, Headside of the grave.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (First Creed). In characters of about the 18th century.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA					
	AMRAVATI DISTRICT					
	ACHALPUR TALUK					
129	DEŪRVĀḌĀ (Devalvādā).— mosque. On the facade.				Arabic, Nasta'liq	Modern. Reads: <i>Yā Allāh Yā Muḥammad</i> (6 Allah, 6 Muḥammad!).
	BULDANA DISTRICT					
	MALKAPUR TALUK					
130	MALKĀPUR.— Graves in the enclosure near the 'Idgāh. Hedstones of graves. No. 1.			A.H. 1108 (& chronogram) = 1696-97 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Fragmentary and damaged. Records the death of some one (name lost).
131	No. 2.			A.H. 96(?)2, Rabi' I 21, night of Wednesday = 1555 A.D., February 13	Arabic, Naskh	Damaged. Records the death of Zainab daughter of Mīrzā Abū Ṭālib al-Husainī.

MEHKAR TALUK

132	LONĀR.—Jāmi' mosque in Roshanpūrā. On the south pillar in the facade.		A.H. [10 ?] 52 (words)= 1642-43 A.D.	Persian, Nasta'liq	Badly damaged. Refers to the construction of a mosque. Only the name...Din Gauhar Khān Khafil' is legible.
133	Do. Loose slab.			Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Nād-i-'Alī</i>). In characters of about the 18th century.
134	MEHKAR.—Gate called Mu'min-Darwāza. Above the arch.			Arabic, Nasta'liq	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XLIX, verse 10). In characters of about the 19th century.
135	GREATER BOMBAY DISTRICT BOMBAY CITY TALUK BOMBAY.—Prince of Wales Museum. Slabs No. 1. Find-spot; Dābhol, Ratnagiri, District	 'Ādil Shāhī	A.H. 1062 (& words)= 1651-52 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records briefly the purport of an order stating that Malik Shaiḫh 'Alī who was the deputy (<i>Nā'ib</i>) of Aḡḡāl (Khān the minister) by the order of the king, on receiving representations from the public against the unjust practice of the governors (<i>Hukkām</i>) of Dābūl (Dābhol) whereby the entire property and personal effects including gowns and head-gears of a person, whether Hindū or Muslim, dying without a heir, were confiscated, accepted their plea and issued an order to his Chief of Guards (<i>Sarnaubat</i>), 'Abdūr-Rasūl, that by the royal order, the people were exempted (from this practice) and instructions in writing were put up. Cf. <i>Ep. Ind Mos.</i> , 1933-34, p. 10, pl. V a.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—Concl'd.					
	GREATER BOMBAY DISTRICT—Cont'd.					
	BOMBAY CITY TALUK—Concl'd.					
	BOMBAY—Concl'd.					
136	No. 2. Findspot : Nāsik.	Mughal	Aurangzeb	A.H. 1092 (& words)= 1681-82 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Assigns the construction of the city-wall (<i>jiḡār</i>) to Lodi Khān. The date is given in Indian numerals also. Ibid., 1929-30, p. 6, pl. IV b.
137	No. 3. Findspot : Dābhol.			A.H. 1059 (& words)= 1649-50 A.D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh	Records the construction and painting of a Jāmi' mosque by Pīr Ahmad, the cream of governors (<i>Hākīmān</i>). Ibid., 1933-34, p. 13, pl. VI a.
138	No. 4. Findspot : Ahmadābād, Gujarat.	Sulṭāns of Gujarat	Mahmūd Shāh I	A.H. 906 words, Jumādā I 26 (?)=1500 A.D., December 18	Arabic, Naskh	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Bā'ī Ḥatīr Sulṭānī. Ibid., 1925-26, p. 10, pl. V b.

139	No. 5. Findspot : Gālnā, District Nāsik.			A.H. 895 (words)= 1489-90 A.D.	Persian verse. Naskh	States that this inn (<i>sarā</i>) was endowed for a mosque by Dastūr Khān, the great minister of land and sea. Composed by Qudsi (?). Cf. <i>ibid.</i> , 1929-30, pp. 5-6, pl. IV a.	
140	No. 6. Findspot : Surat, Gujarat.	Mughal	Farrukh Siyar		Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Fragmentary. Refers to the construction of a fort at Sūrat by the emperor for the protection of the men of the land and the sea. <i>Ibid.</i> , 1925-26, p. 13, pl. VI b.	
141	No. 7. Findspot : Not Known.				Arabic, Naskh	Fragmentary and execution indifferent. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 18th century.	
NAGPUR DISTRICT							
NAGPUR TALUK							
142	NAGPUR.—Central Museum. Findspot : Not known.	Nizām Shāhi	Burhān Nizām Shāh II	A.H. 1.... Rajab 30	Persian, Naskh, Local dialect, Nāgarī	Bilingual. Badly Damaged. Purport not clear.	
143	Graveyard called Karbalā near the Model Mills. On a grave.				Arabic, Thulth & Naskh	Contains religious text (Shiite <i>Durūd</i> , etc.). In characters of about the 18th century.	
144	Tulsi Bagh-ki-Masjid. Above the entrance of the compound.			Ā.H. 1211 (& chronogram) =1796-97 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of the mosque.	
145	Do. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1117/03 = 1691-92 A.D.	Arabic, Nasta'liq	Contains religious text (<i>Basmala</i> , First Creed and <i>Durūd</i>).	

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	MAHARASHTRA—<i>Concl.</i>					
	NAGPUR DISTRICT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	NAGPUR TALUK—<i>Concl.</i>					
	NĀGPUR—<i>Concl.</i>					
146	Christian Cemetery, Civil Lines. On a grave. . . .			A.H. 1204, Rabi' II 28= 1790 A.D., January 15 .	Persian, Nasta'liq .	States that this is the burial place of Mu'izzu'-d-Daula I'tizāmul'-Mulk George Forster Bahādur Tahawwūr Jang, a veteran chief i.e. high official (<i>sardār</i>) of the East India Company who had come to this country i.e. side from Calcutta as an agent (<i>Vakil</i>) and who died a natural death in the given year at the age of 39.
	RAJASTHAN					
	BARMER DISTRICT					
	BALOTRA TAHSIL					
147	BĀLOTRĀ.—Jāmi' mosque. To the right of the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Basmala</i> & First Creed). In characters of about the 19th century.

BARMER TAHSIL					
148	BĀRMER. —Jāmi' mosque. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .		(1) A.H. 1298 (& chrono- gram) = 1880-81 A.D. (2) A.H. 1299 (& chrono- gram) = 1881-82 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque during the given years by Muḥammad Khān. Two fragments composed by Buddū and Nādir.
SIWANA TAHSIL					
149	SIWĀNĀ. —Jāmi' mosque. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			Arabic, Naskh	As in No. 147 above.
CHITORGARH DISTRICT					
CHITORGARH TAHSIL					
150	CHITŌRGARH. —Chhipon-Ki-Masjid. Loose slab.			Do. . .	Fragmentary. Contains religious text, (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter CXII, part of versa 1). In characters of about the 14th century.
151	Dargāh of Ghāibi Pir. In the eastern wall.			Do. . .	Do. (First Creed). In characters of about the 18th century.
152	Do. In the northern wall.			Do. . .	Do.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Contd.					
	JAIPUR DISTRICT					
	JAIPUR TAHSIL					
153	ĀMBER.—Archaeological Museum in the Fort. Loose slab.			A.H. 1075 (& chronogram), V.S. 1722, Srāvāna Su.2 =1664 A.D., July-August.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq; Local dialect, Nāgarī	Bilingual. Records the digging of a well by Hardat.
154	JAIPUR.—Rahmāniyya-Masjid. Over the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1190, Rabī' 28 = 1776 A.D., May 17	Arabic prose & Persian prose & verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Refers to the construction of the mosque.
155	Dargāh of Maulāna Diyāu'd-Dīn. On the main entrance. Lower Inscription.			A.H. 1213 (& chronogram) = 1798-99 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Contains a hemistich (meaning: The true dawn has been filled with light) which also forms the chronogram.

JAISALMER DISTRICT		JAISALMER TAHSIL	
156	JAISALMER.—Faqiron-kā-Takiya. On the second pillar, from east.	Rāwals of Jaisalmer	Amar Singh
			A.H. 1081 = 1670-71 A.D.
			Persian, Nasta'liq
			Contains two visitors' notes one mentioning Mirzā Fathī son of Mirzā 'Isā Tar Khān and another, his servant Mirān Muḥammad son of Qādi Maḥmūd resident of Naṣīrpūt.
157	Do. On the northern side of the platform.	Mughal	Aurangzeb
			Persian verse, Nasta'liq
			Fragmentary. Extant portion comprising a hemistich eulogises (the emperor 'Ālamgīr).
158	On a grav enear the above.		
			Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq
			Records the name (of the deceased) Allāh Baksh son of Mir Nūh (?). In characters of about the 18th century.
159	On the southern wall of a Chhatrī nearby.	Rāwals of Jaisalmer	Gaj Singh
			Persian, Nasta'liq
			Damaged and execution crude: Purport not clear. In characters of about the 19th century.
160	Mullāon-ki-Masjid. Above the central mihrāb.		
			Arabic, Nasta'liq
			Reads: <i>Huwā'r-Razzāq</i> (He is the Provider). Do.
161	LODROVĀ.—Ruined temple called Narā,mā-kī-Mandir. On the western wall, insi de.	Mughal	Akbar
			Persian, Nasta'liq
			Almost obliterated. Seems to be a visitor's record inscribed by Mir Muḥammad Ma'sūm Nāmī. Cf. <i>Jour.Bih.Res.Soc.</i> , Vol. XLII (1956), p. 249.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Concid.					
	JAISALMER DISTRICT — <i>Concid.</i>					
	PHALODI TAHSIL					
162	PHALODI.—Beopāriyon-ki-Masjid. Above the central <i>mīhrāb.</i>		...	A.H. 130 [77], Muḥarram 1 = 1889 A.D., August 28 .	Arabic & Urdu, Naskh & Nasta'liq .	States that the mosque was completed on the given date.
	POKARAN TAHSIL					
163	POKARAN.—Fort. On the outer face of the wall, to the right of the main gate.	Mughal	Aurangzeb	Regnal Year 24, A.H. 1092 = 1681 A.D.	Persian, Nasta'liq .	States that 'this bastion' (<i>burj</i>) of Pokaran was constructed during the time (<i>'amal</i>) of Imām Qulī, the Qal'adār.

JALORE DISTRICT						
JALORE TAHSIL						
164	JĀLORE. —Graves in an enclosure near the Bāoliwāli-Masjid. On the fifth grave in the first row.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, verses 255-56). In characters of about the 15th century.
165	On the second grave, second row.			Do.	Fragmentary. Do.	
JODHPUR DISTRICT						
JODHPUR TAHSIL						
166	JODHPUR. —Qāzi Pāde-kī-Masjid, Mahalla Moti Chauk. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .		A.H. 1230, Rajab 10= 1815 A.D., June 18	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that the mosque was built by Chānd Shāh Chishtī, through the blessings of Shāh Ḥaḍrat Mu'īnu'd-Dīn, the (spiritual) king of India, through whose spiritual benefit, people attain the status of a saint.	
167	Mosque attached to the Ishāqia High School, in Mahalla Kharādiyān. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .			Arabic verse, Naskh	Contains two verses from the famous Qaṣīda-i-Burda in praise of Prophet Muḥammad.	

D—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Contd.					
	NAGAUR DISTRICT					
	JAEI TAHSIL					
168	BARI KHATTU. —Dargāh of Maghribi Shāh. On the ceiling.				Arabic, Naskh in Tughra .	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, part of verse 137). In characters of about the 18th century.
169	Qanāṭī-Masjid, near the Dargāh of Kharīki Pir. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .	Mughal	Aurangzeb	A. H. 1083, Dhu'l-Qa'da 26 = 1673 A. D., March 5	Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq	States that the mosque was built by Suljān son of Barkhū (?) Gardizi resident of the town (qaṣba) of Khattū. Written by Najmud-Dīn son of Qāḍī 'Abdu'r-Rahīm (resident) of the <i>pargana</i> Khattū.
170	Qanāṭī-Masjid, near the tank called Dhārāgīr-kā-Tālab. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .	Do.	Do.	A. H. 1083, Muharram 4 = 1672 A. D., April 22	Persian, Nasta'liq	States that the mosque was constructed at the instance of Chānd Shāh and 'Alāwal Nayāzi son(s) of Bāitū <i>aliās</i> Mahmud. Written by Najmud-Dīn Qāḍī, resident of Pirān Khattū.

NAGAUR TAHSIL								
171	NĀGAUR.—Shamsī Jāmi' mosque. On the facade.				Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (Attributes of God). In characters of about the 15th century.		
172	Fort. In the southern wall facing the Dargāh of Aḥmad 'Alī Bābā.				Arabic, Thulth	Fragmentary. Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XIX, part of verse 96). In characters of about the 15th century.		
173	Fort. Another slab in the wall.		..		Do. . . .	Do. Do. Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XLVIII, part of verse 2). In characters of about the 13th century.		
174	Do. Loose sarcophagus found in the debris of the said wall				Do. . . .	Do. In continuation of No. 172 above.		
175	Do. Another loose sarcophagus, same place.				Arabic, Naskh	Do. Do. In characters of about the 13th century.		
176	Do. Loose slab, same place.				Do. . . .	Do. Do. In characters of about the 14th century.		
177	Do. Loose sarcophagus, same place.				Do. . . .	As in No. 175 above. Do.		
178	Do. Another loose sarcophagus, same place.				Arabic, Thulth	Do. In continuation of No. 173 above.		
179	Do.				Arabic, Naskh	Do. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 14th century.		

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	NĀGAUR DISTRICT—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	NAGAUR TAHSIL—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	NĀGAUR—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
180	Fort. Another loose sarcophagus, same place.				Arabic, Naskh	As in No. 175 above.
181	Sarcophagus lying in the compound of the shop of Rafiq Pahelwān Nālband on the Zilā Kacheri road. Findspot: From the debris of the fort-wall.				Do.	Fragmentary. Do. (First Creed). In characters of about the 13th century.
182	Mosque in Maḥalla Ḥāfiẓān Loose slab.			A.H. 1298 (& chronogram) = 1880-81 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque by 'Abdu'l-Ḥaḡ.
183	Khwaja Khidr-ki-Masjid, Maḥalla Mochiyān. on the central miḥrāb.	...		A.H. 1099 = 1687-88 A.D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh	States that the repairs to the mosque were carried out by Muḡtafā son of Bikhā.

184	Mosque near the Gāndhi Market. On the facade.			A. H. 1298, Sha'bān 7, Friday = 1852 A.D., May 27	Arabic Prose & Persian verse & prose, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XXXIII, part of verse 16, Chapter XXXVIII, part of verse 188 and Chapter III, part of verse 183) and two poetical verses on the transitoriness of the world, one being that of Nāmi.
185	Do. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .				Arabic, Thulth	Contains religious text (First Creed). In characters of about the 17th century.
186	Do. Loose slab.				Do.	Do. In characters of about the 15th century.
187	Naddāfon-ki-Majid. Over the central <i>mihrāb</i> .	Mughal	Aurangzeb	Regnal year 3[1], A.H. 1099, Rabi'II 5 = 1688 A.D., January 29	Persian, Nasta'liq	States that this pleasant mosque was built under the supervision of Khān-Jahān (?), 'Ināyat, Sher 'Alī, Bahādur and Khwāja... Khān.
188	Sarcophagus, near Sāt-Hāfiz, outside the northern city-wall.			A. H. 789, Rabi'II 9, Friday = 1396 A.D., January 21	Arabic, Naskh	States that the grave belongs to the great, the most favourite and the respected Isfahsālār, the fortunate martyr, the magnificent, Asadu d-Dīn son of the late Isfahsālār Ikhtiyāru d-Dīn Buddhū son of Ja [far] al-Afghān al-Bakkārī the governor (<i>Wāfi</i>) of the town (<i>qaybā</i>) of Sodhat (or Sodhit), who died on the given date.
189	Dargāh of Pir Zahiru'd-Dīn, in Mahalla Lohārpūrā. Sides of a grave in the compound.				Arabic, Thulth	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter III, verse 18). In characters of about the 15th century.
190	PABATSAR TAHSIL MAKRĀNĀ. - Bāzār-ki-Masjid. Above the entrance.			A. H. 1284 = 1867-68 A. D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Records the reconstruction of the gate.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—Contd.					
	NAGOUR DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	PARBATSAR TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
	MAKRĀNĀ—Concl'd.					
191	Teliyon-ki-Masjid. Loose slab	Mughal	Shāh Jahān	A.H. 1053, Rabi'II= 1643 A.D., June-July	Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Assigns the construction of the mosque to Shaikh Chānd son of Shāh Muḥammad.
192	Qanāti-Masjid in the local graveyard. Above the central mihrāb.	Do.	Muḥammad Shāh	Regnal Year 15(A.H. 1145), Ramaḍān 4= 1733 A.D., February 18	Do.	States that this Bar-Sāhibi mosque (i.e. the mosque of Bar-Sāhib) was constructed by Nūr Muḥammad and Ḥasan, sons of Sher Muḥammad.
193	Another Qanāti-Masjid, same place, Above the central mihrāb.			A.H. , Ramaḍān 4, Thursday	Arabic & Persian, Naskh	States that the mosque was built in the name of Amānu'llāh. In characters of about the 19th century.

194 Do.				A.H....., Shawwal 29	Do. . .	Records the construction of the mosque in the name of Madāri son of Najū. Do.
PALI DISTRICT						
PALI TAHSIL						
195	PĀLI.—Jāmi' mosque. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1261= 1845 A.D.	Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (First Creed).
196	Chhipon-ki-Masjid. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1284= 1867-68 A.D.	Do. . .	Do. (First Creed and names of the first four caliphs).
197	Chhaq̄dhon-ki-Masjid. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1293= 1876-77 A.D.	Arabic, Nasta'liq	Do. (First Creed).
198	Sipāhiyon-ki-Masjid. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .			A.H. 1121 (Probably 1211, so written) = 1799-97 A.D.	Arabic, Naskh	Do.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Concl.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	RAJASTHAN—<i>Concl.</i>					
	PALI DISTRICT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	PALI TAHSIL—<i>Concl.</i>					
	PĀLI—<i>Concl.</i>					
199	Bohron-ki-Masjid. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .				Arabic, prose & verse, Naskh	Contains religious text (First Shiite Creed and a verse in praise of 'Alī the fourth Caliph and his sword <i>Dhu'l-Faqār</i>). In characters of about the 18th century,
	SOJAT TAHSIL					
200	SOJAT.—Jāmi' mosque. Above the central <i>mīhrāb</i> .	Mughal	Aurangzeb	A.H. 1092 (chronogram) = 1681-12 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that the mosque with a reservoir (<i>ḥauḍ</i>) and a fountain (<i>fawwāra</i>) in its courtyard was constructed by Sardār (Kḥān?).
201	Do. On the northern wall.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.

UTTAR PRADESH

AGRA DISTRICT

AGRA TAHSIL

202	AGRA.—Dargāh of Ahmad <u>Shāh</u> Bukhārī to the north-east of the Tāj-Mahal. Headstone of a grave in the compound.		A.H. 1213 (& chronogram) 1798-99 A.D.	Do. . . .	Records the death of Mughal Baig. Composed by Mu'azzam.
203	Mosque in Maḥalla <u>Shāhi</u> Madrasa. On the central <i>mihrāb</i> . Upper panel.		A.H. 1045 = 1635-36 A.D.,	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter LXII, verses 9-11). Written by 'Abdu'l-Ḥaqq entitled Amānat <u>Khān</u> on the given date.
204	Do. Medallion to the right and to the left of the above.			Arabic, <u>Naskh</u>	Reads: <i>Allāh</i> . In characters of about the 17th century.
205	Do. Lower panel.		A.H. 1046 = 1636-37 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XLVIII, verses 28-29). Written by 'Abdu'l-Ḥaqq entitled Amānat <u>Khān</u> .
206	Do. On the northern <i>mihrāb</i> .		Do. . . .	Do. . . .	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter LX, verses 18-19 and 32). In the same hand as above.
207	To the right and left of the above.			Arabic, <u>Naskh</u>	As in No. 204 above.
208	Do. On the southern <i>mihrāb</i> .			Arabic, <u>Thulth</u> & <u>Naskh</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter XXIV, verse 35). Written by Amānat <u>Khān</u> a <u>sh-Shirāzi</u> .

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—Contd.					
	AGRA DISTRICT—Contd.					
	AGRA TAHSIL—Contd.					
	AGRA—Contd.					
209	To the right and left of the above.				Arabic, Naskh	As in No. 204 above.
210	Graves on a platform in front of the above mosque. No. 1. Top.			A.H. 1223 (& chronogram) 1808-09 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Sayyid Mir, a religious leader.
211	No. 2. Headstone.			A.H.... (& chronogram)	Do.	Badly damaged. Records the death of Mirzā Aḥmadi of the Qādiri order. Portions of the chronogrammatic phrase and figures damaged or lost. In characters of about the 18th century.
212	Dargah of <u>Shah Rafi'ud-Din Muḥaddith</u> in <u>Maḥalla Belanganj</u> . Loose slab.				Arabic <u>Thulth</u>	Damaged and fragmentary. Purport not clear. In characters of about the 17th century.

213	Headstone of a grave on a platform in front of the above.			A.H. 1[22] (& chronogram) = 1806-07 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Badly damaged. Records the demise of one Kalb-i-'Alī.
214	Grave of <u>Shāikh Nāẓir Shāh</u> . On the Drammond Road, near the Agra College. Headstone.			A.H. 1057 (& words & chronogram), = Jumādā II 13, = 1647 A.D., July 6	Do.	Records the death of <u>Shāikh Nāẓir Shāh</u> , a saintly person. Published, <i>Pro Seminar on Medieval Inscriptions</i> , Aligarh, 1970 (Aligarh, 1974), p. 123.
215	Christian Cemetery near the Civil Court. Tomb of Col. Jān William Hessing. Headstone.			1803 A.D., July 21 (& chronogram)	Do.	Records the death of Karnil (Colonel) Jān William Hessing, a Hollandiz (i.e. Hollander) by birth, who had made name in India. Published, <i>Pro. As. Soc. Ben.</i> , 1874, p. 170
216	Tomb of Mīr 'Abdu'līlāh locally called Dargāh of Bābā Sitāra-i-Hind in Maḥalla Nagla Jawāhar near Qandahāri. Panels running along the walls, inside.			A.H. 1035 (& 3 chronograms) = 1625-26 A.D.	Do.	Records the death of Mīr 'Abdu'līlāh who was a great saint (Shāikh and Quṣb of the time), a follower of the <u>Chishtī</u> order and a man of versatile talents, in the given year. Further states that the construction of his tomb also took place in the same year. Written by Muḥammad Ṣāliḥ al-Husainī and composed also by (him under the poetical name) <u>Kaṣṣfī</u> . Published, <i>ibid.</i> , p. 163.
217	Dargāh of Nabī Ṣāhib, in Sarāi Nabī Khān. On the northern wall of the enclosure.			A.H. 1044 = 1634-35 A.D.	Do.	States that the tablet contains foot-print of the Prophet of Allāh (i.e. Prophet Muḥammad) which was brought here by <u>Khidmat Khān</u> . Cf. <i>ibid.</i> , p. 162.
218	Mosque in the enclosure of the above. On the facade.			A.H. 1037 (& chronogram) = 1627-28 A.D.	Persian verse, <u>Thulth</u>	Damaged. States that the mosque was built by <u>Khidmat Khān</u> . Published, <i>ibid.</i> , p. 161.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—Contd.					
	AGRA DISTRICT—Contd.					
	AGRA TAHSIL—Contd.					
	AGRA—Contd.					
219	Inscribed graves in the graveyard in Itimādpur. No. 1			A.H. 947, Jumādā II = 1535 A.D., November- December	Arabic & Persian, Naskh, Thulth & Nasta'liq .	States that the newly born (son of?) Usta[d] Jūjak died on the given date.
220	No. 2.			A.D. 946 = 1539-40 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq .	Records the death of Shāh Muḥammad Sulḥān son of Maḥmūd.
221	No. 3.			A.H. 941 (chronogram) = 1534-35 A.D. .	Do.	Records the death of one 'Arab who died young.

222	No. 4			A.H. 945 (words) = 1538-39 A.D.	Arabic & Persian, Naskh & Nasta'liq	States that Sa'd Baiqi daughter of Ustād Ghulām 'Alī, the architect (<i>Mi'mār</i>) died on the given date.
ALIGARH DISTRICT						
ALIGARH TAHSIL						
223	ALIGARH.—Sir Sayyid Hall of the Muslim University, Aligarh. On the southern wall. Originally from the Koil Minaret.	Mamlūk	Nāṣirud-Dīn Maḥmūd	A.H. 652 (words), Rajab 10 = 1254 A.D., August 26	Arabic, Thulth	States that this edifice was constructed by the great and the learned noble Qutluḡ Khān Bahāu'-l-Haq wa d-Dīn Malik-i-Mulūkī sh-Sharq wa ṣ-Ṣīn Balban a'sh-Shamsi on the given date. Published, <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1913-14, plate XI a, p. 23.
BIJNOR DISTRICT						
BIJNOR TAHSIL						
224	BIJNOR.—Mosque called Paṭhā-nonwālī-Masjid, behind the Tahsil office. Above the central entrance.			A.H. 1181 (& words) = 1767-68 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that the mosque ordered to be built by Najīb Khān Bahādur was completed on the given date, under the supervision of Ghairat Khān.
225	CHĀNDPUR.—Mosque called Unche-Wālī-Masjid in Mahalla Qāzizādagān. In the southern mihrāb.			A.H. 968 (& chronogram) = 1560-61 A.D.	Do.	Damaged. States that this mosque was built by Hājī Muḥammad Shāh. Composed by Shārif (?).
226	JAHĀNĀBĀD (Ganj).—Tomb called Naulakhā. Along the wall, under the roof.			A.H. 1057 (& chronogram) = 1647-48 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of the tomb of a Nawwāb, a high-born Sayyid (name not specified). Composed by Waṣlī (?).

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—Contd.					
	BIJNOR DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	BIJNOR TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
227	MANDĀWAR. —Jāmi' mosque. Above the central <i>mihrāb</i> .				Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter III, verses 15-17 and part of verse 18). In characters of about the 16th century.
228	Below the above.				Do. . . .	Do. (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter I, and the First Creed). Do.
229	TUNDPŪRĀ. —On a well on the Bijnor-Kiratpur Road.			A.H. 1167 (& chronogram) = 1753-54 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that the well was excavated and built by Naurūz Khān and Muḥammad Khān for public use for their memory.
	ETAH DISTRICT					
	ALIGANG TAHSIL					
230	ALIGANJ. —Loose slab in possession of Shri Maqṣūd'Alī Khān, Maḥalla Kūcha Dā'imganj. Originally from the Fort.			A.H. 1143 (& chronogram) = 1730-31 A.D.	Do. . . .	States that Ya'qūt Khān founded 'Aliganj. Written by Muḥammad (son of?) Ādam, Muḥammad Khānī mason or architect (<i>Mi'nār</i>).

231	Mosque in the same Mahalla. Loose slab.		A.H. 1235 (& chronogram) = 1819-20 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of a mosque in 'Aliganj by Nūr Khān.
JALEGAR TAHISIL					
232	JALEGAR.—Dargāh of Ḥaḡrat Mirān Sayyid Ibrāhīm. To the right of the door of the main Tomb.		A.H. 954. Muharram 14 = 1547 A.D., March 6	Persian, Naskh	States that the dome (<i>gumbad</i>) of the (<i>rauḍa</i>) tomb of His Holiness Ḥaḡrat Mirān Sayyid Ibrāhīm was constructed during the gover- norship (<i>'amal</i>) of Masnad-i-'Alī Rūstam Khān at the instance of Miḡān Yahyā by Bilak (?) Rūstam Khān, the official-in-charge (<i>Shiqdār</i>) of the <i>paigāna</i> of Jalesar.
233	Headstone of a grave on the platform to the left of the above tomb.		A.H. 1192 (& chronogram), Shawwāl 14, Wednesday= 1778 A.D., November 5	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that 'Iwāḍ Baig Khān, a follower of 'Alī and a devout believer and son of Kar- balā'i, who was born at Diwān Tappa died on the given date.
234	Headstone of a grave in a small enclosure outside the same tomb.		A.H. 1199 (words) Rabi' I... 1785 A.D., January- February	Arabic & Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Riḡā Qulī Khān son of Riḡā Qulī Khān of Karāmālī tribe who was a resident of Mashhad (in Irān) adjacent to (<i>mutawālī</i>) the Tomb of Imām Mūsā Kāzīm.
235	Two graves on the platform in front of the main gate of the said Dargāh. Headstones. No. 1.		A.H. 1192 (& chronogram), Ṣafar 20, Friday= 1778 A.D., March 20	Arabic & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Damaged. Records the death of Maḡdī Baig Khān, described as a valiant person.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—Contd.					
	ETAH DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	JALESAR TAHSIL—Concl'd.					
	JALESAR—Concl'd.					
236	No. 2			A.H. 1194, Rabi'II 16 1710 A.D., April 21	Persian, Nasta'liq	States that Muḥammad Husain Baig son of Naṣir Baig, a resident of Shīrāz (in Irān) died on the given date.
237	Graves on another platform near the said gate. Headstones. No. 1.			A.H. 1273 (& chronogram), Shawwāi 3, Saturday— 1157 A.D., May, 27 (Wednesday)	Arabic prose, & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq	Records the death of Sundar.
238	No. 2	Mughal	Shāh 'Ālam II	A.H. 1198, Safar 2, Saturday= 1713 A.D., December 27	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the death of Mirzā 'Ashūr Baig son of Mirzā 'Azīz Baig Ghaznavī, a resident of village (<i>dih</i>) Khudābād.

239	Dargāh of Pir Zari Shāh. Above the entrance.		A.H. 1210 (& chronogram) (inscribed as 1012) = 1795-96 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	States that Shāmsir Khān provided a new grave-cover (?) of cloth (<i>qamāsh</i>) at the Dargāh of Pir Zari Zarbaksh and Ahmad 'Alī Khān renovated its edifice.
240	Mosque in Mahalla Bālā-Qila. On the façade.		A.H. 1102 (& chronogram) = 1690-91 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of a mosque by Mihr Dād the pious (<i>gālib</i>). Composed (?) by Ghulām Muḥammad.
241	Jāmi mosque. Above the central mihrāb.		A.H. 1138 (& chronogram) = 1725-26 A.D.	Do.	States that the old mosque of Makhdūm Sanā was rebuilt by Shihābu'd-Dīn. Composed by Minā.
242	Mosque in Mahalla Hatondā. On the façade.		A.H. 1268 (words) = 1851-52 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of the mosque by Husain Khān.
243	Graveyard in Mahalla Hateliyān. Loose slab.		A.H. 1196. Jumādā II 24 Thursday = 1712 A.D., June 6	Do.	States that Āqā 'Alī of Sen Shāhi (?) tribe (<i>qum</i>) and a champion of his time died on the given date.
244	Another loose slab, same place.		A.H. 1203 = 1788-89 A.D.	Urdū, Nasta'liq	Records the death of 'Abdu'r-Rahmān Khān alias Rahīm Khān a Pension-dār (i.e. Pensioner).

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—Contd.					
	ETAH DISTRICT—Concl'd.					
	KASGANJ TAHSIL					
245	KĀSGANJ.—Jāmi' mosque. On the facade.			A.H. 1150 (chronogram) =1737-38 A.D. . .	Persian, verse, Nasta'liq .	Records the construction of a mosque in Yāqūganj by Yāqūt K̄hān.
246	Sarā'i-ki-Masjid. On the facade.			A.H. 1154= 1741-43 A.D.	Do. . .	Damaged. States that Yāqūt K̄hān constructed this mosque of the Sarāi of the town (<i>qāḡha</i>) Yāqūganj and endowed three bighas of land for the <i>ḥijā'u</i> (?) (watershed). Scribe's name ending in Baig illegible.
	MATHURA DISTRICT					
	MATHURA TAHSIL					
247	GOKUL.—On a grave near the Tomb of Rās K̄hān.			A.H. 1069, Shā'bān 6= 1659 A.D., April 19	Persian, Nasta'liq .	Records the death of Mirān Sayyid Shāh Tāj,

248	MATHURĀ.—Jāmi' mosque. Slab above the main gate. . . .		A.H. 1301 (& chronogram) = 1883-84 A.D.	Persian verse & prose. Nasta'liq .	States that the repairs were carried out to the mosque by Hājī Kunwar Muḥammad Hidāyat 'Alī Khān who also wrote the text.
249	Do. To the left of the main gate. . . .	[Mughal]	A.H. 1071 = 1660-61 A.D.	Persian verse. Nasta'liq .	This is the second half of the inscription, the tablet bearing the first half and fixed to the right of the gate being inlaid. States that the builder of the mosque is 'Abdu'n-Nabi Khān. Full text published in <i>Proc.As.Soc. Beng.</i> , 1873, p. 12.
MEERUT DISTRICT					
GHAZIABAD TAHSIL					
250	GHĀZIĀBĀD.—Dargāh of Ghāzu'd-Dīn Khān's mother. On the grave. . . .				Badly scrapped off. Purport not clear.
251	Graveyard in Maḥalla Delhi Gate. Headstone of a grave near the Ashok Electroplating Company. . . .		AD., July 8	Arabic & Persian, Nasta'liq .	Badly damaged. Seems to record the death of Maṅṣūr 'Alī, son of Sardār 'Alī, the resident of Shīrāz in Irān. Year illegible. In recent characters.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	UTTAR PRADESH—<i>Concl'd.</i>					
	SAHARANPUR DISTRICT					
	RÖORKI TAHSIL					
252	JAUŘĀSI.—Jāmi' mosque. On the facade, towards north.	Mughal	Aurangzeb	Regnal year 18. A.H. 1086 = 1675 A.D., March-November	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of the mosque by the orders of emperor under the supervision of 'Ināyat, a servant of the court.
253	Do. Towards south.			A.H. 1086 (& chronogram) 1675-76 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Refers to the construction of the mosque.
254	MANGLAUR.—Mosque of Shāh Wilāyat. On the facade, to the south of the bntrance.	Mamlūk	Balban	A.H. 683 (words). Rajab 10 = 1284 A.D., September 22	Arabic, Naskh	Fragmentary. States that during the governorship of Matlik-i-Mulūkīsh-Sharq wa 'l-Shin (name etc. lost), the order for the construction of this edifice was given by the Amīr, the Ispahsālār (name etc. lost) on the given date; Published, <i>Ep.In.Mos.</i> , 1913-14, p. 30, pl. XI.

255	PIRĀN KALYAR. —Tomb in a field near the Dargāh of Aḥmad Ṣābir.			A.H. 1011 (words), Dhu'l-Hijja 29, Sunday = 1603 A.D., May 30 which is Monday	Persian, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of the dome (<i>gumhad</i> i.e. tomb?) of Rāi Sher Khānī son of Aḥmad under the supervision of Baṣhīr and under the artianship (<i>ustādagi</i>) of Bhajjū Durogar (lit, Carpenter), Sādāt.
256	SAHARANPUR TAHSIL SAHĀRANPUR. —Tombstone lying near the Gāndhi Park.			A.H. 916 (words) = 1510-11 A.D.	Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Nād-i-'Alif</i>). In characters of about the 16th century.
257	WEST BENGAL BIRBHUM DISTRICT SURI SUB-DIVISION SĀKULIPUR. —Jāmi mosque. In the projection of the western wall near the southern doorway leading to the tank.	Sulṭāns of Bengal	Husain Shāh	A.H. 916 (words) = 1510-11 A.D.	Arabic, Thulth	Assigns the construction of a tank (<i>siqāya</i>) to the king, the name of whose father Sayyid Aṣṭraf al-Husainī is also given.
258	SAUGRĀM. —Baḡi-Masjid. Above the central doorway.	Mughal	Aurangzeb	Regnal Year 46 (A.H. 1113-14) = 1702-03 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Damaged. Records the construction of the mosque by Sayyid Pahāī son of Sayyid Ḥasan, son of Sayyid Shāh Sayyid Ḥusainī, a descendant of Shāh Sayyid Rahmān. Also mentions his three brothers, Faṭḥ Muḥammad, Sharafu'd-Dīn and Muḥammad Murād. Cf. <i>Jour.As.Soc.Ben.</i> , Vol. XVIII, New Series (1924), p. 517.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	WEST BENGAL—<i>Contd.</i>					
	BIRBHUM DISTRICT—<i>Concl.</i>					
	SURI SUB-DIVISION—<i>Concl.</i>					
	SAUGRĀM—<i>Concl.</i>					
259	Do. Above the northern doorway.	Mughal	Aurangzee	Regnal year 46 (A.H. 1113-14) =1702-03 A.D.	Arabic, Nasta'liq	Contains religious text (First Creed)
260	Do. Above the southern doorway.				Do.	Do. (<i>Nāḍ-i-'Alī</i>). In characters of about the 18th century.
	BURDWAN DISTRICT					
	BURDWAN SUB-DIVISION					
261	SUĀTĀ.—Tomb of Sayyid Shāh Shāhid Maḥmūd Bahmani. In the northern wall.	Sulḡāns of Bengal	Ḥusain Shāh	A.H. 908 (words)= 1502-03 A.D.	Arabic, Naskh	Records the construction of the Jāmi' mosque (?) by the king. Written by Naṣru d-Dīn (?).

262	Loose slab, same place.	Do.	Do.	A.H. 902 (?) (words)= 1496-97 A.D.	Do.	Invokes prayers for the long life of the king, a number of whose high titles including that of the conqueror of Kāmru and Kāmtā is given. Written by Qāḍī Mināzi (?).
263	Another loose slab, same place.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> Chapter III, verses 25-26) and the name and titles of the king. Written by Qāḍī Mināzi (?).
KATWA SUB-DIVISION						
264	RĀIKHĀ.—Tālābwāli-Masjid. Loose slab.	Do.	Do.		Do.	Fragmentary and damaged. The extant portion refers to the reign of the king. Also contains a number of high titles of the king including that of 'Conqueror of Kāmru and Kāmtā'.
CALCUTTA DISTRICT						
CALCUTTA CITY SUB-DIVISION						
265	CALCUTTA.—Slab in the Indian Museum. Findspot: Kālnā, Burdwān District.	Mughal	Aurangzeb	A.H. 1080 (words)= 1669-70 A.D.	Do.	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Daulat Khān son of Ḥusain Khān. Gives Nāṣiru'd-Dunyā wa'd-Dīn as the title of the emperor. Date that of writing. Cf. <i>Ep. Ind. Mos.</i> , 1933-34, p. 2, pl. I a.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	WEST BENGAL—Contd.					
	HOOGLY DISTRICT					
	ARAMBAGH SUB-DIVISION					
266	ĀRĀMBĀGH.—Mosque in Maḥalla Qāḥpāṭā. On the facade.			A.H. 1221 (& chronogram)= 1806-07 A.D.	Persian verse. Nasta'liq	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Rahmatullāh son of the late Shaikh Jāru'llāh. Composed by Aslam.
267	GARH. MANDĀRAN.—Tomb of Shāh Ismā'il Ghāzī called Chhoṭā Āstāna. To the right of the southern entrance.	Sulṭāns of Bengal	Husain Shāh	A.H. 904 (words). (Ramaḍān)= 1499 A.D., April-May	Arabic, Naskh	Records the construction of a gate by Shāh-zāda Mubārak. Cf. Jour. As. Soc. Ben., Vol. XIII, New Series (1917), p. 134.
268	NIRBHAYPUR.—Mosque. On the façade.			A.H. 1234 (words)= 1818-19 A.D.	Persian verse. Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque by Mīr 'Alī.

269	SANBANDHI (Dinānāth). — Ruined Gate outside the village. On the right and left jambs.			A.H. 1143 (chronogram) = 1730-31 A.D.	Do.	Records the construction of a Sarāi (caravan-sarai) for public use by Nawwāb Mu'taman-ul-Malk. Date that of completion. Published. <i>Misc. Beng.</i> , Vol. IV, pp. 300-01.
CHANDRANAGAR SUB-DIVISION						
270	MOLLĀ SIMLĀ —Tomb of Ḥaḍrat Muḥammad Kabir also called Shāh Anwar Quli Ḥalabi (i.e. of Aleppo). Over the southern entrance.			A.H. 877 (words)= 1472-73 A.D.	Arabic, Bahār	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Khān-i-A'ẓam Ulugh Mukhlis Khān. Ibid., p. 39.
MIDNAPUR DISTRICT						
CONTAI SUB-DIVISION						
271	HIJLI. —Mosque. Above the central doorway.	Mughal	Shāh Jahān	(1) A.H. 1052 1642-43 A.D. (2) A.H. 1055 (& chronogram)= 1645-46 A.D.	Arabic prose & Persian verse. Naskh & Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque by Tāj Khān. Second date that of completion.
272	Loose slab on a platform in front of the above mosque.			A.H. 943 (words)= 1536-37 A.D.	Arabic & Bengālī, Naskh	Fragmentary. Records the construction of a mosque by Ikhtiyār Khān son of Munawwar Khān. Contains a few stray words in Banglā (?) characters.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	WEST BENGAL—Contd.					
	MURSHIDABAD DISTRICT					
	MURSHIDABAD SUB-DIVISION					
273	JANGIPUR.—Platform with graves, called Nimtalla in Maḥalla Raghunāthganj. Into the face side of the platform.	Sulṭāns of Bengal.	Maḥmūd Shāh I	A.H. 847 (words), Ramaḡān 2 = 1443 A.D., December 24	Arabic, Naskh	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Khān-i-Mu'azzam Ulugh Sarfarāz Khān, the Royal Wardrobe-keeper outside the Palace (<i>Jāmdār-i-ghair-i-Maḡallī</i>). Ibid., p. 51.
274	To the left of the above.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do.	Do. Further calls the builder Khāqān-i-Mu'azzam and Minister of the Chancery in the East (<i>Wazīr-i-Dīwān dar Sharq</i>). Cf. <i>ibid.</i> , p. 50.
275	Jāmi' Mosque in Maḥalla Balighaḡḡa. Above the window in the southern wall.	Do.	[Ḥusain Shāh]	A.H. 921 (words), Rabi' I = 1515 A.D., April-May	Do.	Fragmentary. Details lost except the date and benedictory phrases used for the king. Published, <i>Insc. Beng.</i> , Vol. IV, p. 194.

276	Above the central doorway of the same mosque.		A.H. 1155 (chronogram) = 1742-43 A.D.	Arabic & Persian verse, Naskh & Nasta'liq .	Records the construction of a mosque by Sayyid Qāsim. <i>Ibid.</i> , p. 301.
277	Waqtā-Masjid, Mahalla Raghu-nāthganj. Above the central doorway.		A.H. 1261 (& chronogram) = 1845 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq .	States that when Šādīr 'Alī started the construction of the mosque, he died and it was completed by Muni'rū'n-Nisā (his wife ?).
278	JĪĀGUNJ.—House of late Shri Birendra Singh Bahādūr, in Mahalla Mahāraj Bahādūr. Loose slabs. No. 1.		A.H. 1145 (& chronogram) = 1732-33 A.D.	Do. . .	Refers probably to the death of some one.
279	No. 2		A.H. 1243 (& chronogram) (written as 4312) = 1827-28 A.D.	Do. . .	Records the death of 'Idī Begam.
280	No. 3		A.H. 1266 (& chronogram) = 1849-50 A.D.	Do. . .	Records the death of Šādīq 'Alī Khān Bahādūr, a descendant of Haidār (i.e. the fourth caliph 'Alī). Composed by Safīr.
281	No. 4		A.H. 1273 (& chronogram), Shawwāl 4, night of Friday = 1857 A.D., May 28 .	Do. . .	Records the death of Rajab 'Alī son of Shāh Imāmu'd-Dīn, of the Qādīri order (K̄hānwādā) who died unmarried at the age of 19.

D.—ARABIC AND PERSIAN INSCRIPTIONS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	WEST BENGAL— <i>Contd.</i>					
	MURSHIDABAD DISTRICT — <i>Contd.</i>					
	MURSHIDABAD SUB-DIVISION — <i>Contd.</i>					
	JIĀGUNJ— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
282	No. 5				Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter LXI, part of verse 13). In characters of about the 17th century.
283	MURSHIDĀBĀD.—Pirū Qāsāi-ki-Masjid, in Maḥalla Bāns-golā. Above the main gate.				Arabic, <u>Naskh</u>	Do. (First Creed, names of the Prophets and four Caliphs). Written by Sayyid Riḡā. In characters of about the 18th century.
284	On the façade of the same mosque.			A.H. 117(8?)3 (& chrono-gram)= 1769-70 A.D.	Persian verse, <u>Nasta'liq</u>	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Phirū, the Mihtar.
285	On the central <i>miḥrāb</i> , same mosque.				Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Fragmentary and damaged. Contains part of a prayer for repulsion of pestilence. In characters of about the 18th century.

286	Mosque in <u>Mahalla Qutbpur</u> . On the facade.			Bāngla San 1257 (& chronogram), A.H. 1267 (& chronogram) = 1850-51 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque by Dārāb'Ali Khān. Composed by Wilāyat.
287	Mosque near the old Jail. To the right of the central doorway.				Arabic, Nasta'liq	Contains religious text (First Creed). In characters of about the 18th century.
288	To the left of the same doorway.			A.H. 1180(?) = 1766-67 A.D.	Arabic, <u>Thulth</u>	Do. (<i>Durūd</i>).
289	Below No. 288.				Arabic, Nasta'liq	Contains a prayer for repulsion of pestilence. In characters of about the 18th century.
290	Mosque in <u>Gulāb Bagh</u> . On the facade.			A.H. 1131 (& chronogram) = 1718-19 A.D.	Persian verse, Nasta'liq	Records the construction of a mosque near the grave of Muḥammad Zāmān Baig.
291	Mosque on the road to <u>Gulāb Bagh</u> . On the facade.			A.H. 1237 (& chronogram) = 1821-22 A.D.	Do.	Assigns the construction of a mosque to Farḥatū 'ilāh Khān. Composed by Muḡṭṭar.
292	On a gun lying in <u>Mahalla Top Khānā</u> .	Mughal	Shāh Jahān	Regnal Year 11, A.H. 1047 (& chronogram) = 1637-38 A.D.	Do.	Partly obliterated. Assigns the manufacture of the gun called <u>Jahān-Kushā</u> (lit. World-conquering) to the period of the governorship of Bengāl of Islām Khān. for Complete text see, <i>Jour. As. Soc. Beng.</i> , Vol. XVI (1847), p. 592.

D.—INSCRIPTIONS OF PRE-1945-46 COLLECTIONS—*Concl'd.*

Sl. No.	Place of Find or Deposit	Dynasty	King	Date	Language and Alphabet	Remarks
	WEST BENGAL— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	MURSHIDABAD DISTRICT — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	MURSHIDABAD SUB-DIVISION — <i>Concl'd.</i>					
	MURSHIDĀBĀD— <i>Concl'd.</i>					
293	Motijhi-ki-Masjid. On the facade.			A.H. 1163 (& chronogram)= 1749-50 A.D.	Do. . . .	Refers to the (construction) of a mosque.
294	Mosque in Mahalla Banamati-pūr. On the facade.			A.H. 1167 (& chronogram)= 1753-54 A.D.	Do. . . .	Assigns the construction of a mosque to 'Abdu'r-Rahmān who also composed the text.
295	Mosque in Mahalla Ratanpur. Above the main entrance.	Mughal	Muḥammad Shāh	A.H. 1158 (& chronogram)= 1745-46 A.D.	Do. . . .	Records the construction of a mosque by Muḥammad Bandhū.
296	Chowk-ki-Masjid. Loose slab.			A.H. 1206= 1791-92 A.D.	Arabic, Naskh	Contains religious text (<i>Qur'ān</i> , Chapter II, verse 255).

297	Mosque in Roshan-Bāgh. On the facade.		A.H. 1156 (chronogram) =1743-44 A.D.	Persian verse, Nastā'liq .	Records the construction of a mosque by Mahābat Jang Ghāzi.
298	Tomb of Nawwāb Shujā'ud-Daula, same place. On the northern wall.		A.H. 1151 (& chronogram), Dhū'l-Hijja 13, Tuesday =1739 A.D., March 13 .	Do. . .	Records the death of Shujā'ud-Daula.
299	Above the southern entrance of a small Tomb near the above.		A.H. 1278 (& chronogram)= 1861-62 A.D.	Do. . .	Records the death of Shāh Ṣūfi Raḥmat 'Alī, a saint.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6336		Dr. E. Hultzsch	Quarter
6337		Do.	Do.
6338		Do.	Do.
6339		Rao Bahadur H. Krishna Sastri	Do.
6340		Do.	Do.
6341	Nālandā, Biharsharif sub-division, Nalanda District, Bihar.	Terracotta seal of Kumāragupta II (<i>Mem. A. S. I.</i> , No. 66, Plate VIII, e).	Do.
6342	Do.	Terracotta seal of Narasimhagupta (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate VIII b).	Do.
6343	Do.	Terracotta seal of Vainyagupta (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate VIII, f)	Do.
6344	Do.	Terracotta seal of Budhagupta (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate VIII, a).	Do.
6345	Do.	Terracotta seal of Kumāragupta II (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate VIII, d).	Do.
6346		Coin of Chattarāja of the Śilāhāra dynasty. Obverse (<i>J.R.A.S.</i> (1900), plate facing p. 97, No. 18).	Do.
6347		Do. Reverse (<i>ibid.</i> 2)	Do.
6348	Aihole, Hungund Taluk, Bijapur District, Karnatakā.	Inscription of Pulakēśin II, Śaka 556 (634-35 A.D.) <i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. VI, plate facing p. 6.	Do.
6349	Dāmōdarpur, Dinajpur District, Bangladesh.	Copper-plate Inscription, Gupta Year 214. (Plate i a) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 143).	Do.
6350	Do.	Do. (Plate i b). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6351	Do.	Copper-plate Inscription of Budhagupta (Plate i a) (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate facing p. 139).	Do.
6352	Do.	Do. (Plate i b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6353	Takkōlam, Arkonam Taluk, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Rājakēsarivarman (Āditya I). (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XIX, Plate facing p. 87).	Quarter
6354	Kottayam, Kottayam Taluk, Kottayam District, Kerala	Copper-plate grant of Virarāghava (Plate i a). <i>ibid.</i> , Vol. IV, plate facing p. 296.	Do.
6355	Do.	Do. (Plate i b). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6356	Ghumli, Jamnagar District, Gujarat	Copper-plate grant of the time of Agguka II, Gupta Year 513 (Plate i). (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XXVI, plate facing p. 200).	Do.
6357	Do.	Do. (Plate ii). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6358	Do.	Do. (Plate iii) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6359	Do.	Incomplete Copper-plate grant of king Rānaka. (Plate i). (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 210).	Do.
6360	Do.	Copper-plate grant of Rānaka of a subordinate Saindhava branch, Gupta Year 555 (plate i). (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 214).	Do.
6361	Do.	Do. (Plate ii). (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 215).	Do.
6362	Do.	Copper-plate grant of king Agguka III, Gupta year 567 (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 220).	Do.
6363	Do.	Do. (Plate ii). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6364	Do.	Copper-plate grant of king Jaika, Gupta Year 596 (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 224).	Do.
6365	Do.	Do. (Plate ii).	Do.
6366	Do.	Copper-plate grant of Jaika II (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 206).	Do.
6367	Do.	Do. (Plate ii) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6383	Prince of Wales Museum, Bombay. Maharashtra. Findspot : Not known.	Copper-plate grant of Rāshtrakūta Gōvinda III, Śaka 726. (Plate iia). (<i>ibid.</i> , 1962-63, A 13. <i>Ind. Ant.</i> , Vol. XI, plate facing p. 126).	Quarter
6384	Do.	Do. (Plate ii b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6385	Do.	Do. (Plate iii) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6386	Do.	Do. (Seal) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6387	Mathurā, Mathura Tahsil, Mathura District. Uttar Pradesh.	Lion Capital Inscription of Rañjuvula (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. II, Part II. Plate VIII. No. M.)	Do.
6388	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> Nos. B-D)	Do.
6389	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. J)	Do.
6390	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , Nos. I, J, H ¹ , H, M ³ and Q ²)	Do.
6391	Taxila, Pakistan	Silver scroll Inscription. Year 136. Original (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XIV)	Do.
6392	Do.	Do. Transcript	Do.
6393	Do.	Gold-plate Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XVII).	Do.
6394	Do.	Vase Inscription (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6395	Do.	Copper Ladle Inscription (<i>ibid.</i>).	Do.
6396	Do.	Bedadi Copper Ladle Inscription (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6397	Wadrak, Afghanistan	Vase Inscription, Year 51 (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate XXXIII).	Do.
6398	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6399	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6400	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6401	Ci-Aruton, Java, Indonesia	Rock Inscription in Shell Characters (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. XXII plate facing p. 4)	Quarter
6402	London, England	Copper plate grant of Vijayarājadēva (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 313).	Do.
6403	Mount Ābū, Abu Road Tahsil, Sirohi District, Rajasthan	Inscription of Luṅṭigadēva, Vikrama 1377 (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. IX, plate facing p. 79).	Do.
6404	Mathurā, Mathura Tahsil, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh	Jaina Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. II, No. 37, plate facing p. 209).	Do.
6405	Do.	Jaina Inscription engraved on the base of a small statue, year 57. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 38, plate facing p. 205).	Do.
6406	Do.	Inscription of Kumāragupta I, Gupta Year 113. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 39, plate facing p. 209).	Do.
6407	Do.	Jaina Inscription engraved on the back of a large broken slab, the surface of which is beautifully carved. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 40, plate facing p. 209).	Do.
6408	Do.	Jaina Inscription engraved on the base of a quadruple image of four sitting Jinas, Vikrama 1080 (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 41, plate facing p. 209).	Do.
6409	Do. Findspot : Kāman	Buddhist Inscription engraved on the base of the image of a large Buddha, Year 74 (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 42, plate facing p. 209).	Do.
6410	Nāgārjunakoṇḍa, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh	Āyaka Pillar Inscription of the reign of Virapurisadata, Year 6 (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XX, plate facing p. 18).	Do.
6411	Mēlkōte, Pandavapura Taluk, Mandya District, Karnataka.	Copper-plate grant of Krishnarāja Oḍeyār. (Plate iv b)(<i>MAR.</i> , 1947-56, plate LXXX.).	Do.
6412	Pushpagiri, a hamlet of Kotlūru, Cuddapah Taluk, Cuddapah District, Andhra Pradesh.	Vaidyanāthasvāmin temple Inscription of Yādava Singhana (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXX, plate facing p. 34).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6413	Śrivilliputtūr, Śrivilliputtūr Taluk, Ramanathapuram District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Śaḍaiyamāraṅ, Year 2+ 5 (<i>A.R.Ep.</i> , 1965-66, B. 285).	Quarter
6414	Girnar, Junagarh District, Gujarat.	Third Rock Edict of Aśoka (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. I, plate facing p. 10).	Do.
6415	Do.	Fourth Rock Edict of Aśoka (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6416	Do.	Fifth Rock Edict of Aśoka (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6417	Nidagundi, Shiggaon Taluk, Dharwar District, Karnataka	Inscription of the time of Vikramāditya VI and the Kadamba Taila II, 1107 A.D. (<i>Ep.Ind.</i> , Vol XIII, plate facing p. 14)	Do.
6418	New Delhi. Findspot : Compartmented verandah in front of cell No. 3, Ratnagiri, Jajpur Tahsil, Cuttack District, Orissa. No. RTR-2, 338.	Terracotta tablet <i>A.R.Ep.</i> , 1975-76. B 83).	Do.
6419	Do. Findspot : Cell No. 4 of monastery No. 1 Do.	Copper band with decorated triangular projections (<i>ibid.</i> , B 82).	Do.
6420	Basarh, Muzaffarpur District, Bihar.	Terracotta Seal of Dhruvasvāmini (<i>ASI.A.R.</i> , 1903-04, plate XL, No. 1).	Do.
6421	Kirārī, Bilaspur District, Madhya Pradesh.	Wooden Pillar Inscription, (No. I) (<i>Ep.</i> <i>Ind.</i> , Vol. XVIII, plate facing p. 156).	Do.
6422	Do.	Do. (No. II) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6423	Pāngurāria, Budhni Tahsil, Sehore District, Madhya Pradesh.	Minor Rock Edict of Aśoka (<i>A.R.Ep.</i> , 1975-76, B 160).	Do.
6424	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6425	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6426	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6427	Udaipur, Basoda Tahsil, Vidisha District, Madhya Pradesh.	Incomplete eulogy of Sun-god engraved on a slab fixed in the front wall of an old disused shrine near the Udayēśvara temple (<i>ibid.</i> , B 161).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6428	Nālandā, Bihar Sharif Sub-division, Nalanda District, Bihar.	Inscription of Prathamaśiva <i>alias</i> Pūrṇavarman engraved on a stone slab (<i>ibid.</i> , B 72).	Quarter
6429	Hampi, Hospet Taluk, Bellary District, Karnataka.	Brāhmī Inscription engraved on a lime stone block (<i>ibid.</i> , B 94).	Do.
6430	Oorakam, Trichur Taluk, Trichur District, Kerala.	Vatteḷuttu Inscription in the Bhagavati temple (<i>ibid.</i> , B 152).	Do.
6431	Vallam, Thanjavur Taluk, Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu	Inscription of Rājarāja I. Year 16 found in the Ē gauriyamma temple (<i>ibid.</i> , B 259).	Do.
6432	Chējerla, Narasaraopet Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Telugu Inscription on a slab in a field on a cart track (S.N. 267,2 (<i>ibid.</i> , B 2).	Do.
6433	Kondappanāyakkappatti, hamlet of Nariyanēri Tiruppattur Taluk, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Tamil Inscription engraved on a slab in a field on a cart track (S.N. 267,2) (<i>ibid.</i> , B 247).	Do.
6434	Chejerla, Narasaraopet Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Telugu Inscription on another face of an octagonal shaft excavated from the basement around the central shrine (<i>ibid.</i> , B 7).	Do.
6435	Do.	Telugu Inscription on the square face of the above mentioned pillar excavated from the basement around the central shrine (<i>ibid.</i> , B 9).	Do.
6436	Pillaiyārpatti, Tirupattur Taluk, Ramnad District, Tamil Nadu.	Vatteḷuttu Inscription on the extreme left pilaster in the Kāśi-Viśvanātha temple (<i>ibid.</i> , 1935-36, B 156).	Do.
6437	Ellappudaiyānpatti, Harur Taluk, Dharmapuri District, Tamil Nadu.	Vatteḷuttu Inscription on a hero-stone in the Maṇavālkuttai-Vēdiyappa temple. (<i>ibid.</i> , 1975-76, B 219).	Do.
6438	Eḍattanūr, Chengam Taluk, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Mahēndravarmaṇ [I] on a herostone in the Vēdiyappa temple on the bank of the Pennār (<i>ibid.</i> , 1971-72, B 220).	Do.
6439	Hēmāvati, Madakasira Taluk, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscription on a pillar in front of the Henjerapa temple, (First Face). (S.I.I., Vol.VI, plate V facing p. 198).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6440	Junāgarh, Junagarh District, Gujarat.	Inscription of Jivadāman (I) (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XVIII, plate facing p. 340).	Quarter
6441	Shinkot, Bajaur Tribal Territory, Afghanistan.	Steatite Casket Inscription of the time of Menader and Vijayamitra, Year 5 (Inscriptions B and D) (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XXIV, plate facing p. 7).	Do.
6442	British Museum, London, England.	Inscription of the time of Kanishka [Year 10]	Do.
6443	Kahāum, Gorakhpur District, Uttar Pradesh.	Stone Pillar Inscription of Skandagupta, Gupta Year 141, <i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. III, plate IX-A facing p. 68).	Do.
6444	National Museum, Bangkok, Thailand.	Inscription of Mahēndravarma (Ep. Ind., Vol. XXVI plate facing p. 112).	Do.
6455	...	Palaeographical Chart showing the development of the letter 'Śa' (<i>Indian Palaeography and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurti, fig. 51, p. 143).	Do.
6446	Brahmagiri, Chitradurga District, Karnataka.	Minor Rock Edict of Aśoka (Lower Half) <i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. I, plate facing p. 177.	Do.
6447	...	The standard shape of Aśokan Brāhmī Script (<i>The History and Palaeography of Mauryan Brāhmī script</i> by C.S. Upasak, plate facing p. 318).	Do.
6448	Nāgārjunakonda, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Āyaka Pillar Inscription (B 2) of the reign of Virapurisadata, Year 6. (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XX, plate facing p. 17).	Do.
6449	Mathurā, Mathura Tahsil, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh.	Pillar Inscription of Huvishka, Year 28 (<i>Select Inscriptions</i> , Second edition, plate XXVII).	Do.
6450	Duwe Gala, Srilanka.	Brāhmī Inscription inside a cave (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XLIII).	Do.
6451	Sārnāth, Varanasi District, Uttar Pradesh.	Buddhist Image Inscription of the time of Kanishka Year 3 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. VIII, plate iii a facing p. 176).	Do.
6452	Sāñchi, Vidisha District, Madhya Pradesh.	Stone Inscription of Chandragupta II, Gupta Year 93 (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. III, plate iii b facing p. 28).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6453	Rummindēi, Nepal.	Minor Pillar Inscription of Aśōka (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. I, plate facing p. 164).	Quarter
6454	Nāsik, Nasik District, Maharashtra.	Inscription of Ābhīra Īsvarasēna, Year 9 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. VIII, No. 15, plate facing p. 88).	Do.
6455	Nāgārjuni Hill, Gaya District, Bihar.	Inscription of Daśaratha (<i>Ind Ant.</i> , Vol. XX, No. D, plate facing p. 362.)	Do.
6456	Bhāṭṭiprōlu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh.	Alphabet of the Bhāṭṭiprōlu Inscriptions. (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. II, plate facing p. 329).	Do.
6457	Konḍrahalli Nandaguḍi, Hosakote Taluk, Bangalore District, Karnataka.	Sāliggāmē Grant of the Gaṅga king Konguṇi Muttarasa (Plate Ia) (<i>M A.R.</i> , 1941, Plate facing p. 128).	Do.
6458	Do.	Do. (Plate Ib) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6459	Do.	Do. (Plate IIa) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6460	Do.	Do. (Plate II b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6461	Do.	Do. (Plate III a) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 130).	Do.
6462	Do.	Do. (Plate III b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6463	Do.	Do. (Plate IV a) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6464	Do.	Do. (Plate IV b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6465	Do.	Do. (Seal), (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6466	Nāgārjunakoṇḍa, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscription on a memorial pillar (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXV, No. 6A, plate facing p. 14).	Do.
6467	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter (a) (<i>Indian Palaeography and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurty, fig. 20, p. 57).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6468	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'i' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 22, p. 61).	Quarter
6469	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'u' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 24, p. 66).	Do.
6470	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'e' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 25, p. 68).	Do.
6471	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ka' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 32, p. 84).	Do.
6472	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'kha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 33, p. 88).	Do.
6373	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ga' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 34, p. 90).	Do.
6474	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'gha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 35, p. 92).	Do.
6475	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ña' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 36, p. 95).	Do.
6476	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'cha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 37, p. 97).	Do.
6477	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'chha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 38, p. 99).	Do.
6478	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ja' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 39, p. 101).	Do.
6479	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ña' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 40, p. 103).	Do.
6480	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ta' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 41, p. 105).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6481	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'da'. (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 42, p. 107).	Quarter
6482	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'dha'. (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 43, p. 109).	Do.
6483	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ṇa'. (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 44, p. 110).	Do.
6484	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ta' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 45, p. 112).	Do.
6485	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'tha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 46, p. 114).	Do.
6486	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'da'. (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 47, p. 117).	Do.
6487	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'dha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 48, p. 119).	Do.
6488	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'na' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 49, p. 120).	Do.
6489	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'pa' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 50, p. 122).	Do.
6490	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'pha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 51, p. 125).	Do.
6491	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ba' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 52, p. 127).	Do.
6492	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'bha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 53, p. 129).	Do.
6493	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ma' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 54, p. 131).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6494	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ya' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 55, p. 133).	Quarter
6495	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ra' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 56, p. 135).	Do.
6496	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'la' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 57, p. 138).	Do.
6497	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'va' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 58, p. 140).	Do.
6498	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'śa' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. p59. 142).	Do.
6499	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'sha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 60, p. 145).	Do.
6500	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'sa' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 61, p. 147).	Do.
6501	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ha' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 62, p. 149).	Do.
6502	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ja' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 63, p. 151).	Do.
6503	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'la' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 64, p. 152).	Do.
6504	...	Palaeographical chart showing the development of the letter 'ra' (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 65, p. 154).	Do.
6505	Bhattiprōlu, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Casket Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 67, p. 156).	Do.
6506	Sittannavāśal, Tiruchchirapalli District, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmi Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 68, p. 158).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6507	Sārṅāth, Varanasi District, Uttar Pradesh	Buddhist Image Inscription of Kani-shka, Year 3 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 69, p. 159).	Quarter
6508	Nāsik, Nasik District, Maharashtra.	Inscription of Ushavadāta (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 70, p. 160).	Do.
6509	Junāgarh, Junagarh District, Gujarat.	Inscription of Rudradāman I (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 71, p. 162).	Do.
6510	Nāgārjunakoṇḍa, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Āyaka Pillar Inscription of Sirivirapuri-sadata, Year 6 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 73, p. 164).	Do.
6511	Sārṅāth, Varanasi District, Uttar Pradesh.	Buddhist Image Inscription of Kani-shka, Year 6, (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 69, p. 159).	Do.
6512	Sittāṅṅavāśal, Tiruchchirappalli-District, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmī Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 68, p. 158).	Do.
6513	Bhaṭṭīprōlu, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Casket Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 67, p. 156).	Do.
6514	Pārḍī, Surat District, Gujarat.	Copper-plate grant of Dharasēna, [Kalachuri-Chēdi] Year 207 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. X, plate facing p. 51).	Do.
6515	Allahabad, Allahabad District, Uttar Pradesh.	Pillar Inscription of Samudragupta (<i>Indian Palaeography and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurty, fig. 78, p. 171).	Do.
6516	Ēran, Sagar District, Madhya Pradesh.	Inscription of Samudragupta (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 79, p. 172).	Do.
6517	Majhgawam, Satna District, Madhya Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of <i>Mahārāja</i> Hastin, Gupta Year 191 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 81, p. 172).	Do.
6518	Mandasor, Mandasor District, Madhya Pradesh.	Inscription of Yaśōdharman (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 82, p. 173).	Do.
6519	State Archaeological Museum, Lucknow, Lucknow Tahsil, Lucknow District, Uttar Pradesh. Findspot : Banaskhera, Shahjahanpur District, Uttar Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Harshavardhana [Year 22] (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 83, p. 175).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6520	Bilsad, Etah District, Uttar Pradesh.	Inscription of Kumāragupta, Gupta Year 96 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 80, p. 172).	Quarter
6521	Dighwa Dubauli, Formerly Bombay Presidency.	Copper-plate grant of <i>Mahārāja</i> Mahēndrapāla [Harsha] Saṁvat, 125 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 85, p. 178).	Do.
6522	Chandrāvati, Varanasi District, Uttar Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Chandradēva Vikrama 1156 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 86, p. 719).	Do.
6523	Banswara, Banswara District, Rajasthan.	Copper-plate grant of Bhōjadēva, Vikrama 1076 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 87, p. 181).	Do.
6524	Government Museum, Madras, Tamil Nadu. Findspot : Not known.	Copper-plate grant belonging to Kaliṅga (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 89, p. 183).	Do.
6525	Śāluvanguppam, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription on the Atiraṇa Chandēśvara Cave temple (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 90, p. 185).	Do.
6526	Pattadakal, Badami Taluk, Bijapur District, Karnataka.	Inscription of Kīrtivarman II (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 93, p. 189).	Do.
6527	Sitābāldi, Nagpur District, Maharashtra.	Inscription of the time of Vikramāditya VI, Śaka 1008 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 95, p. 191).	Do.
6528	Thana, Thana District, Maharashtra.	Copper-plate grant of Yādava king Rāmachandra, Śaka 1194 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 96, p. 192).	Do.
6529	Satyamaṅgalam, Vellore Taluk, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Dēvarāya II, Śaka 1346 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 97, p. 193).	Do.
6530	Tālagunda, Shikaripur Taluk, Shimoga District, Karnataka.	Pillar Inscription of Kākusthavarman (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 99, p. 196).	Do.
6531	Rāgōlu, Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Śaktivarman (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 101, p. 198).	Do.
6532	Achyutāpuram, Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Indrarvarman (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 103, p. 200).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6533	Penukonda, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Mādhava II (III) (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 106, p. 203).	Quarter
6534	Palitānā, Bhavnagar District, Gujarat.	Copper-plate grant of Dhruvasēna I. (Set I), Valabhi samvat 210 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 107, p. 204).	Do.
6535	Bādāmi, Bijapur District, Karnataka.	Inscription of Maṅgalēsa (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 108, p. 205).	Do.
6536	Nilgunda, Harpanahalli Taluk, Bellary District, Karnataka.	Copper-plate grant of Amōghavarsha, (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 109, p. 206).	Do.
6537	Hūli, Parasgad Taluk, Belgaum District, Karnataka.	Inscription belonging to the reign of Vikramāditya, Year 6 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 110, p. 207).	Do.
6538	Bēfūr, Belur Taluk, Hassan District, Karnataka.	Copper-plate grant of Hoysaḷa Ballāḷa- dēva, (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 111, p. 208).	Do.
6539	Chikkulḷa, Tuni Taluk, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Vikramēndravar- man II, [Year 10] (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 113, p. 211).	Do.
6540	Timmāpuram, Sarvasiddhi Taluk, Visakhapatnam District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Viṣṇuvarhana I Viṣhamasiddhi. (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 114, p. 212).	Do.
6541	Māchilipatnam, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Vijayāditya III (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 115, p. 213).	Do.
6542	Vandram, Bhimavaram Taluk, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Ammarāja II (Plate iii) (<i>ibid.</i> fig. 116, p. 214).	Do.
6543	Chēbrōlu, Bapatla Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Nāgēsvara Temple Inscription of Śaka 1135 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 118, p. 217).	Do.
6544	Phiraṅgipuram, Sattenapalle Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Virabhadrasvāmin Temple Inscription of Pedda-Kōmativēma, Śaka 1331 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 119, p. 219).	Do.
6545	Hampi, Hospet Taluk, Bellary District, Karnataka.	Stone Inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 120, p. 221).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6546	Kāñchīpuram, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Rājasīmha in the Kailāsanātha temple (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 123, p. 224).	Quarter
6547	Kūram, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Paramēśvaravarman (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 124, p. 225).	Do.
6548	Kāsākuḍi, Pondicherry.	Copper-plate grant of Nandivarman Pallavamalla (Plate i) (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 215, p. 227).	Do.
6549	Tiruvellaṅgai, Tiruchirapalli District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Dantivarman (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 126, p. 228).	Do.
6550	Government Museum, Madras, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Uttamachōḷa (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 128, p. 230).	Do.
6551	Tirukkaḷuṅṅam, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Kulōttuṅga I, Year 42 (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 131, p. 233).	Do.
6552	Tiruvālaṅgāḍu, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Rājēndrachōḷa (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 129, p. 231).	Do.
6553	Government Museum, Madras, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Śrīgiribhūpāla, Śaka 1346, (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 132, p. 234).	Do.
6554	Āṇaimalai, Madurai District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Māṅaṅjaḍaiyan (<i>ibid.</i> , fig. 133, p. 236).	Do.
6555	Tiruvālaṅgāḍu, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate grant of Rājēndra Chōla (Seal) <i>ibid.</i> , Plate ii b).	Do.
6556	Chikkūḷa, Tuni Taluk, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh.	Seal and plates of Viṣṇukuṅḍi Vikramēndravarmān and seal of an Eastern Chālukya Copper-plate grant (<i>ibid.</i> , plate III a, b, c).	Do.
6557	Sātālūr, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh	Copper-plate grant of Eastern Chālukya king Vijayāditya III (<i>ibid.</i> , plate IV).	Do.
6558	Kalambākkam, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription of Rājarāja (<i>ibid.</i> , plate VIII a).	Do.
6559	Vijayawāḍa, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh.	Eastern Chālukyan Inscription on the back of a <i>dvārapālaka</i> (<i>ibid.</i> , plate IX c).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6560	Jaugada, Puri District, Orissa.	Rock Edict of Aśoka (Portion) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate V a)	Quarter
6561	Bhattiprōlu, Repalle Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscribed stone reliquary (<i>ibid.</i> , plate V b).	Do.
6562	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate V c).	Do.
6563	Mohenjodaro, Pakistan	Steatite Seal (<i>Indian Epigraphy</i> by D. C. Sircar, Plate I, No. 1).	Do.
6564	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 2).	Do.
6565	Jaggayyapēta, Nandigama Taluk, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh.	Brāhmī Inscription of about the 3rd century A.D. (<i>Indian Epigraphy and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurthy, pl. VI c.)	Do.
6566	Amarāvati, Sattenapalle Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Brāhmī Inscription of about the 2nd century A.D. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate VI b).	Do.
6567	Kāñchīpuram, Chingleput District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscription containing Sūryaśataka on a derelict Sūryamaṇḍapa in Kachchapēśvara temple. (<i>ibid.</i> , Plate IX b.)	Do.
6868	Addanki, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Early Eastern Chālukyan inscription of the 9th century. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate X a).	Do.
6569	Rajahmundry, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh.	Later Eastern Chālukyan inscription of the 11th century. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate X b).	Do.
6570	Nālandā, Nalanda District, Bihar.	Clay seal from Nālandā (<i>Indian Epigraphy</i> by D.C. Sircar Plate I. No. 3).	Do.
6571	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , (Plate II, No. 3).	Do.
6572	Kirārī, Bilaspur District, Madhya Pradesh.	Brāhmī inscription on a wooden pillar (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XVIII, plate between pp. 156-57).	Do.
6573	Lauriya-Nandangarh, Champaran District, Bihar.	Aśōkan pillar edicts. (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. I, pp. 145 ff).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6574	Mehrauli, New Delhi.	Iron pillar inscription of Chandra (C.I.I., Vol. III, plate between pp. 142-43).	Quarter
6575	Śravanabelagola, Hassan District, Karnataka	Stone pillar inscription (<i>Indian Epigraphy</i> by D.C. Sircar, plate X).	Do.
6576	Mathura, Mathura District, Uttar Pradesh.	Nāga pedestal inscription of Kanishka, year 8 (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XI).	Do.
6577	Banavāsi, Sirsi Taluk, North Kanara District, Karnataka.	Inscription of Vinhukada Sātakaṇṇi, year 12 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXIV, plate between pp. 240-41).	Do.
6578	Lucknow, Luknow District, Uttar Pradesh.	Takshaka image inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XXX, plate facing p. 240).	Do.
6579	Mallam, Gudur Taluk, Gudur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Stone inscription of Pallava Kāmpavarman (<i>S.I.I.</i> , Vol. XII, plate facing p. 50).	Do.
6580	Kalakaḍa, Vayalpad Taluk, Chitoor District Andhra Pradesh.	Inscription of Gaṇḍatriṇētra Vaidumbamahārāja (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XII, plate facing p. 279).	Do.
6581	Śālihuṇḍam, Srikakulam District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscribed Conchshell (<i>Indian Epigraphy</i> by D.C. Sircar, plate XVIII).	Do.
6582	Naṇḍūru, Bapatla Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscribed earthen pot. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XIX).	Do.
6583	Jagatgram, Dehradun District, Uttar Pradesh.	A brick containing the inscription of Śilavarman (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XIX).	Do
6584	Sanokhār, Go 'da Sub-division, Santal Parganas District, Bihar.	Inscribed copper cover of Valāśeṇa, (Ballāśeṇa), year 9 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. II, plate facing p. 82).	Do.
6585	Lalguḍi, Tiruchchirapalli District, Tamil Nadu.	Inscribed walls etc. of the Saptariṣṭśvara temple (<i>Indian Epigraphy</i> by D.C. Sircar, plate XXIII).	Do.
6586	Tippera, Tippera District, Bangla Desh.	Copper plate inscription of Lōkanātha, year 44 (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XXVI).	Do.
6587	Udayēndiram, Gudiyattam Taluk, North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu.	Copper-plate set of Ganga Prithvipati II Hastimalla (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XXVIII).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6588	Asirgadh, Nimar District, Madhya Pradesh.	Bronze seal of Śarvavarma-Maukhari (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XXX).	Quarter
6589	British Museum, London	Crystal seal of Avarighsa (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XXXVI).	Do.
6590	Vidisha, Vidisha District, Madhya Pradesh.	Three inscriptions of Rāmagupta (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> Vol. XXXVI, pp. 46 ff.)	Do.
6591	Mehrauli, New Delhi.	Iron pillar inscription of Chandra (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. III, plate between pp. 142-43).	Do.
6592	Erragudi, Pattikonda Taluk, Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh.	Rock edicts of Aśoka (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXII, plate facing p. 7).	Do.
6593	Ānekannambīdi, Holenarasipur Taluk, Hassan District, Karnataka.	Copper plate grant of Hoysala Narasimha (Plate II a) <i>A.R. Ep.</i> , 1975-76, No. 1).	Do.
6594	Do.	Do. (Plate II b) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6595		Evolution of letter <i>ā</i> (<i>Indian Epigraphy and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurty, p. 57).	Do.
6596		Evolution of letter <i>va</i> (<i>ibid.</i> , p. 133).	Do.
6597		Kushāṇa and Gupta characters.	Do.
6598		Gupta characters.	Do.
6599	...	Development of the letter <i>a</i> (<i>Indian Epigraphy and South Indian Scripts</i> by C. Sivaramamurty, p. 59).	Do.
6600		Development of the letter <i>ka</i> (<i>ibid.</i> , p. 8).	Do.
6601	Nāgārjunakoṇḍa, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Āyaka pillar inscription of the reign of Virapurisadata, year 6 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XX, plate facing p. 19).	Do.
6602	Do.	Foot print slab inscription (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XXXII, plate facing p. 250).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6603	Nāgārjunakoṇḍa, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 251).	Quarter
6604	Do.	Inscribed conch shells (<i>Ind. Arch. A Review</i> , 1958-59, plate V B).	Do.
6605	Reṅṅāla, Palnad Taluk, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Pillar inscription of Siri-Chantamūla I, Year 5 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXVII, plate facing p. 31).	Do.
6606	Śittanpavāśal, Tiruchchirappalli District, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmī inscription in the cave. (<i>A.R. Ep.</i> , 1914, No. 388).	Do.
6607	Kunnakkudi, Ramanathapuram District, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmī inscription in a cave (<i>ibid.</i> , 1909, No. 44).	Do.
6608	Mēttuppatti, Madurai District, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmī inscription in a cavern (<i>ibid.</i> , 1908, No. 45).	Do.
6609	Tiruparaṅkuṅgam, Tamil Nadu.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , No. 334).	Do.
6610	Koṅgar-Puliyaṅguḷam, Tamil Nadu.	Brāhmī inscription in a cave (<i>ibid.</i> , 1910, No. 56).	Do.
6611	Tanjore, Tanjore District, Tamil Nadu.	Seal of Karandai Plates of Rājendra-chōla, year 8 (Side View) (<i>ibid.</i> , 1949-50, No. 57).	Do.
6612	Do.	Do. (Back view) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6613	Do.	Do. (With ring) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6614	Do.	Do. (Ring with seal) (<i>ibid.</i>).	Do.
6615	Allahabad, Allahabad District Uttar Pradesh	Queen's Edict (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. I, p. 159).	Do.
6616	Mandasore, Mandasore District, Madhya Pradesh.	Stone inscription of Mālava Saṃvat 524 (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXVII, plate facing p. 15).	Do.
6617	Sārnāth, Benaras District, Uttar Pradesh.	Image inscription of Kumāragupta and Budhagupta (<i>A.R., A.S.I.</i> , 1914-15, plate LXIX).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—Contd.

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6618	Bhavnagar, Bhavnagar District, Gujarat.	Copper-plate grant of Śilāditya IV (Plate ib).	Quarter
6619	Do.	Do. (Plate ii a).	Do.
6620	Do.	Do. (Plate iii b).	Do.
6621	Māndhātā, Burhanpur Tahsil, East Nimar District, Madhya Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Paramāra Jayasimha-Jayavarman, V.S. 1331 (Plate i b) (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XXXII, pp. 139 ff. and plate).	Do.
6622	Do.	Do. (Plate ii a). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6623	Do.	Do. (Plate ii b). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6624	Do.	Do. (Plate iii a). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6625	Do.	Do. (Plate iii b). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6626	Do.	Do. (Plate iv a). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6627	Do.	Do. (Plate iv b). (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6628	Gīrnār, Junagarh District, Gujarat.	Aśōkan edicts (<i>C.I.I.</i> Vol. I, plate facing p. 4).	Do.
6629	Do.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 22).	Do.
6630	Kālsi, Dehra Dun District, Uttar Pradesh.	Do. (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 44).	Do.
6631	Khoh, Satna District, Madhya Pradesh	Copper-plate inscription of mahārāja Jayanātha, year 177 (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. III, plate XVII).	Do.
6632	Do.	Copper plate inscription of mahārāja Śarvanātha, year 193 (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XVIII).	Do.
6633	Do.	Copper plate inscription of mahārāja Śarvanātha (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XIX A).	Do.
6634	Do.	Do., year 197 (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XIX B).	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Contd.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6635	Do.	Do. year 214 (<i>ibid.</i> , plate XX).	Quarter
6636	Yerragudi, Kurnool District, Andhra Pradesh.	Aśōkan edict (General view).	Do.
6637	Do.	Do. (Right Half).	Do.
6638	Do.	Do. (Left Half).	Do.
6639	Penugonda Taluk, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper plate inscription of Western Gaṅga Mādhava II (III ?) (Plates I and II a) (<i>Ep. Ind.</i> , Vol. XIV, plate facing p. 334).	Do.
6640	Do.	Do. (Plates II b and III and seal) (<i>ibid.</i> , plate facing p. 335).	Do.
6641	Sogal, Paragad Taluk, Belgaum District, Karnataka	Inscription of the reign of Taila II, Śaka 902 (Upper half) (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XVI, plate facing p. 4).	Do.
6642	Do.	Do. (Lower half) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.
6643	Sōpāra, Thana District, Maharashtra.	Aśōkan edict (IX) (<i>ibid.</i> , Vol. XXXII, pp. 29 ff and plate).	Do.
6644	Do.	Aśōkan edict (VIII) (<i>C.I.I.</i> , Vol. I, p. 118).	Do.
6645	Warangal, Warangal District, Andhra Pradesh.	Inscription of Kākatiya Vira Rudra (<i>A.R. Ep.</i> , 1957-58, No. B 57).	
6646	Do.	Inscription on the eastern gateway of the fort (<i>ibid.</i> , No. B 56).	Do.
6647	Berhampur, Ganjam District, Orissa.	Seal of the Copper plate inscription of the Nala king Bhīmasēna (<i>ibid.</i> , 1959-60, No. A 62).	Do.
6648	Do.	Copper plate grant of the Nala king Bhīmasēna (Plate I) (<i>ibid.</i>)	Do.

E.—LIST OF PHOTOGRAPHS, 1975-76—*Concl.*

Sl. No.	Locality	Description	Size of Negative
6649	Do.	Do. (Plate II a) (<i>ibid.</i>) . . .	Quarter
6650	Do.	Do. (Plate II b) (<i>ibid.</i>) . . .	Do.
6651	Do.	Do. (Plate III b) (<i>ibid.</i>) . . .	Do.
6652	Dāvanagere, Chitradurga District, Karnataka.	Copper-plate grant of Kadamba Ravi-varma (<i>M.A.R.</i> , 1933, plate XXII).	Do.
6653	Guntur, Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh.	Copper-plate grant of Vishṇukuṇḍin Vikramēndrabhattāarakavarman, year 14 (<i>A.R.Ep.</i> , 1956-57, No. A I).	Do.

निविद्यातासिल विद्याया यदा वा
 माय्युपसृष्टीया विद्याया तयद्वन
 तामनरुसायुष्युन्यनियवपत्यसासा
 कलसीपमिवापिकवायुठविमापमव
 सकपात्रमित्रगुणानामसिहादवाताया
 मबुजावतदारुयाभूदत्राशयाहाइसगा
 यदलकुयास्याद्वगतसमस्रकरकेव
 यद्यादामवासाकसापीलाजाबुपुननि
 ययवसुवनामपुनगाधिपायायस्रकन
 पंभुमागिललनागाडिकपलीगिलसत
 मातिष्टतासहस्रवदनिर्घदीवलागायति
 धापवायाधिखानसमाकुशेपिवशित
 श्रीयायुधिरेत्रिनामत्रानामिवशात्रवावि
 पुत्राकुनष्टलानशिपुसुजाजालवडुहा
 लीकृतयाशादिदुकिपत्सवतसम्यसिहा
 पाकमस्रगतवानधुधनामाथयः॥यना
 शिषकलाविलासकीतिनाघाउयावना

वरुणसर्वाथुन कर्मनिर्मितिप
 पीपाकाकवथा रिताभाद्ययधव
 गीसिवापचितोयनस्रघपी तितोदवा
 इमजलधवलमुविमथात्रयहाउदइया
 ॥३॥ सुसिसमस्रवुवनाशुधीष्टधीवस
 मस्रमयनाधिगस्रपयतिश्रवपमनदा
 पंक्यादवकुलाबपस्रमणिसर्वहस्र
 मागिमालपानुनमलपामुगंडकद
 नस्रघंडपकांगवीचयसहायस्रपुल्लक
 यनेनानिनीजानिमयस्रिपिदुधमस
 स्रपिहादुधमस्रानिबवसिधिनयदिश
 दबुधिसयाजनीमसावीनामथीमदिस
 वहनप्रतापवकवतिहोस्रगामुडवल
 वीयथीनापसिहादवालानायावना
 यजत्रयाजनाद्ययनाद्यापनदानपा
 थरनास्रत्यातकविद्याविशापदत्याथि
 तस्मात्रकवाकुशलत्यावमनिपति

न्यायीतिसंख्यासं स्याताद्याबाहा
 णयशकस्यिक चत्वापिशद्वपय
 ताधिकसहास्रबहुवाहासवसापास
 गासासाभयहाणयतिनामधयद्वे
 पुममहायहापनिविनिवदियतेयुना
 यातुसाभ्यसर्वबाधपपिनापसवस्र
 स्यवापिवापपूर्वकसत्रियापिथावा
 तत्रवपुष्टदादिशोडकयद्वेनास
 यानस्यवाहयाभाधिपातनवावत
 कशवस्यवाहबाहाणनामशीतिवि
 उाधिकाशीतिवृत्रयः॥३॥ तास्य
 मानः॥ मूडलुतस्रगट्टमूडगाका
 पाअलिदपदकणादबेधलुपूर्वदनेक
 याअनतपग्रेयदलुहालयअपलिध
 पत्रांतकलुयमदतवताअलिदप
 सापिधमनागलात्रभिलाकाल

निअतदलुम लोकिविधरभापय
 वरुणसर्वाथुन विघतलहिजहला
 वायद्यदलुवालयनहालुवदगलुहिपि
 यकमीगबदहिप्रिधरसाशीशान्यदलु
 लपिगाडतनेस्रपारयणहिप्रिधर
 णिस्रयस्रपनुअलिदवपलुवालसमुड
 देपि॥ इतिप्रसिधसीमानासामाह्या
 यवस्रस्रवृपाणाकालकालपाल
 नोऽपामवद्वि॥ सवीनतात्राविनापिध्व
 वस्रयायायाघातपमिवद॥ सुदत्रां
 वस्रयायाहापतवसुधपा॥ धर्ववस्रसह
 आणविस्रयाजायातकिमि॥३॥
 ॥श्रीबीधनपसिंददवस्या॥

CHEJERLA BRAHMI INSCRIPTION (B 7)

MATHURA INSCRIPTION OF KANISHKA, YEAR 5 (B 79)

HAMPI BRAHMI INSCRIPTION (B 394)

HAMPI KANNADA INSCRIPTION, CHALUKYA VIKRAMA YEAR 1 (B 95)

PLATE VII

MUTTAGE INSCRIPTION OF RASHTRAKUTA KRISHNA III (B 111)

(a) EPITAPH OF KHWAJA MUBASHSHAR FROM DELHI (D 76)

(b) INSCRIPTION OF HUSAIN SHAH FROM SUATA (D 263)

